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MARINA

**Marine Knowledge Sharing Platform for Federating
Responsible Research and Innovation Communities**

Grant Agreement No. 710566

D3.3 Comprehensive Report on Local MML Workshops

(Phase Two)

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Abstract	D3.3 provides a comprehensive description and the results of the twenty local Mobilization and Mutual Learning (MML) workshops organized during the second phase of the MARINA project MML workshops, which were implemented between January and March 2018.
Title and number of connected deliverables	Grant Agreement of the MARINA project D2.1 Criteria for identifying, collecting, analysing and extracting information from sources and Taxonomy D.2.2 Databases and Ontology Definition D3.1 MML Workshop Methodology Approach and Actor Inclusion Criteria D.4.2 The Marina Web Knowledge Sharing Platform

<p>Explain Deliverable Dependency/ Connection</p>	<p>D3.1 defined a methodological approach and stakeholder involvement principles to assist MARINA partners in organising the workshops in the framework of the Mobilisation and Mutual Learning process at the national and international levels, thus setting foundations for the D3.3.</p> <p>The Grant Agreement described the societal and marine challenges, the socio-technical approach and the RRI dimensions to be discussed and taken into account in the expected results of the MML workshops.</p> <p>The D.3.3 benefited from the D2.2 Databases and Ontology Definition in terms of stakeholder identification to engage in the local MML workshops.</p> <p>The D3.3 and more particularly T3.2 contributed to populating the Marina Web Knowledge Sharing Platform as described in D.4.2.</p>
<p>Title of connected external documents</p>	<p>Hot topic templates of local MML workshops R2 Individual reports of local workshops R2</p>

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List of abbreviations

AAU	Aalborg University
AHHAA	Shitasutus Teaduskeskus AHHAA
APRE	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea
BWMC	Ballast Water Management Convention
BWTS	Ballast Water Treatment Systems
CIC nanoGUNE	Asociacion – Centro de Investigacion Cooperativa en Nanociencias CIC-nanoGUNE
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
CNTI	Cyprus Neuroscience & Technology Institute
DSM	Deep-sea mining
EurOcean	Fundação EurOcean
FRCT	Fundo Regional Para a Ciência e Tecnologia
IOPAN	Institute of Oceanology of the Polish Academy of Sciences
IAS	Invasive Alien Species
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
ISPRA	Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale
IU	Istanbul Universitesi
Mare Nostrum	Organizatia Ecologista Neguvernamentală Mare Nostrum
MML workshop	Mobilisation and Mutual Learning workshop
MSP	Marine Spatial Planning
Nausicaa	Société d'Exploitation du Centre national de la Mer
NIRD GeoEcoMar	National Institute for Research and Development of Marine Geology and Geoecology
NIS	Non Indigenous Species
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OMM	Osservatorio del Mare a Molfetta
ROM WON	Réseau Océan Mondial – World Ocean Network
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
Sciencethics	Institute of Science and Ethics
SEVEN	SEVEN Solutions for the Environment Sustainable Engineering
SmartBay	SmartBay Ireland Limited
TSS	Turkish Strait System
UCC	University College Cork
XPRO	XPRO Consulting Limited

1 Purpose of this Deliverable

The purpose of the Deliverable 3.3 is to provide a comprehensive description of the 20 Local Mobilization and Mutual Learning (MML) workshops, which have been organized by the MARINA partners and associated partners in the context of the second round of MML workshops and have taken place between January and March 2018. The following eleven European Member States hosted the workshops: Cyprus, Denmark, Estonia, France, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Poland, Portugal, Romania, and Spain; and Turkey.

The MML workshops constitute an integral element of the MARINA project for federating communities in familiarizing and adapting Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) in the marine sectors. The workshops engaged a multidisciplinary group of participants including citizens, researchers, business people and policymakers in an attempt to identify actions and solutions towards current and emerging marine and societal challenges.

The workshop results, together with the results of other MARINA workshops across Europe, will be:

- Freely accessible on the [MARINA Knowledge Sharing Platform](#) for anyone interested in marine and coastal issues and RRI;
- Shared with other collaborative projects and likeminded initiatives;
- Presented and discussed at related marine and RRI national and international events;
- Taken forward to shape the next steps of the project and to inform future policy and research;
- Reported to the European Commission.

2 Executive Summary

The main objective of the deliverable D3.3 is to provide a comprehensive description of the 20 Mobilisation and Mutual Learning (MML) workshops organised as part of the MARINA project. These workshops were organized by 14 MARINA partners and 7 associated partners across twelve European countries from January to March 2018.

The workshops succeeded in engaging 443 participants from a diverse spectrum of stakeholders, including citizens, NGOs representatives, researchers, business representatives and policymakers who shared knowledge to define actions to tackle the following five marine societal challenges: Marine Biotechnology, Renewable Energy, Sea Transportation, Marine Changes Caused by Climate, and Deep-sea Mining.

The overarching goal of the workshops was the development of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) roadmaps of actions. RRI is a transparent, interactive process in which societal actors and innovators become mutually responsive to each other with a view on the (ethical) acceptability, sustainability and societal desirability of the innovation process and its marketable products¹. The European Commission distinguishes six key dimensions of RRI: *Public Engagement, Science Education, Open Access, Gender Equality, Governance and Ethics*.²

To facilitate the active engagement of the stakeholders and the development and documentation of the final roadmap of actions for each workshop, five participatory facilitation methods have been used: World Café, Focus Groups, Science Café, Structured Democratic Dialogue, and a simplified version of Science Café (classified as Other).

The analysis of the MML workshops' results revealed that a successful and responsible response to the above-mentioned marine challenges predominantly calls for:

- Raising awareness among all stakeholders, from the general public and business professionals to researchers and policymakers about the potential, the impact and the consequences of the marine challenges;
- Active engagement and cooperation between actors at a national and European level;
- Transferring knowledge, information and best practices across interested stakeholder groups to fully exploit the results of existing knowledge;
- Creating research infrastructures and funds schemes to allow the enhancement of science education and to bridge the gap between academia and industry;
- Enhancing, developing and implementing existing and future policies and regulations;
- Introducing marine related curricula for different educational levels.

The participants generated a total of 485 actions in this phase of the project. RRI dimensions were assigned to each action generated, and the analysis of the results of all workshops shows that *Governance* was linked to the greatest number of actions (351), followed closely by *Open Access* (297 actions) and *Public Engagement* (264 actions). *Science Education* was linked to 255 actions and *Ethics* to 251, while *Gender Equality* was the least considered RRI dimension with 144 actions.

Besides linking the actions with the RRI dimensions, the workshops aimed at associating the proposed actions with seven societal challenges in order to assess the level of contribution of the marine field. The analysis has revealed that the greatest number of actions were connected to the societal challenge of Climate action, environment, resource efficiency and raw materials (292 actions), while only a limited number of actions correlated with the challenge of Secure societies.

The findings of the second phase of international MML workshops corroborate the vision of the Blue Society, developed by the Sea for Society project funded by the 7th Framework Programme of the European Union. The Blue Society promotes “innovation through a close collaboration between researchers, entrepreneurs and decision-makers, in order to find solutions to meet society’s present and future needs”.

¹ Von Schomberg, Rene, A Vision of Responsible Research and Innovation (2013). Responsible Innovation. Managing the responsible emergence of science and innovation in society. Chapter 3, p51-74, J. Wiley: 2013. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2428157>

² <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/responsible-research-innovation>

3 MARINA Workshops - A pan-European process to engage societal actors in Responsible marine Research and Innovation for smart, sustainable, and inclusive Blue Growth in Europe

3.1 Mobilisation and Mutual Learning Workshops

The local workshops have been part of the second round of the Mobilisation and Mutual Learning (MML) Process, composed of two phases of workshops at local and international levels and connected to the international Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) practitioner and policymaker event. *Figure 1* below illustrates the concept.

Figure 1 MARINA Mobilisation and Mutual Learning Process

The workshops:

1. Engaged European societal actors in a multi-actor dialogue and in co-creating a participatory roadmap of actions for tackling a marine challenge and based on RRI principles;
2. Started the process of federating Civil Society Organisations (CSOs), citizens, businesses, industries, researchers, policymakers and communicators face-to-face and online;
3. Set in motion inclusive mechanisms for sharing knowledge and best practice, building common understanding and co-creating solutions to marine challenges based on RRI principles;
4. Facilitated the federation of communities and networks on the MARINA digital platform.

3.2 How can Responsible Research and Innovation ensure a smart, sustainable and inclusive Blue Growth in Europe?

Europe is facing an “innovation emergency”: it spends 0.8% of GDP less than the USA and 1.5% less than Japan on Research & Development (R&D) every year. Thousands of European best researchers and innovators have moved to countries where conditions are more favourable³, despite the support of the European Union to foster research and innovation in terms of networking, funding⁴, social business, start-up, dissemination and incubation⁵.

Seas and oceans are drivers of the European economy and have great potential for innovation and growth. They can contribute to achieving the goals of the Europe 2020 strategy for smart, sustainable and inclusive growth.

Accordingly, the European Union has set out the Blue Growth⁶ long-term strategy to support sustainable development in the marine and maritime sectors in Europe. This strategy aims to boost growth in areas such as aquaculture, coastal tourism, marine biotechnology, ocean energy and seabed mining. It puts forward three priorities to make Europe a smarter, more sustainable and more inclusive place to live:

³ <http://ec.europa.eu/research/innovation-union>

⁴ Employment and Social Innovation Programme, Horizon 2020, SME Instrument, Collective Awareness Platforms, EU structural and investment funds - Guide to Social Innovation. Social Challenges Platform.

⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/growth/industry/innovation/policy/social_it

⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/maritimeaffairs/policy/blue_growth_en

- Smart growth, through the development of an economy based on knowledge, research and innovation;
- Sustainable growth, through the promotion of resource-efficient, green and competitive markets;
- Inclusive growth, through policies aimed at fostering job creation and poverty reduction⁷.

At a global level, in the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, social challenges are a priority for a sustainable growth⁸.

RRI is a key cross-cutting instrument to reach these goals, an investment for our future. In practice, it has been implemented as a package that includes multi-actor and public engagement in research and innovation, thanks to open access to scientific results, formal and informal science education and the take-up of gender and ethics in the research and innovation content and process.

RRI is a transparent, interactive process in which societal actors and innovators become mutually responsive to each other with a view on the (ethical) acceptability, sustainability and societal desirability of the innovation process and its marketable products⁹. The European Commission distinguishes six key dimensions of RRI: *Public Engagement, Science Education, Open Access, Gender Equality, Ethics and Governance*.¹⁰

Public and multi-stakeholder engagement is a societal commitment to provide encouragement, opportunities and competencies that will empower citizens and civil society organisations to participate in research and innovation. It is also about bringing together a diversity of actors from different communities (research, policymaking, business and industry) that would not normally interact with each other on matters of science and technology.¹¹

Science Education aims at increasing society's appetite for innovation and interest in science, in particular among young people with a special emphasis on girls. It encourages innovative pedagogies to teach science, the involvement of institutions that organize such activities, promotes RRI in higher education curricula and eases access to scientific careers.¹²

Open access and open science intend to make research findings, data, scientific publications and information available and free of charge for anyone.

Gender Equality aims at removing barriers that generate discrimination against women in scientific careers and decision-making. It fosters gender balance in research teams and integrates a gender dimension in research and innovation content in order to improve the scientific quality and societal relevance of the produced knowledge, technology and innovation.¹³

Ethics is given the highest priority in the European Union funded research and innovation. It implies the application of fundamental ethical principles and legislation to scientific research and innovation in all possible domains, and includes the avoidance of any breach of research integrity and ethics dumping.¹⁴

Governance is the umbrella for all other dimensions. It addresses the responsibility of policymakers to prevent harmful or unethical developments in research and innovation and developing harmonious models for RRI that integrate Public and *multistakeholder Engagement, Science Education, Open Access, Gender Equality and Ethics*.¹⁵

3.3 Challenge-based approach

Complementary to the scientific approach of RRI which has been intensively introduced in the context of the Horizon 2020, one of the cornerstone of the programme is the integration of a new challenge-based approach called "Societal Challenges" into the planned activities, which requires that resources and knowledge deriving from a wide spectrum of fields,

⁷http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Smarter,_greener,_more_inclusive_-_indicators_to_support_the_Europe_2020_strategy

⁸ "Sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth is essential for prosperity. [...] We will work to build dynamic, sustainable, innovative and people-centered economies, promoting youth employment and women's economic empowerment, in particular, and decent work for all."

⁹ Von Schomberg, Rene, A Vision of Responsible Research and Innovation (2013). Responsible Innovation. Managing the responsible emergence of science and innovation in society. Chapter 3, p51-74, J. Wiley: 2013. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2428157>

¹⁰ <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/responsible-research-innovation>

¹¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/node/766>

¹² <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/node/795>

¹³ <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/node/797>

¹⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/node/767>

¹⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/research/swafs/pdf/pub_public_engagement/responsible-research-and-innovation-leaflet_en.pdf

technologies and disciplines are put in place to address the following seven challenges as identified by the European Union¹⁶:

- **Health, demographic change and well-being:** the goal is to provide sustainable solutions for a better health for all European citizens;
- **Food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry, marine and maritime and inland water research, and the bioeconomy:** the objective is to provide solutions to tackle the main challenges faced by the fields of agriculture, forestry, fisheries and aquaculture in Europe;
- **Secure, clean and efficient energy:** the goal is to provide energy efficiency solutions, to develop and enhance the integration of low carbon technologies in the market and finally promote the development of smart cities;
- **Smart, green and integrated transport:** the goal is to create a European transport system which is characterized by resource efficiency and respect towards the climate and the environment, while providing safety and security to European citizens;
- **Climate action, environment, resource efficiency and raw materials:** one of its main objectives is to produce actions to facilitate the development of societies which can be resilient to climate change while providing a viable management system of natural resources and ecosystems;
- **Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies:** the goal is to provide measures and actions which could help reducing inequalities and social exclusion in Europe to achieve a sustainable integration of all European citizens into the society;
- **Secure societies - protecting freedom and security of Europe and its citizens:** the objective is to develop research and actions to ensure that a high level of security is offered to European citizens in order to be resilient to natural disasters and criminal activities.

3.4 The MARINA workshops and Sustainable Development Goals

The European Union's response to the 2030 agenda of the United Nations Organisation is "The new European consensus on development of 'our world, our dignity, our future". The document highlights that "the EU and its Member States will integrate the respect of human rights, democracy, the rule of law and gender equality into their political dialogue" and that "sustainable development requires a holistic and cross-sector policy approach and is ultimately an issue of governance which needs to be pursued in partnership with all stakeholders and on all levels"¹⁷. Accordingly, the topics addressed at the MARINA workshops have been related to the following Sustainable Development Goals¹⁸:

¹⁶ <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/societal-challenges#Article>

¹⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/europeaid/sites/devco/files/european-consensus-on-development-final-20170626_en.pdf

¹⁸ <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org>

4 Methodology of Local MML Workshops, Phase Two

4.1 Hot Topic selection

In total twenty MML workshops were organized in twelve European countries between January and March 2018. Four workshops were organised in Italy by CNR (14 March 2018), APRE (12 March 2018), ISPRA (13 March 2018) and OMM (16 February), three in France by Sciencethics (29 January 2018), Nausicaa (13 March 2018) and WON (13 March 2018), two in Portugal by FRCT (9 March 2018) and EurOcean (9 March 2018), two in Ireland by Smartbay (8 March 2018) and UCC (15 March 2018), two in Romania by Mare Nostrum (6 March 2018) and NIRD GeoEcoMar (9 March 2018), one by XPRO/CNTI in Cyprus (21 February 2018), one by AAU in Denmark (13 March 2018), one by AHHA in Estonia (8 February 2018), one by SEVEN in Greece (28 February 2018), one by IOPAN in Poland (5 March 2018), one by CIC nanoGUNE in Spain (2 February 2018), and finally one by IU in Turkey (7 February 2018).

Following the workshop methodology approach developed in the framework of the first round of local MML Workshops (Deliverable 3.1), the partners identified a relevant marine issue in their country to be tackled during the MML workshop. In order to comply with our contractual agreement according to which each partner is obliged to address two of the eight marine challenges throughout the lifecycle of the MARINA project (Figure 2), the partners and associated partners chose a different marine challenge in every round.

Figure 2 Marine Challenges

Figure 3 below shows the distribution of marine challenges across the workshops, whereas Figure 4 presents the titles of the workshops categorized by marine challenges. Marine Biotechnology constitutes the most popular marine challenge in the second round of MML workshops as it was chosen by six partners, followed by Renewable Energy in second position (five workshops). Four workshops addressed the challenge of Sea Transportation while Marine Changes Caused by Climate was the preferred topic in three local workshops. Finally, the least prevalent marine challenge was Deep-sea Mining, as only two workshops, or 10% of the total number of workshops, focused on this particular hot topic. Figure 5 shows the geographical spread of the workshops in Europe.

Figure 3 Distribution of Marine Challenges among 20 Local MML Workshops

Figure 4 MML Workshops per Marine Challenge addressed

Figure 5 MML workshops per location

Out of the eight identified marine challenges, three of them were not addressed in this second round: Tourism and Coastal Cities, Fishing and Aquaculture, and Pollution Caused Human Land and Sea Pressures, given their considerably high prevalence (82% of the workshops) in the 17 local MML workshops organized between 2016 and 2017 in the first round.

4.2 Triggering question and hot topic

The overarching goal of the workshops was to provide room to the participants to suggest actions responding to a clearly defined and structured Triggering Question. The Triggering Question served as the communicative mechanism to spark discussions and encourage participants to develop a holistic vision of the marine challenges discussed by sharing knowledge and experience, and learning other actors' perspectives and priorities. In order to bring a homogenous approach to all workshops, the Triggering Question was formulated as "What responsible research and innovation actions are needed to make [workshop specific text] sustainable?"

Apart from merely responding to the Triggering Question, it was necessary that the participants include the notion of RRI into their contributions as well as relate their actions to a set of societal challenges. To facilitate this process, a specific slot was provided at the start of each workshop to introduce the participants to the approach of RRI.

To further facilitate the introduction of the participants to the topic of the workshop and foster their active engagement, a hot topic description documenting the necessity of responding to the identified marine challenge was developed and circulated among them electronically before the day of the workshop.

It was expected that the participants would correlate their contributions with the following RRI dimensions: 1) *Public Engagement*; 2) *Open Access*; 3) *Science Education*; 4) *Gender Equality*; 5) *Ethics*; 6) *Governance*, while aligning them with the

seven identified societal challenges: 1) *Health, demographic change and well-being*; 2) *Food security, agriculture, marine and maritime and inland water research, bioeconomy*; 3) *Secure, clean and efficient energy*; 4) *Smart, green and integrated transport*; 5) *Climate action, environment, resource efficiency and raw materials*; 6) *Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies*.

4.3 Workshop facilitation methods

According to the Grant Agreement and the D.3.1 *MML Workshop Methodology Approach and Actor Inclusion Criteria*, which provides the methodological approaches and principles for the organization of the local and international MML workshops, each partner could select one participatory and facilitation method from a range of six identified and agreed methods: Focus Groups, World Café, Science Café, Delphi, Future Search and Structured Democratic Dialogue (SDD).

Except for the SDD, the facilitation methods followed the instructions in D3.1 *MML Workshop Methodology Approach and Actor Inclusion Criteria* and the Action Catalogue (<http://actioncatalogue.eu/search>) that had been developed in the framework of the Engage2020 project funded by the European Union's 7th Framework Programme for research, technological development and demonstration.

As illustrated in Figure 6 below, the partners ran their workshops exploiting five of the suggested methods, as Delphi and Future Search were not used in any of the workshops implemented. Seven workshops (35%) have been implemented through Focus Groups making it the most widely used method among the workshops, tightly followed by World Café with a percentage of 30%. The least used methodologies were Science Café and Structured Democratic Dialogue, which were used twice.

7 MML workshops	Focus Groups
6 MML workshops	World Café
3 MML workshops	Other
2 MML workshops	Science Café
2 MML workshops	Structured Democratic Dialogue

Figure 6 MML workshops facilitation methods

The **World Café**¹⁹ method is used to implicate groups of people from various backgrounds into structured discussions aiming at collecting the knowledge, wisdom and ideas of the group on a particular predefined topic set by the facilitator. In particular, the World Café follows a simple method involving multiple rounds of conversations which enable all groups to reflect on and contribute to the different perspectives of the topics under discussion.

The **Focus Groups**²⁰ method refers to a qualitative approach used to identify people's preferences or to evaluate strategic plans and concepts. The selection of participants lies on a possession of a set of characteristics they have in common which are related to the hypotheses investigated. The questions asked are usually open-ended, allowing the participants to interpret them according to their understanding and feelings.

The **Science Café**²¹ is a method used in an informal, public setting allowing the interaction and open dialogue in a lay language between an expert and participants coming from a wide spectrum of the society, academia and industry. Anyone

¹⁹ <http://actioncatalogue.eu/method/7402>

²⁰ <http://actioncatalogue.eu/method/7409>

²¹ <http://actioncatalogue.eu/method/7439>

can walk in and take part in the workshop, during which attendees are allowed to raise questions to the expert related to the scientific topic under discussion.

The **Structured Democratic Dialogue (SDD)** is a method that supports *democratic* and *structured* dialogue among a group of stakeholders. It is delivered by a trained moderator and a dedicated software. The SDD is specifically designed to assist heterogeneous groups to deal with complex issues, in a reasonably limited amount of time. It enables the integration of contributions from individuals with diverse views, backgrounds and perspectives through a process that is structured, inclusive and collaborative.

Other: The workshops used a modified version of the Science Café method. A Science Café is an event organised in an informal, public setting open and accessible to anybody. An expert presents a subject in a concise and open manner after which the floor is open for a discussion. The moderator facilitates the sharing of a wide range of views on the subject at hand. However, since the workshops were not held in a public café but in a room located in a building with a restricted access (e.g. National Research Council in Rome), their methodology was classified as “Other”.

4.4 Participating stakeholder groups

The second round of local MML workshops assembled a total of 443 participants in 20 participatory workshops, a ratio of 22 participants per workshop in average who contributed with as many as 485 specific actions in response to the Triggering Questions of the workshops. The most populated workshop was organized by APRE (Italy) with 49 participants, followed by Seven (Greece) and Sciencethics (France) with 40 and 38 participants respectively. Almost a quarter of the total number of participants (101) were engaged in Italy as an immediate result of the fact that four workshops were organised in this country, followed by France and Portugal. As presented in Figure 7, a number of 75 and 58 stakeholders participated in the three French and two Portuguese workshops respectively.

Considering the number of actions per workshop, Figure 7 reveals that the MML workshops organized by IU (Turkey), using World Café, and Mare Nostrum (Romania), using Focus Groups, contributed with the highest number of actions, that is 41 actions each. The second position is shared between CNTI-XPRO (Cyprus) and Seven (Greece), the workshops of which generated as many as 38 actions exploiting the methodologies of Structured Democratic Dialogue and Focus Groups respectively.

Figure 7 Number of Participants and Number of Actions per MML workshop

The participants constituted a multidisciplinary group of stakeholders deriving from the whole spectrum of the society, ranging from Civic Society Organizations (CSOs) and Citizens, to Business Representatives, Researchers and Policymakers.

Figure 8 reveals the composition of the workshops and shows that the group of Researchers was the most represented with a percentage that climbs up to 32% of the total number of participants. A number of 116 Citizens/CSO/NGO representatives, that is a proportion of slightly over 26%, has made this category of stakeholders the second most prevalent group across the workshops. Thus, more than half of the participants, i.e. 58%, came from the two aforementioned groups. The group “Other” is made up of a variety of profiles which did not fit in any of the other four groups.

Figure 8 Local MML workshop participants, round 2 - Breakdown by stakeholder groups

4.5 Description of the analysis steps of local MML workshops in phase two

The following elements have been taken into account for the analysis steps of the second round of local MML workshops drawing from the experience and the lessons learned during phase one:

- I. Compliance of all partners with the requirements and obligations provided in the Deliverable 3.1 and its amendment. The organisers followed the steps for the successful implementation of the local MML workshop which includes instructions related to the stakeholder engagement criteria, workshop implementation as well as to the reporting procedure.
- II. The reporting template documents used in the first round of local MML workshops had been reviewed and significantly modified to allow the development of a more coherent and homogenous reporting system to document and compare the results of each workshop. Therefore, the reporting forms and the participants' survey had been standardised in a way that they could be used by all organizers regardless of the facilitation method of the workshop.
- III. Identification, development and review of the Hot Topic for each local MML workshop.
- IV. Workshop planning, organisation, implementation and reporting by the organisers.
- V. Development of the structure of the comprehensive overall report by CNTI (task leader), Nausicaa (WP leader) and CNR (Coordinator).
- VI. Compilation of 20 individual reports written by 20 partners and associated partners responsible for executing the workshops by Nausicaa. Drafting of the comprehensive report by CNTI (task leader) and Nausicaa (WP leader) with the contribution of the rest of the partners.
- VII. Review of first draft by Nausicaa (WP3 leader) and the workshop organisers.
- VIII. Update of the draft by CNTI and Nausicaa.
- IX. Final quality check by XPRO (quality manager).
- X. Final review by CNR (coordinator).

5 Outcomes

5.1 Local MML Workshops and Responsible Research and Innovation

5.1.1 Overall results

The 443 participants of the twenty local workshops proposed 485 actions in response to the Triggering Question and in link with the six main RRI dimensions²²:

Figure 9 Dimensions of Responsible Research & Innovation (RRI)

Drawing from the results of the first round of local MML workshops, the overarching goal of the local MML workshops organized in 2018 was to further facilitate the development of a marine and RRI situational awareness among existing RRI communities and societal forums for knowledge exchange and issue understanding. This could not be achieved without the prudent identification and the active engagement of European citizens and multidisciplinary stakeholders determined to share knowledge and build common understanding and vision, with a purpose of integrating RRI principles in their suggested actions to solve current marine and societal challenges.

To facilitate this process and as demonstrated earlier, the organizers of the MML workshops communicated the hot topic description to the participants prior to the implementation of the workshop. They introduced them to the overall aims of the MARINA project, and the specific objectives of the workshop in particular.

The communication material sent to all participants contained an introduction to RRI and a detailed explanation of how the hot topic of the workshop relates to each of the six main RRI dimensions. To ensure a common understanding of the RRI dimensions by the workshop participants, which could further guarantee that RRI would be embedded in the suggested actions generated during the workshop, a presentation of RRI was given before the beginning of the discussions. Using lay

²² A description of the RRI dimensions is provided in section 3.2

language which could be understood by the multidisciplinary group of participants, the presentation provided a comprehensible introduction to the concept of RRI and encouraged them to ask questions related to the integration of the RRI dimensions into their actions.

Depending on the facilitation method of the workshop, the actions were collected through a formalized method in some workshops, whereas in other workshops the final collection of actions was a result of discussions and revision internal to the groups of stakeholders.

Next, the participants were expected to link their actions with the RRI dimensions by answering whether an action was related to each of the six dimensions or not. It was explained to the participants that there was no one-to-one limitation, in the sense that one action must be linked with only one RRI dimension but rather, they were free to associate each action with more than one dimension. This is evident in the *Table 1* which provides a summary of the number of actions related to each RRI dimension (absolute frequency) per MML workshop according to which several actions are connected to more than one RRI dimensions.

For example in the workshop Marine Biotech – the opportunity of a sustainable economy organized by FRCT, 37 actions were generated (see *Figure 7*). *Table 1* below demonstrates that all of these actions are connected to the RRI dimension of *Governance* while 30 and 28 of them are connected with *Ethics* and *Science Education* respectively indicating that the vast majority of actions were linked with more than one RRI dimension.

Title of the workshop	Public Engagement	Science Education	Open Access	Gender Equality	Ethics	Governance	Total	Total no of actions
Marine Biotech – the opportunity of a sustainable economy (Portugal)	22	28	27	21	30	37	165	37
Marine biotechnologies as a source of local and sustainable economy in Nice, what are the challenges for the future? (France)	11	23	24	24	24	21	127	24
Oil spills at sea: what if the solution were bacteria? (Italy)	15	10	18	0	9	19	71	33
Blue biotechnologies – what are the challenges for the future? (France)	4	9	8	4	7	4	36	12
Sustainable Marine Biotechnologies, what's at stake for tomorrow? Focus on Marine pollution (France)	5	2	2	0	4	4	17	6
How may we develop the Marine Biotechnology as a source of local and sustainable economy in Cyprus? (Cyprus)	15	22	24	2	5	16	84	38
Renewable Energies that impact on coastal environment and development: what are the challenges in Italy? (Italy)	10	9	5	2	5	11	42	15
Energy from the sea: future or a road to nowhere? (Poland)	7	14	12	3	6	13	55	24
Offshore wind energy: Our future? How? (Spain)	19	2	19	0	19	19	78	21
Black Sea - an inexhaustible source of energy? How to tip the balance towards renewable energy? (Romania)	15	14	17	9	12	12	79	17
What is Marine Spatial Planning (MSP) and how can it be used to help inform decisions about the sustainable utilisation of Ireland's marine resources (Ireland)	27	24	24	17	19	29	140	30
Turning sea transportation threats into sea transportation opportunities on the Baltic Sea (Estonia)	5	7	4	0	4	12	32	16
What will maritime transportation be like in 2050? (Italy)	7	2	9	0	1	7	26	10
Blue Growth and Sea Transportation in Turkish Straits System (Turkey)	7	17	2	1	5	27	59	41
Ballast Water Management and the Marine Environment (Greece)	27	11	35	17	37	38	165	38
More value. Collaboration on mitigating climate change in coastal areas by community-driven processes (Denmark)	16	5	4	0	1	10	36	21
Will the unique character of the Black Sea ecosystem survive climate changes? (Romania)	23	29	34	35	38	41	200	41
Challenges of Coastal Protection in a Changing Climate (Ireland)	9	4	3	1	3	3	23	9
Deep-sea mining in the North Atlantic... an opportunity to do things right (Portugal)	12	9	13	5	17	20	76	34
Sustainable sea mining and Responsible Research and Innovation (Italy)	8	14	13	3	5	8	51	18
TOTAL	264	255	297	144	251	351	1562	485
PERCENTAGE	16.9%	16.33%	19.01	9.22%	16.07%	22.47%	100%	

Table 1 Number of actions related to the RRI dimensions per local MML workshop

Table 1 reveals that the greatest number of actions generated during the second round of local MML workshops addressed the RRI dimension of *Governance* (351 actions), followed by *Open Access* (297 actions) and *Public Engagement* (264 actions).

The column of Total shows a variance in the overall number of the associations/connections to the RRI dimensions of the actions generated in every workshop, from a minimum of 17 in the workshop “Sustainable Marine Biotechnologies, what’s at stake for tomorrow? Focus on Marine pollution” to a maximum of 200 associations in the workshop “Will the unique character of the Black Sea ecosystem survive climate changes?”.

In *Table 1*, the results of the MML workshops have the overall weight regardless of the number of actions identified. In order to avoid that each workshop contributes with a different weight in determining the implications and impacts of the RRI dimensions and to make the results of each local MML workshop comparable, the values in *Table 1* have been normalised by calculating a relative weighting of the RRI dimensions in every MML workshop and giving the same weight (equal to 10) to each MML workshop. The weighted values have been computed using the following formula:

$$\text{Number of actions related to the RRI dimension} * 10 / \text{Total number of connections to RRI dimensions of the local MML workshop}$$

For example in the workshop “Ballast Water Management and the Marine Environment” the relative weight of the RRI dimension of *Open Access* can be computed as follows:

$$35 * 10 / 165 = 2.12$$

The weighted values of the results of all local MML workshops in round two are demonstrated in *Table 2* below. Particular attention should be given to the row “Average of the Relative Weightings” which indicates the average of the relative weightings for each of the six RRI dimensions.

Title of the workshop	Public Engagement	Science Education	Open Access	Gender Equality	Ethics	Governance	Total
Marine Biotech – the opportunity of a sustainable economy (Portugal)	1.33	1.7	1.64	1.27	1.81	2.24	10.00
Marine biotechnologies as a source of local and sustainable economy in Nice, what are the challenges for the future? (France)	0.87	1.81	1.89	1.89	1.89	1.65	10.00
Oil spills at sea: what if the solution were bacteria? (Italy)	2.11	1.41	2.54	0	1.27	2.68	10.00
Blue biotechnologies – what are the challenges for the future? (France)	1.11	2.50	2.22	1.11	1.94	1.11	10.00
Sustainable Marine Biotechnologies, what's at stake for tomorrow? Focus on Marine pollution (France)	2.94	1.18	1.18	0	2.35	2.35	10.00
How may we develop the Marine Biotechnology as a source of local and sustainable economy in Cyprus? (Cyprus)	1.79	2.62	2.86	0.24	0.60	1.90	10.00
Renewable Energies that impact on coastal environment and development: what are the challenges in Italy? (Italy)	2.38	2.14	1.19	0.48	1.19	2.62	10.00
Energy from the sea: future or a road to nowhere? (Poland)	1.27	2.55	2.18	0.55	1.09	2.36	10.00
Offshore wind energy: Our future? How? (Spain)	2.44	0.26	2.44	0.00	2.44	2.44	10.00
Black Sea - an inexhaustible source of energy? How to tip the balance towards renewable energy? (Romania)	1.90	1.77	2.15	1.14	1.52	1.52	10.00
What is Marine Spatial Planning (MSP) and how can it be used to help inform decisions about the sustainable utilisation of Ireland's marine resources (Ireland)	1.93	1.71	1.71	1.21	1.36	2.07	10.00
Turning sea transportation threats into sea transportation opportunities on the Baltic Sea (Estonia)	1.56	2.19	1.25	0.00	1.25	3.75	10.00
What will maritime transportation be like in 2050? (Italy)	2.69	0.77	3.46	0.00	0.38	2.69	10.00
Blue Growth and Sea Transportation in Turkish Straits System (Turkey)	1.19	2.88	0.34	0.17	0.85	4.58	10.00
Ballast Water Management and the Marine Environment (Greece)	1.64	0.67	2.12	1.03	2.24	2.30	10.00
More value. Collaboration on mitigating climate change in coastal areas by community-driven processes (Denmark)	4.44	1.39	1.11	0.00	0.28	2.78	10.00
Will the unique character of the Black Sea ecosystem survive climate changes? (Romania)	1.15	1.45	1.70	1.75	1.90	2.05	10.00
Challenges of Coastal Protection in a Changing Climate (Ireland)	3.91	1.74	1.30	0.43	1.30	1.30	10.00
Deep-sea mining in the North Atlantic... an opportunity to do things right (Portugal)	1.58	1.18	1.71	0.66	2.24	2.63	10.00
Sustainable sea mining and Responsible Research and Innovation (Italy)	1.57	2.75	2.55	0.59	0.98	1.57	10.00
AVERAGE OF THE RELATIVE WEIGHTINGS	1.99%	1.73%	1.88%	0.63%	1.44%	2.33%	10%

Table 2 Weighted number of RRI-driven actions per each MML workshop

Figure 10 below shows a visual representation of the different relative weightings resulting from each local MML workshop:

Figure 10 Relative weightings on RRI dimensions

5.1.2 Results per RRI dimension

Public Engagement: The *Public Engagement* dimension has an average relative weighting of 1.99% with peaks in seven MML workshops. The most prominent was related to climate change (over 3.5). It was followed by marine biotechnologies and sea transportation. In terms of the number of actions addressing this particular dimension, it has appeared as the **second most significant RRI dimension** in the local MML workshops in the second round. *Figure 11* illustrates the radar diagram of the number of actions relating to *Public Engagement* in every MML workshop.

Science Education: The average relative weighting of the *Science Education* dimension has reached 1.73%, a percentage which has been exceeded in ten workshops. The exception is the workshop “*Offshore wind energy. Our future? How?*” in which the average relative weighting is close to zero (0.26). *Science Education* is tightly correlated to the topic of renewable energies while no significant link has been drawn between this particular RRI dimension and the topic of climate change. *Science Education* appears as **the fourth most significant RRI dimension** across the MML workshops. The radar diagram of the *Science Education* related actions per workshop is provided in *Figure 12*.

Open Access: With an average relative weighting of 1.88% and peaks in ten workshops, the *Open Access* dimension seemed very important in the discussions about marine biotechnologies and renewable energies while a very low correlation between this particular RRI dimension and climate change can be seen in the *Figure 12*. *Open Access* can be ranked as **the third most significant RRI dimension** in terms of the number of actions that were addressing it in the second round of the MML workshops. *Figure 13* shows the radar diagram of the actions relating to *Open Access* per workshop.

Gender Equality: *Figure 14* presents the radar diagram of the *Gender Equality* dimension which has come up as **the least considered RRI dimension** in the workshops with an average relative weighting not exceeding 0.63. While the average relative weighting has been exceeded in eight workshops, the radar diagram reveals that in 6 MML workshops, that is 30% of the workshops, the relative weighting was equal to zero. The RRI dimension of *Gender Equality* was not integrated in 107 actions generated by the stakeholders in the following workshops: (1) *Oil spills at sea: what if the solution were bacteria?* (Italy) (2) *Sustainable Marine Biotechnologies, what’s at stake for tomorrow? Focus on Marine pollution* (France) (3) *Offshore wind energy: Our future? How?* (Spain) (4) *Turning sea transportation threats into sea transportation opportunities on the Baltic Sea.* (Estonia) (5) *What will maritime transportation be like in 2050?* (Italy) (6) *More value. Collaboration on mitigating climate change in coastal areas by community-driven processes* (Denmark).

Ethics: *Figure 15* shows the radar diagram of the *Ethics* dimension which has an average relative weighting of 1.44% and peaks in as many as eight workshops. As demonstrated, a strong connection to this particular RRI dimension is apparent in the actions dealing with the topics of marine biotechnologies, wind energy, ballast water management and deep-sea mining. *Ethics* is **the fifth most significant RRI dimension** of the actions generated in the MML workshops.

Governance: *Figure 16* presents the radar diagram of the *Governance* dimension. With an average relative weighting of 2.33 this particular RRI dimension is present in the greatest number of actions and in the majority of the workshops with peaks evident in nine workshops covering five marine challenges. *Governance* is the most significant dimension in three workshops (i.e. 75%) related to the topic of Marine Transportation: “*Turning sea transportation threats into sea transportation opportunities on the Baltic Sea*” (3.75); “*Blue Growth and Sea Transportation in Turkish Straits System*” (4.58); “*Ballast Water Management and the Marine Environment*” (2.30). *Governance* is **the most significant RRI dimension** because it was addressed by the greatest number of actions during the local MML workshops.

Figure 11 Weighted value of actions related to Public Engagement per MML workshop

Figure 12 Weighted value of actions related to Science Education per MML workshop

Figure 13 Weighted value of actions related to Open Access per MML workshop

Figure 14 Weighted value of actions related to Gender Equality per MML workshop

Figure 15 Weighted value of actions related to Ethics per MML workshop

Figure 16 Weighted value of actions related to Governance per MML workshop

5.2 Local MML Workshops and Societal Challenges

5.2.1 Overall results

The purpose of this section is to demonstrate the connections between the actions generated during the 20 local MML workshops and the seven societal challenges described in section 3.3 in order to explore the level of contribution of the marine field in tackling some of those challenges.

The MARINA partners followed different approaches to introduce the societal challenges to the debate. Some partners (e.g. Nausicaa) left it up to the participants to categorise the actions per societal challenges. Other organisers classified the actions in terms of the societal challenges following the completion of each local MML workshop, by merely linking each action with one or more societal challenges as demonstrated in *Table 3*, and sending the results to the participants in the workshop reports afterwards and asking for their feedback.

It turned out that the societal challenge of *Climate action, environment, resource efficiency & raw materials* was the most popular among the marine challenges addressed in the workshops with 292 associated actions. Elaborating on the distribution of the societal challenges across six marine topics addressed in the second round, *Table 3* shows that the greatest number of actions (83 actions) related to this specific societal challenge were produced in five workshops tackling marine renewable energy (16.6% per workshop). *Climate action, environment, resource efficiency & raw materials* seems to be the most significant societal challenge in the workshops about climate change with a ratio of 22.3% per workshop. *Europe in a changing world – inclusive, innovative & reflective societies* ranks in the second position with 242 actions pointing to it. It is followed by *Food security, sustainable agriculture & forestry, marine, maritime & inland water research, and bio-economy* which was addressed by as many as 227 actions.

It is worth noting that all twenty MML workshops generated actions correlated with the challenge of *Climate action, environment, resource efficiency & raw materials* and that in almost all of the workshops the actions addressed all three aforementioned societal challenges. The only exceptions were the workshops *Offshore wind energy: Our future? How?* and *Blue Growth and Sea Transportation in Turkish Straits System*. The challenge of *Smart, green & integrated transport* was linked to 163 actions, and almost half of them have been generated in four MML workshops addressing the topic of marine transportation. Finally, no strong correlations between the marine topics addressed in the workshops and the societal challenge of *Health, democratic change and well-being* and *Secure societies* can be drawn.

Title of the workshop	Health, democratic change and well-being	Food security, sustainable agriculture & forestry, marine, maritime & inland water research, and bio-economy	Secure, clean & efficient energy	Smart, green & integrated transport	Climate action, environment, resource efficiency & raw materials	Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative & reflective societies	Secure societies	Total	Total no of actions
Marine Biotech – the opportunity of a sustainable economy (Portugal)	2	28	5	2	27	35	4	103	37
Marine biotechnologies as a source of local and sustainable economy in Nice, what are the challenges for the future? (France)	13	16	12	15	12	24	0	92	24
Oil spills at sea: what if the solution were bacteria? (Italy)	0	15	0	15	15	21	0	66	33
Blue biotechnologies – what are the challenges for the future? (France)	12	12	12	11	12	9	4	72	12
Sustainable Marine Biotechnologies, what's at stake for tomorrow? Focus on Marine pollution (France)	0	3	0	0	3	6	0	12	6
How may we develop the Marine Biotechnology as a source of local and sustainable economy in Cyprus? (Cyprus)	6	34	3	2	8	14	0	67	38
Renewable Energies that impact on coastal environment and development: what are the challenges in Italy? (Italy)	6	8	15	4	11	3	1	48	15
Energy from the sea: future or a road to nowhere? (Poland)	3	10	11	4	14	9	5	56	24
Offshore wind energy: Our future? How? (Spain)	0	0	19	0	19	0	0	38	21
Black Sea - an inexhaustible source of energy? How to tip the balance towards renewable energy? (Romania)	5	9	12	9	13	15	12	75	17
What is Marine Spatial Planning (MSP) and how can it be used to help inform decisions about the sustainable utilisation of Ireland's marine resources (Ireland)	13	25	26	22	26	22	19	153	30
Turning sea transportation threats into sea transportation opportunities on the Baltic Sea (Estonia)	8	6	6	14	7	4	4	49	16
What will maritime transportation be like in 2050? (Italy)	1	4	4	10	3	4	3	29	10
Blue Growth and Sea Transportation in Turkish Straits System (Turkey)	0	4	1	9	4	0	0	18	41
Ballast Water Management and the Marine Environment (Greece)	5	12	3	38	28	19	6	111	38
More value. Collaboration on mitigating climate change in coastal areas by community-driven processes (Denmark)	7	2	2	1	19	7	7	45	21
Will the unique character of the Black Sea ecosystem survive climate changes? (Romania)	6	9	4	6	41	27	7	100	41
Challenges of Coastal Protection in a Changing Climate (Ireland)	5	6	1	0	7	2	2	23	9
Deep-sea mining in the North Atlantic... an opportunity to do things right (Portugal)	15	11	0	0	14	17	0	57	34
Sustainable sea mining and Responsible Research and Innovation (Italy)	8	13	2	1	9	4	3	40	18
TOTAL	115	227	138	163	292	242	77	1254	485
PERCENTAGE	9.17%	18.10%	11%	13%	23.29%	19.30%	6.14%	100%	

Table 3 Number of actions relating to Societal challenges per each MML Workshop

Following the process of normalization of the values of the RRI dimensions described in 5.1.1, the same method has been employed in order to achieve more comparable outcomes with regards to the link between the actions and the societal challenges. Consequently, the relative average weighting for each MML workshop and each societal challenge presented in *Table 4* and *Figure 17* has been generated by applying the following formula:

$$\frac{\text{Number of actions related to a Societal challenge} * 10}{\text{Total number of connections to societal challenges of the local MML workshop}}$$

For example the workshop “*How may we develop the Marine Biotechnology as a source of local and sustainable economy in Cyprus?*” in which the relative weight of the challenge *Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative & reflective societies* has been calculated as follows:

$$14 * 10 / 67 = 2.09$$

Title of the workshop	Health, democratic change and well-being	Food security, sustainable agriculture & forestry, marine, maritime & inland water research, and bio-economy	Secure, clean & efficient energy	Smart, green & integrated transport	Climate action, environment, resource efficiency & raw materials	Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative & reflective societies	Secure societies	Total
Marine Biotech – the opportunity of a sustainable economy (Portugal)	0.19	2.72	0.49	0.19	2.62	3.40	0.39	10.00
Marine biotechnologies as a source of local and sustainable economy in Nice, what are the challenges for the future? (France)	1.41	1.74	1.30	1.63	1.30	2.61	0.00	10.00
Oil spills at sea: what if the solution were bacteria? (Italy)	0.00	2.27	0.00	2.27	2.27	3.18	0.00	10.00
Blue biotechnologies – what are the challenges for the future? (France)	1.67	1.67	1.67	1.53	1.67	1.25	0.56	10.00
Sustainable Marine Biotechnologies, what's at stake for tomorrow? Focus on Marine pollution (France)	0.00	2.50	0.00	0.00	2.50	5.00	0.00	10.00
How may we develop the Marine Biotechnology as a source of local and sustainable economy in Cyprus? (Cyprus)	0.90	5.07	0.45	0.30	1.19	2.09	0.00	10.00
Renewable Energies that impact on coastal environment and development: what are the challenges in Italy? (Italy)	1.25	1.67	3.13	0.83	2.29	0.63	0.21	10.00
Energy from the sea: future or a road to nowhere? (Poland)	0.54	1.79	1.96	0.71	2.50	1.61	0.89	10.00
Offshore wind energy: Our future? How? (Spain)	0.00	0.00	5.00	0.00	5.00	0.00	0.00	10.00
Black Sea - an inexhaustible source of energy? How to tip the balance towards renewable energy? (Romania)	0.67	1.20	1.60	1.20	1.73	2.00	1.60	10.00
What is Marine Spatial Planning (MSP) and how can it be used to help inform decisions about the sustainable utilisation of Ireland's marine resources (Ireland)	0.85	1.63	1.70	1.44	1.70	1.44	1.24	10.00
Turning sea transportation threats into sea transportation opportunities on the Baltic Sea (Estonia)	1.63	1.22	1.22	2.86	1.43	0.82	0.82	10.00
What will maritime transportation be like in 2050? (Italy)	0.34	1.38	1.38	3.45	1.03	1.38	1.03	10.00
Blue Growth and Sea Transportation in Turkish Straits System (Turkey)	0.00	2.22	0.56	5.00	2.22	0.00	0.00	10.00
Ballast Water Management and the Marine Environment (Greece)	0.45	1.08	0.27	3.42	2.52	1.71	0.54	10.00
More value. Collaboration on mitigating climate change in coastal areas by community-driven processes (Denmark)	1.56	0.44	0.44	0.22	4.22	1.56	1.56	10.00
Will the unique character of the Black Sea ecosystem survive climate changes? (Romania)	0.60	0.90	0.40	0.60	4.10	2.70	0.70	10.00
Challenges of Coastal Protection in a Changing Climate (Ireland)	2.17	2.61	0.43	0.00	3.04	0.87	0.87	10.00
Deep-sea mining in the North Atlantic... an opportunity to do things right (Portugal)	2.63	1.93	0.00	0.00	2.46	2.98	0.00	10.00
Sustainable sea mining and Responsible Research and Innovation (Italy)	2.00	3.25	0.50	0.25	2.25	1.00	0.75	10.00
AVERAGE OF THE RELATIVE WEIGHTINGS	0.943	1.8645	1.125	1.295	2.402	1.8115	0.558	

Table 4 Weighted number of actions relating to societal challenges per each MML workshop

Figure 17 Relative weights on EU societal challenges in local MML workshops

5.2.2 Results per societal challenge

To demonstrate the average relative weighting of the MML workshops in relation to each of the seven societal challenges in a graphical way, radar charts have been developed.

Health, democratic change and well-being: *Figure 18* reveals that this societal challenge has been significant in the actions generated in two workshops dealing with deep-sea mining.

Food security, sustainable agriculture & forestry, marine, maritime & inland water research, and bio-economy: The *Figure 19* demonstrates that the average relative weighting reaches 1.86 with peaks, 50% of which in the workshops dealing with marine biotechnologies. The only exception is the workshop “*Offshore wind energy: Our future? How?*” In the remaining 19 workshops, the participants proposed actions which have been correlated with this specific societal challenge. It seems to be significant in the discussions about the marine biotechnology and deep-sea mining.

Secure, clean & efficient energy: All MML workshops dealing with the topic of renewable energy not only have generated actions to address this challenge, but their relative weighting exceeded the average and climbed at 1.13 (*Figure 20*). The figure also reveals a significantly low connection between this particular challenge and the actions in the workshops about deep-sea mining and climate change.

Smart, green and integrated transport: With an average relative weighting of 1.30, this societal challenge was significant for the workshops dealing with the topic of marine transportation. The evidence has also revealed some partial correlation with the topic of marine biotechnology. As shown in *Figure 21*, this societal challenge was insignificant in the workshops dealing with deep-sea mining.

Climate action, environment, resource efficiency and raw materials: This societal challenge has been ranked as **the most significant** as it has been connected with the greatest number of actions amongst the twenty MML workshops (*Figure 22*). This specific challenge has an average of 2.4 with peaks in nine workshops and a strong correlation with the topic of climate change. It is also significant in the actions addressing marine biotechnology and renewable energies. It is worth mentioning that all local MML workshops have generated actions which are related to this challenge.

Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative & reflective societies: *Figure 23* shows the radar diagram of this societal challenge. With an average of 1.81 and peaks in several workshops, this specific societal challenge, which seems to be tightly connected to the topic of marine biotechnology, was addressed in only two workshops: “*Offshore wind energy: Our future? How?*” and “*Blue Growth and Sea Transportation in Turkish Straits System*”.

Secure societies: *Figure 23* shows a relatively significant relationship between the challenge of *Secure Societies* and the topic of climate change.

Figure 18 Weighted value of number of actions to Health, democratic change and well-being

Figure 19 Weighted value of number of actions to Food security, sustainable agriculture & forestry, marine, maritime & inland water research, and bio-economy

Figure 20 Weighted value of number of actions to Secure, clean & efficient energy

Figure 21 Weighted value of number of actions to Smart, green and integrated transport

Figure 22 Weighted value of number of actions to Climate action, environment, resource efficiency & raw materials

Figure 23 Weighted value of number of actions to Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative & reflective societies

Figure 24 Weighted value of number of actions to Secure societies

5.3 Action Plans

The following section presents the five marine challenges addressed during the local MML workshops. It is organised by marine challenge, and each subsection contains its description, followed by the individual workshop results: the roadmaps of RRI-driven actions and conclusions. Detailed reports of the individual MML workshop hot topics and reports can be found on <https://www.marinaproject.eu/>.

5.3.1 Marine Biotechnologies

5.3.1.1 Description

The notion that raw materials could be transformed into an improved product for the benefit of mankind is the key concept of biotechnology. Since the dawn of civilisation, humans have manipulated genes to improve their food production. They selected the best cereal species and they have been using yeast for fermentation as early as 7,000 BC. Today modern biotechnology is mostly associated with drug development and industrial food processing.

The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) defines biotechnology as “the application of science and technology to living organisms, as well as parts, products and models thereof, to alter living and non-living materials for the production of knowledge, goods and services”. Marine biotechnology, or blue biotechnology, uses marine living resources as the target or source of biotechnological applications.

Oceans and seas are home to over 90% of the earth’s biosphere. Living in extreme conditions (pressure, darkness, salinity, temperature, etc.), the marine macro- and micro-organisms have developed unique metabolic abilities to ensure their survival. This biological, chemical and genetic diversity makes marine organisms a huge and largely unexplored reservoir for new developments in both basic knowledge and biotechnological innovations.

The marine biotechnology sector is a growing emerging sector that has the potential to deliver blue growth through the development of a wide range of applications in the food industry, health, pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, energy and environment.

According to a report from the DG for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries, marine biotech revenues in Europe could reach €1 billion within five years if the current market growth of 6-8% per year is maintained, and this could result in the creation of 10,000 new jobs.

5.3.1.2 Results of the workshop in Cyprus (the Mediterranean Sea) held by XPRO/CNTI, Nicosia

With technological developments helping to explore the sea and its environment, marine biotechnology is a fast growing field. It is a field where the EU is trying to position itself and so could Cyprus. As of today, only one micro marine biotech SME operates in Cyprus, which works mostly with algae.

The topic of the workshop held by XPRO/CNTI was “How may we develop the Marine Biotechnology as a source of local and sustainable economy in Cyprus?” The workshop aimed at answering the triggering question: “What Responsible Research and Innovation actions are needed to make marine biotechnology a sustainable source of local economy in Cyprus?”

The participants of this workshop used the SDD method to generate a final action-influence map. 38 ideas were initially generated by the participants in the form of concise SMART action-statements through the “idea generation phase”. The participants mutually and collaboratively identified 8 clusters:

1. Research,
2. Stakeholders,
3. Incentives – Economy,
4. Risk Management,
5. [No name was given to this cluster],
6. Legislation,
7. Environment,
8. Education.

The distribution of the actions across the 8 clusters is demonstrated in Figure 25 and Figure 26 below.

Figure 25 Clusters 1 to 4 of the workshop in Nicosia, Cyprus

Figure 26 Clusters 5 to 8 of the workshop in Nicosia, Cyprus

Figure 27 below shows the final influence map developed by the participants.

Figure 27 Final influence map produced by the participants in Nicosia, Cyprus

Next, the final influence map (roadmap) was produced as a result of voting and deciding how actions influence one another. It shows the convergence of ideas with 5 actions as goals at the top Level 1 and the driver actions at levels 4 and 5, and many inter-related actions in the middle (levels 2 and 3).

As demonstrated in Figure 27, the influence map incorporates 5 different levels. The most influential actions are the root actions, which are considered as drivers, and which should be implemented first to stimulate the implementation of the subsequent actions considering that the latter rely on the former. These root actions are located at the lower levels of the roadmap and in particular at the levels 5 and 4. Therefore, to enable the development of the marine biotechnology sector in Cyprus, it is pivotal that the following actions are implemented first:

- Level 5: Tax incentives (A27, C3, V2)²³

²³ A= Action, C=Cluster, V=Votes

- Level 4: *Creation of funding mechanisms for marine biotechnology (A7, C3, V5), Cooperation among academic institutions and the industry (A30, C2, V1) and Development of university educational programmes on marine biotechnology (A21, C8, V1)*

Level 3 is composed of one action: *Founding a research centre in marine biotechnology (C1, V: 7)* which was considered the most important action during the voting phase, as illustrated in *Figure 27*. Three out of the four actions positioned at the Level 2, namely, *Use of technology for the surveillance and monitoring of the marine environment (A: 13, C: 7, V: 6)*, *Defining a legal framework (A: 26, C: 6, V: 4)*, and *Involvement of citizens in decision making (A: 34, C: 2, V: 5)* were the most important actions in the clusters C7: *Environment*, C6: *Legislation* and C2: *Stakeholders* as demonstrated in *Figure 25* and *Figure 26*.

The main conclusions of the workshop were the following:

- The marine biotechnology sector is a complex multidisciplinary field that needs cooperation between public and private societal actors.
- A national strategy and a legal framework are required focusing on enabling businesses through financial and tax incentives to invest in the field of marine biotechnologies.
- A national research centre in marine biotechnology and educational programmes at university level is required.
- Creation of funding mechanisms for marine biotechnology through private public partnerships is needed.
- Marine literacy and awareness must be included in school programmes and extended to the wider public through a natural history museum.
- Citizens should participate in decision-making and in monitoring the marine and coastal environmental status.

The actions focused on the following dimensions: *Open Access* was the most common dimension that appeared in 24 actions, to be followed closely by *Science Education* (22 actions). *Governance* (16 actions) and *Public Engagement* (15 actions). *Ethics* relates to 5 actions and *Gender Equality* to 2 actions.

5.3.1.3 Results of the workshop in France (the Mediterranean Sea) held by Sciencethics, Nice

The immense marine biodiversity of the Mediterranean offers the potential to generate sustainable business opportunities through the development of numerous applications. Despite these encouraging prospects, development in the Mediterranean region is difficult. The Mediterranean regions host high-level research centres with internationally recognized innovation platforms, but most of them are poorly known at the regional level, and only a few are integrated into regional innovation strategies. As a result, many emerging private players in this field do not know where to find innovative knowledge and ideas. There is a lack of coordination and communication between research centres, innovation platforms, policymakers and SMEs. Consequently, the slow pace of innovation and competitiveness is commonly encountered by Mediterranean countries. Market needs, potential for regional development, lack of existing knowledge and sustainable development goals are not well studied and financial resources on this theme are very limited in research institutions. A working group specialized in the know-how and tools of marine biotechnology is missing in Nice.

The topic of the workshop held by Sciencethics was “*Marine Biotechnology as a source of local and sustainable economy in Nice: what are the challenges for the future?*” The workshop aimed at answering the triggering question: “*How can responsible research and innovation allow marine biotechnology to become sustainable?*”

Table 5 shows the roadmap of actions suggested during this workshop.

WHY - overall objectives for making a roadmap and a common vision		Operational policy actions (decision-makers) that would make marine biotechnology in Nice a sustainable economic opportunity								
		Which collaborations would create synergy and dynamics around marine biotechnologies?				What social or cultural actions would develop the knowledge of the general public on marine biotechnologies?				
WHO Stakeholder target group(s) Choose from : Citizens/CSOs/NGOs (C), Business/Industry (B), Researchers & Academia (R), Policymakers & implementers (P) Other (Please specify)	WHAT Action	WHEN	OVERALL GOAL: Which societal challenge will the action contribute to? Choose from:							
		How long will it take to complete the action? short (now-1 year), medium (2-5 years), long term (over 5 years)	Health, democratic change and well-being	Food security, agriculture, marine and maritime and inland water research, bioeconomy	Secure, clean and efficient energy	Smart, green and integrated transport	Climate action, environment, resource efficiency, and raw materials	Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies	Secure societies	
PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT										
C, R, P	Create and initiate the week of the Taste and Health, in Nice or in cooperation with Monaco, including products from Marine biotechnology development	MT	x	x					x	
C, R, B, P	Exchange with star chefs on new products from the transformation of marine resources	ST		x					x	
C, R, P	Make the general public aware of the marine biotechnology sector and its potential through the organization of a Marine biotech day at the regional level including different actors	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
C, R, B	Raise awareness of the general public thanks to "ambassadors", "figures" who carry the project at the level of the region (navigators, high level sportsman, divers, swimmers), with a special attention to quality and ethics. Popularize the topic thanks to students, NGOs and researchers/industries	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
SCIENCE EDUCATION										
P	Realize a complete inventory of local skills on the subject, academic actors, start-ups or companies already established in the region	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
P	Create a one-stop shop for the Institute of (Bio) Blue Technologies	LT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
P	Create a Trophy, an award "the best Blue (bio)technologies innovation or product"	LT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
C, R, P	Create and initiate the week of the Taste and Health, in Nice or in cooperation with Monaco, including products from Marine biotechnology development	MT	x	x					x	
P	Coordinate and develop industrial, academic and political linkages to boost funding	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
C, R, B, P	Exchange with star chefs on new products from the transformation of marine resources	ST		x					x	
C, R, P	Make the general public aware of the marine biotechnology sector and its potential through the organization of a Marine biotech day at the regional level including different actors	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
C, R, B	Raise awareness of the general public thanks to "ambassadors", "figures" who carry the project at the level of the region (navigators, high level sportsman, divers, swimmers), with a special attention to quality and ethics. Popularize the topic thanks to students, NGOs and researchers/industries	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
OPEN ACCESS										

P	Realize a complete inventory of local skills on the subject, academic actors, start-ups or companies already established in the region	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	
P	Create a one-stop shop for the Institute of (Bio) Blue Technologies	LT	x	x	x	x	x	x	
P	Create a Trophy, an award “the best Blue (bio)technologies innovation or product”	LT	x	x	x	x	x	x	
C, R, P	Create and initiate the week of the Taste and Health, in Nice or in cooperation with Monaco, including products from Marine biotechnology development	MT	x	x				x	
P	Coordinate and develop industrial, academic and political linkages to boost funding	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	
C, R, B, P	Exchange with star chefs on new products from the transformation of marine resources	ST		x				x	
C, R, P	Make the general public aware of the marine biotechnology sector and its potential through the organization of a Marine biotech day at the regional level including different actors	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	
C, R, B	Raise awareness of the general public thanks to "ambassadors", “figures” who carry the project at the level of the region (navigators, high level sportsman, divers, swimmers), with a special attention to quality and ethics. Popularize the topic thanks to students, NGOs and researchers/industries	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	
GENDER EQUALITY									
P	Realize a complete inventory of local skills on the subject, academic actors, start-ups or companies already established in the region	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	
P	Create a one-stop shop for the Institute of (Bio) Blue Technologies	LT	x	x	x	x	x	x	
P	Create a Trophy, an award “the best Blue (bio)technologies innovation or product”	LT	x	x	x	x	x	x	
C, R, P	Create and initiate the week of the Taste and Health, in Nice or in cooperation with Monaco, including products from Marine biotechnology development	MT	x	x				x	
P	Coordinate and develop industrial, academic and political linkages to boost funding	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	
C, R, B, P	Exchange with star chefs on new products from the transformation of marine resources	ST		x				x	
C, R, P	Make the general public aware of the marine biotechnology sector and its potential through the organization of a Marine biotech day at the regional level including different actors	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	
C, R, B	Raise awareness of the general public thanks to "ambassadors", “figures” who carry the project at the level of the region (navigators, high level sportsman, divers, swimmers), with a special attention to quality and ethics. Popularize the topic thanks to students, NGOs and researchers/industries	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	
ETHICS									
P	Realize a complete inventory of local skills on the subject, academic actors, start-ups or companies already established in the region	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	
P	Create a one-stop shop for the Institute of (Bio) Blue Technologies	LT	x	x	x	x	x	x	
P	Create a Trophy, an award “the best Blue (bio)technologies innovation or product”	LT	x	x	x	x	x	x	
C, R, P	Create and initiate the week of the Taste and	MT	x	x				x	

	Health, in Nice or in cooperation with Monaco, including products from Marine biotechnology development								
P	Coordinate and develop industrial, academic and political linkages to boost funding	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	
C, R, B, P	Exchange with star chefs on new products from the transformation of marine resources	ST		x				x	
C, R, P	Make the general public aware of the marine biotechnology sector and its potential through the organization of a Marine biotech day at the regional level including different actors	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	
C, R, B	Raise awareness of the general public thanks to "ambassadors", "figures" who carry the project at the level of the region (navigators, high level sportsman, divers, swimmers), with a special attention to quality and ethics. Popularize the topic thanks to students, NGOs and researchers/industries	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	
GOVERNANCE									
P	Realize a complete inventory of local skills on the subject, academic actors, start-ups or companies already established in the region	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	
P	Create a one-stop shop for the Institute of (Bio) Blue Technologies	LT	x	x	x	x	x	x	
P	Create a Trophy, an award "the best Blue (bio)technologies innovation or product"	LT	x	x	x	x	x	x	
C, R, P	Create and initiate the week of the Taste and Health, in Nice or in cooperation with Monaco, including products from Marine biotechnology development	MT	x	x				x	
P	Coordinate and develop industrial, academic and political linkages to boost funding	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	
C, R, B, P	Exchange with star chefs on new products from the transformation of marine resources	ST		x				x	
C, R, P	Make the general public aware of the marine biotechnology sector and its potential through the organization of a Marine biotech day at the regional level including different actors	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	

Table 5 Final roadmap produced by the participants of the workshop in Nice, France

The RRI dimensions that scored the biggest number of actions were *Ethics*, *Gender equality* and *Open Access*, followed closely with *Science Education*. This may be due to several factors such as the composition of the group.

The workshop informed the civil society and regional economic actors and clusters about marine biotechnology. It is expected that the gained knowledge will impact in the following years on the interest of policymakers to the sector. Multiplying such events where researchers from academia and industry exchange with a broader community, will favour the creation of such community in Nice and surrounding area and foster its visibility. Policymakers and citizens would finally pay attention to the development of this sector.

5.3.1.4 Results of the workshop in France (the Channel) held by Nausicaa, Boulogne-sur-Mer

The increase in importance of the blue biotechnologies in France is undeniable. With 75% of the frontiers bordered by seas and oceans (13,000 km), France has a role to play in the development of marine biotechnologies and even though most of the projects are still in R&D or test phases, the growing public interest in the blue technologies augurs their development and growth. Only 1.4% of all patents filed worldwide between 2000 and 2011 dealt with marine biotechnologies. In France, this figure reached 3%.

The topic of the workshop held by Nausicaa was “Blue biotechnologies: what are the challenges for the future?” The workshop aimed at answering the triggering question: “What Responsible Research and Innovation actions are needed to make marine biotechnologies sustainable in France?”

Table 6 shows the roadmap of actions suggested during this workshop. The actions were categorised in three clusters of actions:

- Cluster 1: Make an inventory of innovations and tools, and facilitate collaboration and networking.
- Cluster 2: Train and convince policymakers and implementers, and convince investors.
- Cluster 3: Raise awareness about the benefits of marine biotechnologies.

WHY - overall objectives for making a roadmap and a common vision									
TO ENSURE THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF MARINE BIOTECHNOLOGIES IN FRANCE									
WHO Stakeholder target group(s) Choose from : Citizens/CSOs/NGOs (C), Business/Industry (B), Researchers & Academia (R), Policymakers & implementers (P) Other (Please specify)	WHAT Action	WHEN How long will it take to complete the action? short (now-1 year), medium (2-5 years), long term (over 5 years)	OVERALL GOAL: Which societal challenge will the action contribute to? Choose from:						
			Health, democratic change and well-being	Food security, agriculture, marine and maritime and inland water research, bioeconomy.	Secure, clean and efficient energy	Smart, green and integrated transport	Climate action, environment, resource efficiency, and raw materials	Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies	Secure societies
PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT									
B, R	(C1) Collect information at local level	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	
C, B, R, P, Scientific Officer	(C1) Create a transdisciplinary network (health, marine, food, energy, climate)	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P	(C1) Start a regional project about marine biotechnologies, based on networks	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	
C, B, R, P	(C3) Organise Open Days for the public in marine biotechnologies companies	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	
SCIENCE EDUCATION									
C, B, R, P, Scientific Officer	(C1) Create a transdisciplinary network (health, marine, food, energy, climate)	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
B, R	(C1) Facilitate collaboration between Research, Education and Industry	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	
B, P	(C2) Train policymakers and implementers	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	
P	(C2) Convince investors	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	
C, B, R, P	(C3) Organise Open Days for the public in marine biotechnologies companies	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	
C, R	(C3) Raise tourism awareness about marine biotechnologies	ST	x	x	x		x		
C, R	(C3) Raise academic awareness about marine biotechnologies	ST	x	x	x	x	x		
C, Media	(C3) Involve the media	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
R	(C3) Communicate on marine biotechnologies in layman's terms	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
OPEN ACCESS									
B, R	(C1) Collect information at local level	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	
C, B, R, P, Scientific Officer	(C1) Create a transdisciplinary network (health, marine, food, energy, climate)	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P	(C1) Start a regional project about marine biotechnologies, based on networks	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	

B, P	(C2) Train policymakers and implementers	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	
P	(C2) Convince investors	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	
C, B, R, P	(C3) Organise Open Days for the public in marine biotechnologies companies	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	
C, Media	(C3) Involve the media	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
R	(C3) Communicate on marine biotechnologies in layman's terms	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
GENDER EQUALITY									
B, R	(C1) Collect information at local level	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	
C, B, R, P, Scientific Officer	(C1) Create a transdisciplinary network (health, marine, food, energy, climate)	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
B, R	(C1) Facilitate collaboration between Research, Education and Industry	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	
C, B, R, P	(C1) Start a regional project about marine biotechnologies, based on networks	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	
ETHICS									
B, R	(C1) Collect information at local level	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	
C, B, R, P, Scientific Officer	(C1) Create a transdisciplinary network (health, marine, food, energy, climate)	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
C, R	(C3) Raise academic awareness about marine biotechnologies	ST	x	x	x	x	x		
C, Media	(C3) Involve the media	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
R	(C3) Communicate on marine biotechnologies in layman's terms	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
GOVERNANCE									
C, B, R, P, Scientific Officer	(C1) Create a transdisciplinary network (health, marine, food, energy, climate)	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
B, P	(C2) Train policymakers and implementers	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	
P	(C2) Convince investors	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	
Professional organisations	(C1) Use the example of professional organisations to bring structure to the marine biotechnologies sector	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	x

Table 6 Final roadmap produced by the participants of the Nausicaa workshop in Boulogne-sur-Mer, France

The RRI dimension that scored the biggest number of actions was *Science Education*. This may be due to several factors such as the nature of the hot topic and the composition of the group. The majority of participants were not working directly with biotechnologies, and only a few scientists were present. As a result, the general need for more scientific information and training may not have transpired as much if the participants had had a different profile. Some of the scientists that attended the workshop expressed their surprise at the workshop method. They expected an in-depth coverage of marine biotechnologies and they were not used to the participatory approach of the World Café method.

The main message was the importance of *Science Education* and *Open Access* for all stakeholder groups. To ensure a sustainable future for marine biotechnologies, researchers and scientists need to communicate effectively and share data with the general public to gain their support, with business investors to spark interest and rationalise the risks, and with policymakers to break down any administrative or regulatory barrier.

5.3.1.5 Results of the workshop in France (the Channel) held by WON, Boulogne-sur-Mer

Human activities are the main source of marine pollution, whether industrial or domestic. This pollution is thus linked to the consumer society and it is not only detrimental to marine biodiversity, but human health is also affected.

All stakeholders in society are thus responsible and concerned by marine pollution. Citizens, although more and more exposed to images showing the impact of pollution on marine life and coastlines, do not all seem sufficiently aware and

informed. A change of production and consumption behaviour patterns of economic actors, especially citizens, seems necessary to reduce the impacts of pollution. The media coverage of plastic waste pollution analysed and documented by both the scientific community (e.g. Tara Expeditions) and associations (e.g. Ellen MacArthur Foundation) has put the sea back on the stakeholders' agenda. Acidification, eutrophication and pollution are now also part of the United Nations Oceans Programme under Sustainable Development Goal 14.

It is in this context that the contribution of marine biotechnologies makes perfect sense. These resources, used in a responsible manner, can provide a sustainable solution to marine pollution, not only in terms of prevention and reduction of pollution, but also by promoting the blue economy. Indeed, the global market for marine biotechnologies is estimated to reach 4.8 billion euros by 2020²⁴.

The topic of the workshop held by WON was “Sustainable Marine Biotechnologies, what’s at stake for tomorrow? Focus on Marine pollution”. The workshop aimed at answering the triggering question: “How can marine biotechnologies help reduce marine pollution?”

Table 7 shows the roadmap of actions suggested during this workshop.

WHY - overall objectives for making a roadmap and a common vision		TO ENSURE SUSTAINABLE MARINE BIOTECHNOLOGIES IN ORDER TO REDUCE MARINE POLLUTION AND ENGAGE ALL STAKEHOLDERS								
WHO Stakeholder target group(s) Choose from : Citizens/CSOs/NGOs (C), Business/Industry (B), Researchers & Academia (R), Policymakers & implementers (P) Other (Please specify)	WHAT Action	WHEN How long will it take to complete the action? short (now-1 year), medium (2-5 years), long term (over 5 years)	OVERALL GOAL: Which societal challenge will the action contribute to? Choose from:							
			Health, democratic change and well-being	Food security, agriculture, marine and maritime and inland water research, bioeconomy.	Secure, clean and efficient energy	Smart, green and integrated transport	Climate action, environment, resource efficiency, and raw materials	Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies	Secure societies	
PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT										
C, B, R, P	Training for students and professionals in schools and universities and guidance for careers in marine biotechnologies	MT		x	x		x	x		
C, R, B, P	Knowledge transfer through an online platform, organised diffusion to target groups, award with popular vote to support research and innovation	ST		x					x	
C, R, Information multipliers	Raising awareness thanks to trained marine educators and information relays on marine biotechnologies	MT							x	
C, B, R, P	Creation of a European Panel of Marine Bioethics with inventory of knowledge and projects as well as indicators and good practices	ST							x	
C, B, R, P	Certification label of projects as an incentive process with a guideline for different actors for the sustainable development of marine biotech and an ethic committee that delivers the labelling	MT & LT							x	
B, R, P	Develop a Social and Solidarity Economy	MT & LT							x	

²⁴ ERA-MBT, 2017

	framework for marine biotechnologies								
SCIENCE EDUCATION									
C, B, R, P	Training for students and professionals in schools and universities and guidance for careers in marine biotechnologies	MT		x	x			x	x
C, R, Information multipliers	Raising awareness thanks to trained marine educators and information relays on marine biotechnologies	MT							x
OPEN ACCESS									
C, R, B, P	Knowledge transfer through an online platform, organised diffusion to target groups, award with popular vote to support research and innovation	ST		x					x
GENDER EQUALITY									
ETHICS									
C, R, B, P	Knowledge transfer through an online platform, organised diffusion to target groups, award with popular vote to support research and innovation	ST		x					x
C, B, R, P	Creation of a European Panel of Marine Bioethics with inventory of knowledge and projects as well as indicators and good practices	ST							x
C, B, R, P	Certification label of projects as an incentive process with a guideline for different actors for the sustainable development of marine biotech and an ethic committee that delivers the labelling	MT & LT							x
B, R, P	Develop a Social and Solidarity Economy framework for marine biotechnologies	MT & LT							x
GOVERNANCE									
C, B, R, P	Training for students and professionals in schools and universities and guidance for careers in marine biotechnologies	MT		x	x			x	x
C, B, R, P	Creation of a European Panel of Marine Bioethics with inventory of knowledge and projects as well as indicators and good practices	ST							x
C, B, R, P	Certification label of projects as an incentive process with a guideline for different actors for the sustainable development of marine biotech and an ethic committee that delivers the labelling	MT & LT							x
B, R, P	Develop a Social and Solidarity Economy framework for marine biotechnologies	MT & LT							x

Table 7 Final roadmap produced by the participants of the WON workshop in Boulogne-sur-Mer, France

The RRI dimension that scored the biggest number of actions was *Public Engagement*. This may be due to several factors such as the nature of the hot topic which was quite complex, requiring a greater level of public understanding and the composition of the group: a large majority of representatives from civil society and citizens.

The main messages were the importance of information and knowledge transfer between all the stakeholders, as well as the implementation of a legal and economic framework for marine biotechnologies. The role of *Governance* and *Ethics* were therefore very significant. Overall, the participants agreed on the need for better sharing of information and good practices

between the different sectors and the need to frame marine biotechnology to be a more sustainable and responsible innovation.

Lastly, the outcomes of the workshop strongly validate the role of projects like MARINA, not only in engaging multiple stakeholders on research and innovation topics, but also in developing the online Platform. The participants’ focus on the need for multi-stakeholder engagement and their appreciation for the concept and format of the workshop itself made it clear that scaling up this type of participatory activity on the topic of marine biotechnologies for roll-out at European level would be greatly beneficial. Likewise, the specific recommendations for training, knowledge transfer through an online platform and raising awareness made it clear that the MARINA platform can serve as a key tool in disseminating knowledge and as a hub for stakeholders to engage on the societal concerns around the topic of marine biotechnologies and their role in combatting marine pollution.

5.3.1.6 Results of the workshop in Italy (the Mediterranean Sea) held by ISPRA, Rome

Italian seas are constantly at risk of oil spill. From 1977 to 1998 more than 160 accidents occurred, affecting the Italian waters and coastlines, with a total of more than 200,000 tonnes of hazardous substances released.

Oil spills can have disastrous consequences for society: economically, environmentally, and socially. Increasing the efficiency of the conventional methods (chemicals or physical), which rarely achieve complete clean-up of oil spills, seems to be a priority for Italy as well for all Mediterranean countries. The natural marine cleaning process has not evolved to face huge amounts of oil such as those discarded in the marine environment during oil spill. Researchers are investigating methodologies to speed up this process, called bioremediation.

The topic of the workshop held by ISPRA was “Oil spills at sea: what if the solution were bacteria?” The workshop aimed at answering the triggering question: “What Responsible Research and Innovation actions are needed to make marine bioremediation application sustainable?”

Table 8 shows the roadmap of actions suggested during this workshop.

WHY - overall objectives for making a roadmap and a common vision		To benefit from the results of the researches in marine biotechnologies in a sustainable way. To provide the decision chain, in the future, with another tool to be used in case of oil pollution in the marine environment.								
WHO Stakeholder target group(s) Choose from : Citizens/CSOs/NGOs (C), Business/Industry (B), Researchers & Academia (R), Policymakers & implementers (P) Other (Please specify)	WHAT Action	WHEN How long will it take to complete the action? short (now-1 year), medium (2-5 years), long term (over 5 years)	OVERALL GOAL: Which societal challenge will the action contribute to? Choose from:							
			Health, democratic change and well-being	Food security, agriculture, marine and maritime and inland water research, bioeconomy.	Secure, clean and efficient energy	Smart, green and integrated transport	Climate action, environment, resource efficiency, and raw materials	Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies	Secure societies	
PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT										
C, R, P	Direct involvement of stakeholders								x	
C, B, R, P	Apply pressure on policymakers to create appropriate legislation								x	
C, R	Dissemination of messages through diversified communication tools such as key ambassadors								x	
C, R, P	Dissemination of results								x	
C, R	Inform the public about the real importance of bacteria								x	
C, R, P	Testing on the field and spread of the positive results								x	
C, B, R	Information and dissemination activities								x	

C, R, P	Raise awareness and prepare the political class and citizens for the problem through an internationally coordinated communication campaign								x
C, B, R, P	Disclose the results of the research not only in scientific journals to reach the widest possible audience, also attracting investors and start-up								x
B, P	Getting support from businesses and activities that use the resources to be protected			x		x	x		
B, R	Identify through industries the most appropriate regulatory tools to develop innovative technologies			x		x	x	x	
R, P	Collaborate with policymakers and urge them to define a regulatory framework								x
B, R	Start experimentation activities that involve researchers and specific stakeholders			x		x	x		
C, B, R, P	Increase knowledge about bacteria and their functions in marine ecosystems								x
SCIENCE EDUCATION									
C, R, O	Dissemination of messages through diversified communication tools such as key ambassadors								x
B, R	Increase of knowledge / scientific evidence; Increase knowledge about bacteria and their functions in marine ecosystems			x		x	x		
C, R, P, O	Dissemination of results								x
C, R, O	Inform the public about the real importance of bacteria								x
C, R, P, O	Testing on the field and spread of the positive results								x
C, B, R, O	Information and dissemination activities								x
C, R, O	Dissemination of results								x
C, R, P, O	Raise awareness and prepare the political class and citizens for the problem through an internationally coordinated communication campaign								x
C, B, R, P, O	Disclose the results of the research not only in scientific journals to reach the widest possible audience, also attracting investors and start-up								x
OPEN ACCESS									
C, R, O	Dissemination of messages through diversified communication tools such as key ambassadors								x
B, R	Increase of knowledge / scientific evidence			x		x	x		
B, R, P	Develop an accessible and easily updatable database			x		x	x		
B, R, P	Create a network of laboratories that integrate the different aspects of the topic								x
C, R, P, O	Dissemination of results								x
C, R, O	Inform the public about the real importance of bacteria								x
C, R, P, O	Testing on the field and spread of the positive results								x
C, B, R, O	Information and dissemination activities								x
B, R, P	Evaluate a method for assessing the effects of new technologies in the field			x		x	x		
R, P	Create a network between researchers and policymakers								x

B, R, P	Create a network to exchange data and best practices								x
C, R, O	Dissemination of results								x
C, R, P, O	Raise awareness and prepare the political class and citizens for the problem through an internationally coordinated communication campaign								x
C, B, R, P, O	Disclose the results of the research not only in scientific journals to reach the widest possible audience, also attracting investors and start-up								x
B, R, P	Deepen and experiment with new technologies			x		x		x	
B, R	Start experimentation activities that involve researchers and specific stakeholders			x		x		x	
B, R, P	Prepare operational instructions /guidelines to use new technologies								x
C, B, R, P, O	Increase knowledge about bacteria and their functions in marine ecosystems								x
GENDER EQUALITY									
ETHICS									
C, B, R, P	Apply pressure on policymakers to create appropriate legislation								x
B, R, P	"In-situ" experimentation			x		x		x	
B, R, P	Create a network of laboratories that integrate the different aspects of the topic								x
B, R, P	Test the effectiveness of new technologies on real, circumscribable and authorized scenarios			x		x		x	
B, R, P	Create a network to exchange data and best practices								x
C, B, R, P	Disclose the results of the research not only in scientific journals to reach the widest possible audience, also attracting investors and start-up								x
C, B, R, P	Allow field experimentation in a context of shared rules attentive to the impact on society			x		x		x	
B, R, P	Deepen and experiment with new technologies			x		x		x	
B, R	Carry out experiments in order to have robust data, both from laboratory analysis and from field studies			x		x		x	
GOVERNANCE									
C, R, P, O	Direct involvement of stakeholders								x
C, B, R, P, O	Apply pressure on policymakers to create appropriate legislation								x
B, R, P	"In-situ" experimentation			x		x		x	
B, R, P	Develop an accessible and easily updatable database			x		x		x	
B, R, P	Create a network of laboratories that integrate the different aspects of the topic								x
B, R, P	Test the effectiveness of new technologies on real, circumscribable and authorized scenarios			x		x		x	
R, P	Create a network between researchers and policymakers								x
B, R, P	Create a network to exchange data and best practices								x
P	Legislative interventions at the end of the whole process of study and dissemination								x
B, R, P	Funding research and development actions on these issues			x		x		x	x
B, R, P	To implement initiatives that bring the potentialities of the proposed technology to								x

	the attention of decision makers								
	To facilitate the development of technologies through legislative and financial instruments			x		x	x	x	
B, P	Getting support from businesses and activities that use the resources to be protected			x		x	x		
C, B, R, P, O	Allow field experimentation in a context of shared rules attentive to the impact on society			x		x	x		
B, R, P	Deepen and experiment with new technologies			x		x	x		
B, R	Identify through industries the most appropriate regulatory tools to develop innovative technologies			x		x	x	x	
R, P	Collaborate with policymakers and urge them to define a regulatory framework								x
B, R, P	Prepare operational instructions /guidelines to use new technologies								x
B, R, P	Monitoring of short and long-term marine ecosystems			x		x	x		

Table 8 Final roadmap produced by the participants of the workshop in Rome on Marine Biotechnology, Italy

On the proposed actions, none of the related stakeholder groups overcome the other, confirming that all the groups are crucial, even if formed by common citizens, when dealing with complex and interdisciplinary problems such as the introduction of a completely new methodology in the emergency procedures for oil spills.

Among the RRI dimensions, *Governance*, closely followed by *Open Science/Open Access*, were those related to the highest number of actions.

The key issue emerging from the discussion and from the actions was that regulations and legislations about the release of bacteria at sea should be in line with the achievements of the last 20 years of research. At least a regulatory framework is needed, according to the participants to develop this innovative sector. RRI, while fostering the consideration of all the key stakeholder groups, a wider spreading of the scientific achievements, free and easy access to data and results, inclusive and adaptive governance models which take into consideration all the factors, could highly facilitate this process.

5.3.1.7 Results of the workshop in Portugal (the Atlantic Ocean) held by FRCT, the Azores

The Azores are characterized by a strong geothermal activity, which supports unique terrestrial and marine environments. These highly mineralized environments serve as suitable habitats to microorganisms and invertebrates. Their metabolic activity produces new biological compounds of biotechnological interest for industrial enzymes, pharmaceutical, agro-food sector, bio-energy and bio-remediation, and scientific research products.

Several research projects carried out by the IMAR Centre from the University of the Azores have focused on such potential. The results are clear: the Azorean hydrothermal vent fields can provide many important biotechnological resources. Scientists at the recently created R&D centre OKEANOS are beginning to decipher all the biotechnological potential around the Azores Sea. Their work will serve as an example on how to exploit various marine environments in other parts of Portugal.

The topic of the workshop held by FRCT was “*Marine Biotechnology: the opportunity of a sustainable economy*”. The workshop aimed at answering the triggering question: “*What Responsible Research and Innovation actions are needed to make marine biotechnologies economically sustainable in the Azores?*”

Table 9 below shows the roadmap of actions suggested during this workshop.

WHY - overall objectives for making a roadmap and a common vision		What Responsible Research and Innovation actions are needed to make marine biotechnologies economically sustainable in the Azores?							
WHO Stakeholder target group(s): Citizens/CSOs/ NGOs (C), Business/Industry (B), Researchers & Academia (R), Policymakers & implementers (P) Other (Please specify)	WHAT Action	WHEN How long will it take to complete the action? short (now-1 year), medium (2-5 years), long term (over 5 year)	OVERALL GOAL: Which societal challenge will the action contribute to?						
			Health, democratic change and well-being	Food security, agriculture, marine and maritime and inland water research, bioeconomy.	Secure, clean and efficient energy	Smart, green and integrated transport	Climate action, environment, resource efficiency, and raw materials	Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies	
PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT									
C, R, B, P	Introducing marine biotech (MB) in schools	ST & MT		x			x	x	
P, B	Improve the interaction of knowledge centres with society	ST		x			x	x	
R, B, P	Dissemination and awareness campaigns about MB	ST & MT		x			x	x	
P	Creating participatory budgets for science	ST & MT		x			x	x	
R, B, P	Creating an open data platform for MB	ST		x			x	x	
C, R, B, P	Encouraging the use of alternatives to synthetic ones, which have a low impact on finite resources	ST		x			x	x	
R, B, P	Create a marine biotechnology society to promote this area of knowledge	ST & MT		x			x	x	
R, B, P	Attract research and support industries that take advantage of biological waste generated by other industries	ST		x			x	x	
C, R, B, P	Involving people in the entire process, ensuring adjusted communication to all	ST & MT						x	
SCIENCE EDUCATION									
C, R, B, P	Introducing marine biotech (MB) in schools	ST & MT		x			x	x	
P, B	Improve the interaction of knowledge centres with society	ST & MT		x			x	x	
R, B, P	Dissemination and awareness campaigns about MB	ST & MT		x			x	x	
P	Creating participatory budgets for science	ST & MT		x			x	x	
R, B, P	Create a marine biotechnology society to promote this area of knowledge	ST		x			x	x	
C, R, B, P	Involving people in the entire process, ensuring adjusted communication to all	ST & MT		x			x	x	
P	Create facilitation mechanisms for knowledge transfer between research and industry	ST		x			x	x	
OPEN ACCESS									
C, R, B, P	Introducing marine biotech (MB) in schools	ST & MT		x			x	x	
P, B	Improve the interaction of knowledge centres with society	ST		x			x	x	
R, B, P	Dissemination and awareness campaigns about MB	ST & MT		x			x	x	

R, B, P	Create a marine biotechnology society to promote this area of knowledge	ST & MT		x			x	x	
R, B, P	Involve and empower the media	ST & MT						x	
P	Creating participatory budgets for science	ST & MT						x	
R, B, P	Creating an open data platform for MB	ST & MT		x			x	x	
R, B, P	Creating a seal of biological sustainability, environmental and called source	ST		x			x	x	
C, R, B, P	Characterize and strengthen the Azores' specific value chain, leveraging the link between economic and social potential: knowledge, consumption and promotion	ST & MT		x			x	x	
P	Creation of public biobanks	ST		x			x	x	
R, B, P	Benchmarking of good practices on islands	ST		x			x	x	
R, B, P	Create facilitation mechanisms for knowledge transfer between research and industry	ST & MT		x			x	x	
R, B, P	Use of the sample for several studies	ST		x			x	x	
P	Centralized and shared infrastructures for research on MB	ST & MT		x			x	x	
C, R, B, P	Real Market needs research - Market Oriented Research	ST & MT		x			x	x	
GENDER EQUALITY									
P	Specific legislation to implement gender equality and ethics	ST & MT						x	
C, R, B, P	Introducing marine biotech (MB) in schools	ST & MT		x			x	x	
P, B	Improve the interaction of knowledge centres with society	ST & MT		x			x	x	
R, B, P	Dissemination and awareness campaigns about MB	ST & MT		x			x	x	
P	Creating participatory budgets for science	ST & MT		x			x	x	
B, P	Attract research and support industries that take advantage of biological waste generated by other industries	ST & MT		x			x	x	
P	Centralized and shared infrastructures for research on MB	ST & MT		x			x	x	
ETHICS									
P	Specific legislation to implement gender equality and ethics	ST & MT						x	
P	Creating participatory budgets for science	ST & MT		x			x	x	
R, B, P	Creating an open data platform for MB	ST & MT		x			x	x	
R, B, P	Use of the sample for several studies	ST		x			x	x	
R, B, P	Creation of public biobanks	ST		x			x	x	
R, B, P	Creating a seal of biological sustainability, environmental and called source	ST		x			x	x	
R, B, P	Create facilitation mechanisms for knowledge transfer between research and industry	ST		x			x	x	
R, B, P	Study and development of a legal framework adapted to the specificities and needs of the region	ST		x			x	x	
P	Creation of a government cabinet that produces and enforces a legal framework, as well as promoting investment policies to attract private capital	ST		x			x	x	
C, R, B, P	Promote and improve mechanisms that can filter and guarantee the reliability of information that reaches citizens	ST & MT		x			x	x	

GOVERNANCE									
P	Creating participatory budgets for science	ST & MT		x			x	x	
R, B, P	Create a marine biotechnology society to promote this area of knowledge	ST & MT		x			x	x	
R, B, P	Creating an open data platform for MB	ST		x			x	x	
C, R, B, P	Introducing marine biotech (MB) in schools	ST & MT		x			x	x	
P, B	Improve the interaction of knowledge centres with society	ST		x			x	x	
C, R, B, P	Dissemination and awareness campaigns about MB	ST & MT		x			x	x	
R, B, P	Involve and empower the media	ST & MT						x	
C, R, B, P	Encouraging the use of alternatives to synthetic ones, which have a low impact on finite resources	ST		x			x	x	

Table 9 Final roadmap produced by the participants of the workshop in Ribeira Grande, São Miguel, Azores, Portugal

The RRI dimension that scored the highest number of actions was *Governance*. This may be due to several factors such as the nature of the hot topic, the composition of the group and to the fact that the workshop was hosted in collaboration with EurOcean, which was launching the Deep-sea Mining topic.

The main message was the importance of *Science Education* for all stakeholder groups: for the general public to make informed responsible consumption choices, for business and industry professionals to produce socially and environmentally acceptable goods and services, for scientists to scale up research to bring responses to sustainable marine biotech challenges, and finally for policymakers to reinforce policies and adopt coherent legislative frameworks of economic competitiveness and sustainability of marine biotech in the Azores and to create research infrastructures and offer conditions for marine biotech research in the region.

5.3.2 Sea Transportation

5.3.2.1 Description

Sea transportation in Europe is facing many challenges:

- Increasing traffic and maritime activities,
- Increased size of ships,
- Increased number of ships carrying oil and hazardous substances and increased risk of spillage,
- Increased ship waste and discharges,
- Increased pressures on coastal and harbour areas,
- Increased environmental stress on species (introduction of non-indigenous species, underwater noise, natural habitat destruction),
- Increased air and sea pollution.

However, there are many opportunities for sustainability in this sector: advancing cargo ship technology to increase speed while reducing the environmental impact of transportation, improving the safety of crew and passengers, improving the quality of life in coastal and harbour areas, developing innovative infrastructure in harbour areas that maximise the economic value of the commercial and tourism activities while reducing the impact of the coastal areas and populations.

To tackle conflicting interests and the differences in regulations at European or international level, it is clear that collaboration between all stakeholders needs to take place.

5.3.2.2 Results of the workshop in Estonia (the Baltic Sea) held by AHHA, Tartu

Sea transportation has recently been the focus in Estonian local media and the public with only one issue: how to get Estonian cargo ships to sail under the Estonian flag and thus pay taxes to Estonia (0 out of 60 big Estonian cargo ships sail

under the Estonian flag). If ships do not pay taxes to Estonia, then they will not use any potential environmentally sustainable business tax incentives. With this issue in place, it seems that concentrating efforts to make sea transport more sustainable is not economically beneficial.

There is potential left to unlock in the sea transport sector, with new technologies emerging gradually, such as autonomous ships, while ports are not working at maximum capacity (shipments through the Port of Tallinn fell by 38,7% in January 2017, compared to January 2016). This potential should be used if sea transportation can affirm itself as the most environmental friendly solution. This can only be achieved by making sea transportation sustainable, also in terms of RRI, by concentrating research where it is necessary.

The topic of the workshop held by AHHA was “Turning sea transportation threats into sea transportation opportunities on the Baltic Sea”. The workshop aimed at answering the triggering question: “What Responsible Research and Innovation actions are needed to make maritime transport effective and sustainable?”

Table 10 shows the roadmap of actions suggested during this workshop.

WHY - overall objectives for making a roadmap and a common vision		Adjusting legislation to allow for more open access to marine-related research								
WHO Stakeholder target group(s) Choose from : Citizens/CSOs/NGOs (C), Business/Industry (B), Researchers & Academia (R), Policymakers & implementers (P) Other (Please specify)	WHAT Action	WHEN How long will it take to complete the action? short (now-1 year), medium (2-5 years), long term (over 5 years)	OVERALL GOAL: Which societal challenge will the action contribute to? Choose from:							
			Health, democratic change and well-being	Food security, agriculture, marine and maritime and inland water research, bioeconomy.	Secure, clean and efficient energy	Smart, green and integrated transport	Climate action, environment, resource efficiency, and raw materials	Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies	Secure societies	
PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT										
R	Get researchers involved in awareness raising campaigns	MT		x		x				
P	Reduce bureaucracy and documentation, unified approach throughout the EU	MT		x		x				
C	Strengthen the link between non-governmental organizations and citizens	LT		x		x				
B	Strengthen the link between business aspirations and environmental goals	LT		x		x				
SCIENCE EDUCATION										
R	Revisit the marine curricula used in academia	MT				x				
P	Supervise more the quality of marine education provided in schools	ST				x				
C	Allow citizens to determine their level of involvement in shaping marine education	MT				x				
B	Consult the industry on their needs in marine education	MT				x				
OPEN ACCESS										
R	Empower researchers to call on incompetent media coverage of research data	MT			x					
P	Encourage policymakers to revalue the funding schemes for marine sector	MT			x					

	operators								
C	Inform the public about the possibility to get acquainted with open research data	ST			x				
B	Encourage the creation of a test area for self-sailing ships on the sea	MT			x				
GENDER EQUALITY									
ETHICS									
R	Insisting on ethical checks of all new marine research	MT				x			
P	Making sure marine issues are communicated in the media in an ethical manner	MT				x			
C	Empowering the citizens to report unethical behaviour/decisions	LT				x			
B	Endorsing ethical business models	MT				x			
GOVERNANCE									
R	Base actions to put in place on research findings	MT			x	x	x		
P	Add marine consideration into the priorities of policymakers and implementers	LT			x	x	x		
C	Consulting with the public on the feasibility of marine-related legislative actions	MT			x	x	x		
B	Granting businesses incentives and making use of novel technologies to apply marine protection methods in their daily work	LT			x	x	x		

Table 10 Final roadmap produced by the participants of the workshop in Tartu, Estonia

The RRI dimension that scored the biggest number of actions was *Governance*. This may be due to several factors such as the nature of the hot topic, the composition of the group and to the fact that in the local culture ground-breaking changes often result from legislative action taken by the governing bodies and institutions.

The main message was that the government and other governing institutions need to find a way to introduce legislature that both protects the natural environment of the Baltic Sea, as well as promotes the implementation of new technologies and solutions that help make sea transportation a viable sector of activity in the region. The importance of *Science Education* for all stakeholder groups was also stressed: for the general public to make informed choices about the pros and cons of marine transportation, for business and industry professionals to consult with scientists while developing new goods and services, for scientists to scale up research on the sustainability of sea transportation and for policymakers to reinforce policies and adopt coherent legislative frameworks of economic competitiveness and sustainability of the Baltic Sea.

5.3.2.3 Results of the workshop in Greece (the Aegean Sea) held by SEVEN, Athens

With more than 480,000 annual ships movement around the world, shipping is considered as the primary contributor to the transfer of non-indigenous species (NIS) through ballast water. In the Mediterranean, the NIS increase at the rate of one every two weeks, and it is reported that around 1,000 are present. NIS represent a threat to the local biodiversity, which can generate a series of socio-economic and human health impacts.

To prevent the spread of NIS, the International Convention for the Control and Management of Ships' Ballast Water and Sediments (BWMC) (IMO, 2004) entered into force in September 2017, establishing standards and procedures for the management and control of ballast water and sediments, applicable to vessels of 172 member states. The implementation of the BWMC presents some difficulties including the high cost of the Ballast Water Treatment Systems (BWTS), as well as issues related to their installation (when retrofitting), operation and maintenance. Technical developments to further

address the problem of IAS have intensified, focusing on prevention (ballast water treatment systems), early detection (metagenomics) and eradication of invasive alien species.

The topic of the workshop held by SEVEN was “Ballast Water Management and the Marine Environment”. The workshop aimed at answering the triggering question: “Which Responsible Research and Innovation actions are needed to make maritime transport sustainable while safeguarding the marine environment?”

Table 11 shows the roadmap of actions suggested during this workshop.

WHY - overall objectives for making a roadmap and a common vision		TO FACILITATE THE PROPER IMPLEMENTATION OF BALLAST WATER MANAGEMENT AND BWMC TO IMPROVE THE SUSTAINABILITY OF MARITIME TRANSPORT WHILE SAFEGUARDING THE ENVIRONMENT							
WHO Stakeholder target group(s) Choose from : Citizens/CSOs/NGOs (C), Business/Industry (B), Researchers & Academia (R), Policymakers & implementers (P) Other (Please specify)	WHAT Action	WHEN How long will it take to complete the action? short (now-1 year), medium (2-5 years), long term (over 5 years)	OVERALL GOAL: Which societal challenge will the action contribute to? Choose from:						
			Health, democratic change and well-being	Food security, agriculture, marine and maritime and inland water research, bioeconomy.	Secure, clean and efficient energy	Smart, green and integrated transport	Climate action, environment, resource efficiency, and raw materials	Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies	Secure societies
PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT									
P, Ship-owners/shipping companies	Develop clarifications regarding the application of contingency measures of the BWMC	ST				x	x		
C, R, P	Define and implement criteria for delineating "same risk areas"	ST				x	x		
B, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies, Classification societies	Harmonize systems' type approval, and apply less stringent compliance criteria (at least in the current phase of the BWMC implementation)	ST-MT				x			
P, Classification societies	Promote (at central level, via IMO) the proper and timely dissemination of regional/local regulations and type approvals to third parties. Possibly develop an electronic platform (protected intranet) for this purpose	MT				x			
C, B, R, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies, Classification societies	Establish a framework (including protocol, indicators, etc.) for the collection and exchange of data regarding different parameters and components, so that the overall system efficacy can be assessed in the short, medium and long term	MT-LT				x	x		
C, R, P	Develop operational IAS monitoring programmes to produce the necessary scientific evidence/data, allowing thus for transparency	MT	x	x		x	x	x	x
B, R, Ship-owners/shipping companies	Thorough analysis of the full set of BWT system requirements (installation constraints, voyage characteristics, design limitations, energy specifications, etc.) and selection of BWTS based on robust engineering studies (as opposed to an a priori arbitrary selection)	ST				x	x		
C, B, Ship-owners/shipping companies	Strengthen the technical capacity of the crew through intensified crew training (responsibility of ship-owners). Reinforce the crew training offered by the BWTS makers and customize it to better fit the crew needs (responsibility of the makers)	ST-MT				x			

B, R, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies	Conduct robust Technology Readiness Assessments (TRA) based on unbiased data and communicate to the IMO issues related to the operational readiness of BWTS so that less stringent criteria apply during the current transitional phase	ST-MT		x		x	x		
B, R, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies, RTD funders	Invest in technological development of BWTS and their large scale testing and validation under fully operational conditions (reaching TRL7 ²⁵ or higher)	MT		x		x	x	x	
C, B, R, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies, classification societies	Establish procedures for communication and feedback between all actors involved (ship operators, vendors, engineers, makers, etc.) as this is necessary to in order to optimize the BWTSs' performance. Explore the use of dedicated electronic platforms, forums, etc. for that purpose.	ST-MT				x		x	x
C, B, R, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies	Strengthen and intensify the presence of the Greek maritime community in international organizations to leverage international decision-making regarding BWV	ST-MT		x		x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P, Port authorities, Municipalities/ Local administration	Construction of Port reception facilities	MT-LT	x			x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P	Develop eco-labelling schemas for the BWTS (e.g. based on the utilization of the by-products)	MT		x	x	x	x	x	
SCIENCE EDUCATION									
C, R, P	Develop operational IAS monitoring programmes to produce the necessary scientific evidence/data, allowing thus for transparency	MT	x	x		x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P, Port authorities, Municipalities/ Local administration	Construction of Port reception facilities	MT-LT	x			x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P	Develop eco-labelling schemas for the BWTS (e.g. based on the utilization of the by-products)	MT		x	x	x	x	x	
B, R, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies	Link to H2020 Blue Growth initiatives and funding mechanisms to boost BWTS technology development, operational application, system optimization, etc.	ST-MT		x	x	x	x	x	
OPEN ACCESS									
P, Ship-owners/shipping companies	Develop clarifications regarding the application of contingency measures of the BWMC	ST				x	x		
C, R, P	Define and implement criteria for delineating "same risk areas"	ST				x	x		
B, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies, Classification societies	Harmonize systems' type approval, and apply less stringent compliance criteria (at least in the current phase of the BWMC implementation)	ST-MT				x			
P, Classification societies	Promote (at central level, via IMO) the proper and timely dissemination of regional/ local regulations and type approvals to third parties. Possibly develop an electronic	MT				x			

²⁵ Technology readiness levels (TRLs)

TRL 7: system prototype demonstration in operational environment

TRL 8: system complete and qualified

TRL 9: actual system proven in operational environment

	platform (protected intranet) for this purpose								
C, B, R, P, Ship-owners/ shipping companies, Classification societies	Establish a framework (including protocol, indicators, etc.) for the collection and exchange of data regarding different parameters and components, so that the overall system efficacy can be assessed in the short, medium and long term	MT-LT				x	x		
C, R, P	Develop operational IAS monitoring programmes to produce the necessary scientific evidence/ data, allowing thus for transparency	MT	x	x		x	x	x	x
B, R, Ship-owners/shipping companies	Thorough analysis of the full set of BWT system requirements (installation constraints, voyage characteristics, design limitations, energy specifications, etc.) and selection of BWTS based on robust engineering studies (as opposed to an a priori arbitrary selection)	ST				x	x		
C, B, Ship-owners/shipping companies	Strengthen the technical capacity of the crew through intensified crew training (responsibility of ship-owners). Reinforce the crew training offered by the BWTS makers and customize it to better fit the crew needs (responsibility of the makers)	ST-MT				x			
B, R, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies	Conduct robust Technology Readiness Assessments (TRA) based on unbiased data and communicate to the IMO issues related to the operational readiness of BWTS so that less stringent criteria apply during the current transitional phase	ST-MT		x		x	x		
B, R, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies, RTD funders	Invest in technological development of BWTS and their large scale testing and validation under fully operational conditions (reaching TRL ²⁶ or higher)	MT		x		x	x	x	
C, B, R, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies, classification societies	Establish procedures for communication and feedback between all actors involved (ship operators, vendors, engineers, makers, etc.) as this is necessary to in order to optimize the BWTSs' performance. Explore the use of dedicated electronic platforms, forums, etc. for that purpose.	ST-MT				x		x	x
C, B, R, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies	Strengthen and intensify the presence of the Greek maritime community in international organizations to leverage international decision-making regarding BWM	ST-MT		x		x	x	x	x
P	Provide incentives and benefits (e.g. subsidies) as applied for the case of air emissions (linked to TECH2a)	MT-LT				x	x	x	
B, R, P, Local and regional administrations	Invest in the development of floating installations	MT-LT		x		x	x	x	
B, R, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies	Explore the feasibility of "ballast-free ships"	MT-LT		x		x	x	x	
B, R, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies	Explore the feasibility of "permanent ballast"	MT-LT		x		x	x	x	
B, R, P, Ship-	Select and underpin/promote solutions	MT-LT		x		x	x	x	x

²⁶ Technology readiness levels (TRLs)

TRL 7: system prototype demonstration in operational environment

TRL 8: system complete and qualified

TRL 9: actual system proven in operational environment

owners/shipping companies	which can simultaneously reduce other environmental footprint								
C, B, R, P	Develop eco-labelling schemas for the BWTS (e.g. based on the utilization of the by-products)	MT	x	x	x	x	x		
C, B, P	The relevant EU Directives (Marine Strategy Framework Directive-MSFD, EU Regulation 1143/2014 on Invasive Alien Species) are different in scope that the BWMC. Explore the relevance and applicability of an EU specific regulation on BWM	MT			x	x	x		
B, R, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies	Link to H2020 Blue Growth initiatives and funding mechanisms to boost BWTS technology development, operational application, system optimization, etc.	ST-MT	x	x	x	x	x		
GENDER EQUALITY									
B, R, Ship-owners/shipping companies	Thorough analysis of the full set of BWT system requirements (installation constraints, voyage characteristics, design limitations, energy specifications, etc.) and selection of BWTS based on robust engineering studies (as opposed to an a priori arbitrary selection)	ST			x	x			
C, B, Ship-owners/shipping companies	Strengthen the technical capacity of the crew through intensified crew training (responsibility of ship-owners). Reinforce the crew training offered by the BWTS makers and customize it to better fit the crew needs (responsibility of the makers)	ST-MT			x				
B, R, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies	Conduct robust Technology Readiness Assessments (TRA) based on unbiased data and communicate to the IMO issues related to the operational readiness of BWTS so that less stringent criteria apply during the current transitional phase	ST-MT	x		x	x			
B, R, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies, RTD funders	Invest in technological development of BWTS and their large scale testing and validation under fully operational conditions (reaching TRL ²⁷ or higher)	MT	x		x	x	x		
C, B, R, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies, classification societies	Establish procedures for communication and feedback between all actors involved (ship operators, vendors, engineers, makers, etc.) as this is necessary to in order to optimize the BWTSs' performance. Explore the use of dedicated electronic platforms, forums, etc. for that purpose.	ST-MT			x		x	x	
C, B, R, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies	Strengthen and intensify the presence of the Greek maritime community in international organizations to leverage international decision-making regarding BWM	ST-MT	x		x	x	x	x	
P	Provide incentives and benefits (e.g. subsidies) as applied for the case of air emissions (linked to TECH2a)	MT-LT			x	x	x		
B, R, P, Local and regional administrations	Invest in the development of floating installations	MT-LT	x		x	x	x		
B, R, P, Ship-owners/shipping	Explore the feasibility of "ballast-free ships"	MT-LT	x		x	x	x		

²⁷ Technology readiness levels (TRLs)

TRL 7: system prototype demonstration in operational environment

TRL 8: system complete and qualified

TRL 9: actual system proven in operational environment

companies									
B, R, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies	Explore the feasibility of “permanent ballast”	MT-LT		x		x	x	x	
B, R, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies	Select and underpin/promote solutions which can simultaneously reduce other environmental footprint	MT-LT		x		x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P	Develop eco-labelling schemas for the BWTS (e.g. based on the utilization of the by-products)	MT		x	x	x	x	x	
B, R, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies	Link to H2020 Blue Growth initiatives and funding mechanisms to boost BWTS technology development, operational application, system optimization, etc.	ST-MT		x	x	x	x	x	
ETHICS									
P, Ship-owners/shipping companies	Develop clarifications regarding the application of contingency measures of the BWMC	ST				x	x		
C, R, P	Define and implement criteria for delineating "same risk areas"	ST				x	x		
B, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies, Classification societies	Harmonize systems' type approval, and apply less stringent compliance criteria (at least in the current phase of the BWMC implementation)	ST-MT				x			
P, Classification societies	Promote (at central level, via IMO) the proper and timely dissemination of regional/local regulations and type approvals to third parties. Possibly develop an electronic platform (protected intranet) for this purpose	MT				x			
C, B, R, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies, Classification societies	Establish a framework (including protocol, indicators, etc.) for the collection and exchange of data regarding different parameters and components, so that the overall system efficacy can be assessed in the short, medium and long term	MT-LT				x	x		
C, R, P	Develop operational IAS monitoring programmes to produce the necessary scientific evidence/data, allowing thus for transparency	MT	x	x		x	x	x	x
B, R, Ship-owners/shipping companies	Thorough analysis of the full set of BWT system requirements (installation constraints, voyage characteristics, design limitations, energy specifications, etc.) and selection of BWTS based on robust engineering studies (as opposed to an a priori arbitrary selection)	ST				x	x		
C, B, Ship-owners/shipping companies	Strengthen the technical capacity of the crew through intensified crew training (responsibility of ship-owners). Reinforce the crew training offered by the BWTS makers and customize it to better fit the crew needs (responsibility of the makers)	ST-MT				x			
B, R, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies	Conduct robust Technology Readiness Assessments (TRA) based on unbiased data and communicate to the IMO issues related to the operational readiness of BWTS so that less stringent criteria apply during the current transitional phase	ST-MT		x		x	x		
B, R, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies, RTD funders	Invest in technological development of BWTS and their large scale testing and validation under fully operational conditions (reaching TRL ²⁸ or higher)	MT		x		x	x	x	
C, B, R, P, Ship-	Establish procedures for communication and	ST-MT				x		x	x

²⁸ Technology readiness levels (TRLs)

TRL 7: system prototype demonstration in operational environment

TRL 8: system complete and qualified

TRL 9: actual system proven in operational environment

owners/shipping companies, classification societies	feedback between all actors involved (ship operators, vendors, engineers, makers, etc.) as this is necessary to in order to optimize the BWTSs' performance. Explore the use of dedicated electronic platforms, forums, etc. for that purpose.								
C, B, R, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies	Strengthen and intensify the presence of the Greek maritime community in international organizations to leverage international decision-making regarding BMW	ST-MT		x		x	x	x	x
P	Provide incentives and benefits (e.g. subsidies) as applied for the case of air emissions (linked to TECH2a)	MT-LT				x	x	x	
B, R, P, Local and regional administrations	Invest in the development of floating installations	MT-LT		x		x	x	x	
B, R, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies	Explore the feasibility of "ballast-free ships"	MT-LT		x		x	x	x	
B, R, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies	Explore the feasibility of "permanent ballast"	MT-LT		x		x	x	x	
B, R, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies	Select and underpin/promote solutions which can simultaneously reduce other environmental footprint	MT-LT		x		x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P, Port authorities, Municipalities/ Local administration	Construction of Port reception facilities	MT-LT	x			x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P	Develop eco-labelling schemas for the BWTS (e.g. based on the utilization of the by-products)	MT		x	x	x	x	x	
C, B, P	The relevant EU Directives (Marine Strategy Framework Directive-MSFD, EU Regulation 1143/2014 on Invasive Alien Species) are different in scope that the BWMC. Explore the relevance and applicability of an EU specific regulation on BWM	MT				x	x	x	
B, R, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies	Link to H2020 Blue Growth initiatives and funding mechanisms to boost BWTS technology development, operational application, system optimization, etc.	ST-MT		x	x	x	x	x	
GOVERNANCE									
P, Ship-owners/shipping companies	Develop clarifications regarding the application of contingency measures of the BWMC	ST				x	x		
C, R, P	Define and implement criteria for delineating "same risk areas"	ST				x	x		
B, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies, Classification societies	Harmonize systems' type approval, and apply less stringent compliance criteria (at least in the current phase of the BWMC implementation)	ST-MT				x			
P, Classification societies	Promote (at central level, via IMO) the proper and timely dissemination of regional/ local regulations and type approvals to third parties. Possibly develop an electronic platform (protected intranet) for this purpose	MT				x			
C, B, R, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies, Classification societies	Establish a framework (including protocol, indicators, etc.) for the collection and exchange of data regarding different parameters and components, so that the overall system efficacy can be assessed in the short, medium and long term	MT-LT				x	x		
C, R, P	Develop operational IAS monitoring programmes to produce the necessary scientific evidence/data, allowing thus for transparency	MT	x	x		x	x	x	x

B, R, Ship-owners/shipping companies	Thorough analysis of the full set of BWT system requirements (installation constraints, voyage characteristics, design limitations, energy specifications, etc.) and selection of BWTS based on robust engineering studies (as opposed to an a priori arbitrary selection)	ST				x	x		
C, B, Ship-owners/shipping companies	Strengthen the technical capacity of the crew through intensified crew training (responsibility of ship-owners). Reinforce the crew training offered by the BWTS makers and customize it to better fit the crew needs (responsibility of the makers)	ST-MT				x			
B, R, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies	Conduct robust Technology Readiness Assessments (TRA) based on unbiased data and communicate to the IMO issues related to the operational readiness of BWTS so that less stringent criteria apply during the current transitional phase	ST-MT		x		x	x		
B, R, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies, RTD funders	Invest in technological development of BWTS and their large scale testing and validation under fully operational conditions (reaching TRL ²⁹ or higher)	MT		x		x	x	x	
C, B, R, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies, classification societies	Establish procedures for communication and feedback between all actors involved (ship operators, vendors, engineers, makers, etc.) as this is necessary to in order to optimize the BWTSs' performance. Explore the use of dedicated electronic platforms, forums, etc. for that purpose.	ST-MT				x		x	x
C, B, R, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies	Strengthen and intensify the presence of the Greek maritime community in international organizations to leverage international decision-making regarding BWM	ST-MT		x		x	x	x	x
P	Provide incentives and benefits (e.g. subsidies) as applied for the case of air emissions (linked to TECH2a)	MT-LT				x	x	x	
B, R, P, Local and regional administrations	Invest in the development of floating installations	MT-LT		x		x	x	x	
B, R, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies	Explore the feasibility of "ballast-free ships"	MT-LT		x		x	x	x	
B, R, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies	Explore the feasibility of "permanent ballast"	MT-LT		x		x	x	x	
B, R, P, Ship-owners/shipping companies	Select and underpin/promote solutions which can simultaneously reduce other environmental footprint	MT-LT		x		x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P, Port authorities, Municipalities/ Local administration	Construction of Port reception facilities	MT-LT	x			x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P	Develop eco-labelling schemas for the BWTS (e.g. based on the utilization of the by-products)	MT		x	x	x	x	x	
C, B, P	The relevant EU Directives (Marine Strategy Framework Directive-MSFD, EU Regulation 1143/2014 on Invasive Alien Species) are	MT				x	x	x	

²⁹ Technology readiness levels (TRLs)

TRL 7: system prototype demonstration in operational environment

TRL 8: system complete and qualified

TRL 9: actual system proven in operational environment

	different in scope that the BWMC. Explore the relevance and applicability of an EU specific regulation on BWM								
B, R, P, Ship-owners/ shipping companies	Link to H2020 Blue Growth initiatives and funding mechanisms to boost BWTS technology development, operational application, system optimization, etc.	ST-MT		x	x	x	x	x	

Table 11 Final roadmap produced by the participants of the workshop in Piraeus, Greece

The RRI dimension that scored the biggest number of actions was *Governance*. This is because the implementation of the BWMC requires the cooperation of many actors: policymakers, national public authorities, port authorities (which can be public or private), inspectors, classification societies, technology developers/BWTS makers, engineering offices, implementers/end-users (ship-owners and their crew), NGOs, researchers and scientists involved in the monitoring and analysis of IAS. Streamlining these actors to work together and provide an educated feedback to each-other is crucial from a feasibility and sustainability point of view. A sustainable maritime transportation system requires international collaboration across borders. This entails partnerships and alliances between governments, shipping companies, classification societies, ship builders, technology manufacturers, R&D establishments and academic institutions.

One key message is the importance of clarifying aspects of the BWMC and bridging existing gaps in relation to the definition of same risk areas, the application of contingency measures, and the harmonization of the different system type approval across countries and regions. Guidelines need further updating. Also, in view of the current legislative gaps, the different system type approvals, and the current operational readiness of the BWTS, it is suggested that less stringent criteria apply at this phase of implementation.

Hands-on crew training, during all the implementation phases (from commissioning to on-board operation) is a high necessity and needs strengthening.

Finally, it is recognized that although ballast water is a major contributor to the introduction of invasive alien species, additional pathways do exist (spreading through hull fouling in leisure and fishing boats, corridors, aquaculture, aquarium trading) and thus it is important to develop adequate monitoring programmes which can identify, on one-hand, hot spots/priority areas, and analyse, on the other hand, the links between IAS and their vectors/pathways to establish the necessary scientific and transparent evidence base. This will boost acceptability and awareness of the problem.

5.3.2.4 Results of the workshop in Italy (the Mediterranean Sea) held by CNR, Rome

In 2017 in Italy, the maritime transport of goods increased by 3.4% in terms of tons. The country ranks third in the maritime transport of goods; it is preceded by the United Kingdom and the Netherlands (Italian Statistical Yearbook 2017 - related to the year 2015). In Lazio region, there are different and very relevant harbours both for the transport of goods and people, such as the Civitavecchia and the Fiumicino harbours.

The maritime transport is a very relevant topic as a strong demand for a development model (at a global level) that combines growth and employment safeguarding high-quality life styles is emerging, also ensuring that ecosystems (and therefore also the marine ecosystem) are safeguarded.

The topic of the workshop held by CNR was “*What will maritime transportation be like in 2050?*” The workshop aimed at answering the triggering question: “*What Responsible Research and Innovation actions are needed to reduce the impact of sea transportation on the environment and increase the safety levels?*”

Table 12 shows the roadmap of actions suggested during this workshop.

WHY - overall objectives for making a roadmap and a common vision									
TO ENSURE MARINE TRANSPORTATION SECURITY FOR PRESENT AND FUTURE GENERATIONS TO REDUCE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF MARITIME TRANSPORT AND INCREASE SAFETY LEVEL									
WHO Stakeholder target group(s) Choose from : Citizens/CSOs/NGOs (C), Business/Industry (B), Researchers & Academia (R), Policymakers & implementers (P) Other (Please specify)	WHAT Action	WHEN	OVERALL GOAL: Which societal challenge will the action contribute to? Choose from:						
		How long will it take to complete the action? short (now-1 year), medium (2-5 years), long term (over 5 years)	Health, democratic change and well-being	Food security, agriculture, marine and inland water research, bioeconomy.	Secure, clean and efficient energy	Smart, green and integrated transport	Climate action, environment, resource efficiency, and raw materials	Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies	Secure societies
PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT									
R, P, B, C	Integrating terrestrial-maritime transport systems and railway development for freight transport in ports	LT	x		x	x	x		
R, B, P	Sharing of infrastructures and information	LT		x		x		x	
R, B, P, C	Improving/developing technological solutions to support the "safe by design" of maritime systems	LT				x			x
R, B, P, C	Implementation of decision support systems (multi-parameter models) that consider safety, environmental impact, social impact and inter-modality	LT				x			x
R, B, P, C	Promote actions at transnational level (in the Mediterranean area) on the basis of a comparison among research, industry, policymakers and all stakeholders in the marine and maritime sectors	ST				x	x		
R, B, P, C	Provide education at all levels to reduce the environmental impact of maritime transport and increase safety level. Trainers and students should cooperate to better understand the importance of the marine environment, as a fundamental resource for the socio-economic development of Italy	ST		x	x	x		x	
R, B, P, C	Promote a closer collaboration between politicians and the population to increase funding for research, fishing, and transport. The importance of ports, gulfs, coasts and marine protected areas is fundamental for the Italian economic recovery	ST		x	x	x		x	
SCIENCE EDUCATION									
R, B, P, C	Provide education at all levels to reduce the environmental impact of maritime transport and increase safety level. Trainers and students should cooperate to better understand the importance of the marine environment, as a fundamental resource for the socio-economic development of Italy	ST		x	x	x		x	
R, B, P, C	Promote a closer collaboration between politicians and the population to increase funding for research, fishing, and transport. The importance of ports, gulfs, coasts and	ST		x	x	x		x	

	marine protected areas is fundamental for the Italian economic recovery								
OPEN ACCESS									
R, P, B, C	Integrating terrestrial-maritime transport systems and railway development for freight transport in ports	LT	x		x	x	x		
R, B	Advertising a national competition for the evaluation of advanced ship propulsion technologies	ST			x	x	x		
R, B, P	Sharing of infrastructures and information	LT		x		x		x	
R, B, C	Using nanotechnology for protection of cargo holds and tanks	MT & LT		x		x			
R, B, P, C	Improving/developing technological solutions to support the "safe by design" of maritime systems	LT				x			x
R, B, P, C	Implementation of decision support systems (multi-parameter models) that consider safety, environmental impact, social impact and inter-modality	LT				x			x
R, P, C	Development of information-based decision support tools, with automated intervention systems that can be used: a) in critical security and safety situations; b) for the matching of demand and supply of services	ST & MT				x		x	x
R, B, P, C	Provide education at all levels to reduce the environmental impact of maritime transport and increase safety level. Trainers and students should cooperate to better understand the importance of the marine environment, as a fundamental resource for the socio-economic development of Italy	ST		x	x	x		x	
R, B, P, C	Promote a closer collaboration between politicians and the population to increase funding for research, fishing, and transport. The importance of ports, gulfs, coasts and marine protected areas is fundamental for the Italian economic recovery	ST		x	x	x		x	
GENDER EQUALITY									
ETHICS									
R, B, C	Using nanotechnology for protection of cargo holds and tanks	MT & LT		x		x			
GOVERNANCE									
R, P, B, C	Integrating terrestrial-maritime transport systems and railway development for freight transport in ports	LT	x		x	x	x		
R, B, P	Sharing of infrastructures and information	LT		x		x		x	
R, B, P, C	Improving/developing technological solutions to support the "safe by design" of maritime systems	LT				x			x
R, B, P, C	Implementation of decision support systems (multi-parameter models) that consider safety, environmental impact, social impact and inter-modality	LT				x			x
R, P, C	Development of information-based decision	ST & MT				x		x	x

	support tools, with automated intervention systems that can be used: a) in critical security and safety situations; b) for the matching of demand and supply of services								
R, B, P, C	Provide education at all levels to reduce the environmental impact of maritime transport and increase safety level. Trainers and students should cooperate to better understand the importance of the marine environment, as a fundamental resource for the socio-economic development of Italy	ST		x	x	x			x
R, B, P, C	Promote a closer collaboration between politicians and the population to increase funding for research, fishing, and transport. The importance of ports, gulfs, coasts and marine protected areas is fundamental for the Italian economic recovery	ST		x	x	x			x

Table 12 Final roadmap produced by the participants of the CNR workshop in Rome, Italy

The RRI dimension that scored the biggest number of actions was *Open Access*. This may be due to multidisciplinary and transnationality of the issues related to maritime transport. Several disciplines are involved and *Open Access* can facilitate the mutual comprehension and collaboration.

The chief message was the need to promote actions at transnational level (in the Mediterranean area) on the basis of a comparison among research, industry, policymakers and all stakeholders in the marine and maritime sectors. This aims at sharing a common strategy for policies involving research, industry, policymakers and all stakeholders in the marine and maritime sectors.

5.3.2.5 Results of the workshop in Turkey (Sea of Marmara) held by IU, Istanbul

The Turkish Straits System (TSS) is the only sea route that connects the Black Sea and the Mediterranean Sea. It is a sensitive ecosystem that acts as a biological corridor made of the inner Sea of Marmara and of the narrow straits of Istanbul and Canakkale. It is also of high economic and touristic importance. Problems in the TSS include: occasional collisions, oil spills, ship waste and illegal discharge, air and sea pollution, etc., all of which are detrimental to the environment, the health of inhabitants, and local and global economy.

The topic of the workshop held by IU was “*Blue Growth and Sea Transportation in Turkish Straits System*”. The workshop aimed at answering the triggering question: “*What Responsible Research and Innovation actions are needed to make maritime transport sustainable in TSS?*”

Table 13 shows the roadmap of actions suggested during this workshop.

WHY - overall objectives for making a roadmap and a common vision									
TO IMPROVE LEGISLATION, EDUCATION TO DISSEMINATE USAGE OF NEW TECHNOLOGY TO PROTECT MARINE ECOSYSTEM AND PREVENT MARINE POLLUTION									
WHO Stakeholder target group(s) Choose from : Citizens/CSOs/NGOs (C), Business/Industry (B), Researchers & Academia (R), Policymakers & implementers (P) Other (Please specify)	WHAT Action	WHEN How long will it take to complete the action? short (now-1 year), medium (2-5 years), long term (over 5 years)	OVERALL GOAL: Which societal challenge will the action contribute to? Choose from:						
			Health, democratic change and well-being	Food security, agriculture, marine and maritime and inland water research, bioeconomy.	Secure, clean and efficient energy	Smart, green and integrated transport	Climate action, environment, resource efficiency, and raw materials	Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies	Secure societies
PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT									
C, R	Integration of the blue growth into the education system	ST				x			
C, R	Education bodies together with NGOs and maritime institutions should run programs to increase maritime culture, particularly to younger generation	ST				x			
R	Economic value of TSS should be determined	ST		x			x		
R	Impacts of maritime activities and ship based noise on migration patterns of marine life should be investigated and counter measures should be taken	ST		x		x	x		
SCIENCE EDUCATION									
C, R	Integration of the blue growth into the education system	ST				x			
R, B	New technology such as drones and AUVs should be utilized in controlling emission levels and ballast water discharges	ST, LT				x			
R, P	Clean energy in marine transportation should be initiated and tested in pilot zones and considering infrastructure needs regarding association with land cargo transport.	ST, LT				x			
P	Technological capacity of shipyards should be increased through extending new technology applications	ST, LT			x	x			
R	Protection of the existing marine ecosystem	ST		x			x		
R	Economic value of TSS should be determined	ST		x			x		
OPEN ACCESS									
R	Protection of the existing marine ecosystem	ST		x			x		
GENDER EQUALITY									
ETHICS									
P	Regulation of substandard ships including mandatory insurance with Turkish P&I	ST							
P	Increase control of disposal ballast water in Turkish Straits System (TSS)	ST							
GOVERNANCE									
P	Integration of maritime and investment policies	ST				x			
P	Regulation of substandard ships including mandatory insurance with Turkish P&I	ST				x			
P	Increase control of disposal ballast water in	ST				x			

	Turkish Straits System (TSS)								
C, R, P	Improvement of vocational training and recruitment of trained personnel to maritime sector	ST				x			
R, P	Clean energy in marine transportation should be initiated and tested in pilot zones and considering infrastructure needs regarding association with land cargo transport	ST, LT				x			
P	Technological capacity of shipyards should be increased through extending new technology applications.	ST, LT			x	x			

Table 13 Final roadmap produced by the participants of the workshop in Istanbul, Turkey

The RRI dimension that scored the biggest number of actions was *Governance*. The chief message was the importance of maritime transportation sustainability that could be achieved by improving legislation, and by increasing education through environmental awareness and vocational training of policymakers and implementers. The main target group was policymakers, who need to reinforce policies and adopt coherent legislative frameworks of health of ecosystem, pollution prevention and sustainability of maritime transportation in TSS. The importance of *Science Education* for all stakeholder groups transpired as well. Participants also underlined the declaration of TSS as a special region in Turkey, and the need for new regulations to define economic value of the TSS.

5.3.3 Renewable Energy (Wave, Wind, Tidal)

5.3.3.1 Description

The energy consumption in the last decades has been characterised by an intense growth that has accelerated in the last decade, owing to the industrialisation of developing countries and the high economic growth rate of emerging countries such as India and China.

Our seas and oceans offer a vast renewable energy resource. The marine environment is an enormous pool of energy, which according to the European Commission, globally exceeds the present and projected future energy needs. The European Union wants to fulfil its commitment to reduce greenhouse gases by up to 80-95% by 2050. It is expected that the market of offshore wind energy could reach the value of 80,000 million euros by 2020, and the wave and tidal energy market could increase up to 535 billion euros between 2010 and 2050.

Offshore wind energy uses higher wind speeds, which are available offshore, in comparison with land. As a result, offshore wind power's contribution in terms of electricity supplied is relatively high (increased productivity of more than 40% compared to onshore wind turbines). The vast majority (ca. 91%) of the world's offshore wind-energy is produced in Europe, mainly in the Baltic, Irish and North Seas and in the English Channel. The very first offshore wind farm (Vindeby) was installed in Denmark in 1991.

However, offshore installations present some disadvantages, such as high installation costs, difficult access, and harsh conditions for the units. Offshore wind turbines are exposed to high humidity, salt water and salt water spray which have adverse impact on service life, cause corrosion and oxidation, resulting in increased maintenance and repair costs and in general make every aspect of installation and operation much more difficult, time-consuming, more dangerous and far more expensive than sites on land. High waves and storms may damage installations while sea currents may play a role in eroding the foundations. Ship routes may have to be changed as well in order to minimize the collision threat.

5.3.3.2 Results of the workshop in Ireland (the Atlantic Sea) held by SmartBay Ireland, Galway

Ireland is obliged under EU Directive 2014/89/EU to establish a framework for marine spatial planning. Recently the Irish government signalled an intent to diversify the mix of renewable energy technologies to include offshore wind and has unveiled plans to hold its first renewable electricity auction under a new Renewable Electricity Support Scheme (RESS) in 2019. The new RESS will be the first step for Ireland in delivering its contribution towards the EU's 2030 targets.

The Marine Spatial Planning process has been established to support government organisations and local communities to help sustainably manage Ireland’s marine resources and provide long term investment predictability for development and activities in the maritime area. The process complements existing measures such as licensing and day-to-day management. It focuses on a specific area, considers economic, environmental and social issues, encompasses all sectors, and is forward looking with a clearly set out vision, objectives and policies.

The topic of the workshop was “What is Marine Spatial Planning (MSP) and how can it be used to help inform decisions about the sustainable utilisation of Ireland’s marine resources.” The workshop aimed at answering the triggering question: “What Responsible Research and Innovation actions are needed to make informed decisions on the identification of zones for the development of marine renewable energy devices?”

Table 14 shows the roadmap of actions suggested during this workshop.

WHY - overall objectives for making a roadmap and a common vision									
WHO Stakeholder target group(s) Choose from : Citizens/CSOs/NGOs (C), Business/Industry (B), Researchers & Academia (R), Policymakers & implementers (P) Other (Please specify)	WHAT Action	WHEN How long will it take to complete the action? short (now-1 year), medium (2-5 years), long term (over 5 years)	OVERALL GOAL: Which societal challenge will the action contribute to? Choose from:						
			Health, democratic change and well-being	Food security, agriculture, marine and maritime and inland water research, bioeconomy	Secure, clean and efficient energy	Smart, green and integrated transport	Climate action, environment, resource efficiency, and raw materials	Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies	Secure societies
PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT									
C, B, R, P	Provide opportunities for stakeholders to provide feedback	MT		x	x	x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P	Optimise reach to include smaller communities and public/ willing messengers and trusted voices (e.g. fedia) format and structure of meeting/layout and set up/ engaging silent voices/local feedback social media	MT		x	x	x	x	x	x
R, P	Define the processes and procedures after initial engagement	MT		x	x	x	x	x	x
C, R, P	Structured communications strategy and outreach activities including planning frameworks, process flows and Service Level agreements	ST		x	x	x		x	
C, B, R, P	Develop community representatives	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
C, P	Local information centres	MT		x	x	x	x	x	
B,R, P	Increased awareness of MSP, ensure all coastal communities have an appreciation of MSP and the implications for their areas	MT					x		
B, R, P	Clarify the benefits and disadvantages	MT			x		x	x	
C, B, R, P	To engage all stakeholders to make good decisions	ST		x	x		x	x	x
C, B, R, P	Need to take into consideration and understand the various views at the local level	ST	x					x	
C, B, R, P	To involve all the different sectors	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	x

SCIENCE EDUCATION									
C, B, R, P	Utilise MSP to realise opportunity for sustainability	LT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P	To develop a common understanding of what the MSP process will result in	ST	x	x	x	x	x		x
B, R, P	To insure inclusive application of social-ecological systems, ecosystem-based approaches to MSP development	MT	x	x			x		x
B, R, P	To generate maps or other interactive support to inform policymakers and stakeholders about biodiversity	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
R, P	To generate up-to-date maps and identify areas requiring further focused research	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
OPEN ACCESS									
C, B, R, P	Use of different communications platforms/technologies to communicate with stakeholders and make data accessible	ST		x	x	x	x	x	x
R, P	To integrate various marine spatial datasets	MT		x	x	x			
GENDER EQUALITY									
ETHICS									
C, R, B, P	Cultural diversity in coastal communities	MT		x	x	x	x	x	x
C, R, B, P	Open inclusive and transparent MSP through the promotion of equality of operating for involvement for all sectors	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
GOVERNANCE									
P	Define the processes and procedures after initial engagement	ST		x			x	x	x
P	Build a culture of trust around MSP. Opportunity to advance a cultural shift in how processes such as MSP are perceived	MT		x	x	x	x	x	x
C, R, P	Build capacity	LT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
B, R, P	Investment in research capital infrastructure	LT		x	x	x	x	x	x
B, R, P	Using MSP to inform understanding and decisions for zonation (non-exclusive)	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
P	Integrated planning	MT					x		
P	To develop an acceptable zonification process	MT			x	x			
P	To harmonise the dumping at sea foreshore licencing and planning processes	MT			x	x		x	
B, R, P	To consider the environmental impact that the devices will cause	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
P	To be effective MSP must not focus on the creation of zones	LT		x			x		

Table 14 Final roadmap produced by the participants of the workshop in Galway, Ireland

The results of the workshop confirmed the effectiveness of using the RRI dimensions for stimulating discussion and dialogue between stakeholder groups.

Two of the key questions examined by participants throughout the workshop were comprehensively addressed generating numerous actions. Bridging the gap in awareness around MSP in the context of a fixed timeline for implementations stimulated multiple actions attributed across multi-stakeholder groups. Increasing awareness of MSP to all stakeholders especially coastal communities, enabling them to make informed decisions and contribute to the process by making information accessible in a language they understand and provide the opportunity for feedback emerged as key actions

across all stakeholder groups. Achieving this will be a challenge, but the opportunity exists that by firmly committing to the process the second question addressed by the workshop could be achieved in tandem.

When examining how the MSP process can be utilised to realise the opportunity for sustainability - in a social, economic and environmental context, the participants concluded that through developing a culture of trust around MSP and how the process is perceived, that it could be leveraged and extended to other policy development processes in Ireland. This method, if successful, would serve to facilitate capacity building through a culture of trust amongst all stakeholders as the process progressed with the establishment of community advocates within local information centres resulting in an investment and sense of responsibility amongst all social actors.

The remaining two questions “How can the interaction between land and Marine Spatial Planning evolve? (Responsibility and roles/local, national scales)” and “Is zonation the way forward for MSP? (Value of environment/ecosystems services/empowerment/trade-offs/new and emerging sectors)” were partially addressed with actions attributed to them but they lacked the sense of cohesiveness which can be seen with the solution focused actions above.

This presents a clear picture of where the challenges are for the development and implementation of MSP generally and for offshore wind in particular. Terrestrial planning in Ireland has traditionally relied on a Zoning Model, with residential, industrial and agricultural zoned lands having clear boundaries. This model is not applicable in the marine environment as boundaries are only effective for a proportion of activities. In the case of renewable energy planning for onshore wind, developments have experienced some issues with planning and if the offshore industry is to progress to meet the ever-increasing energy demands, a solution which is acceptable to all must be a crucial focus in the development of the National Marine Spatial Plan for Ireland.

In conclusion the workshop and the actions originating from it will be considered by the Department of Housing, Planning and Local Governments public consultation process currently underway as it builds towards Marine Spatial Plan for Ireland.

5.3.3.3 Results of the workshop in Italy (the Mediterranean Sea) held by APRE, Rome

In the ocean energy sector, Italy has made great steps forward in both research and device implementation, and it has by now acquired a prominent position among the international insiders. However, targeted policy interventions and investment are needed, in order to fully disclose the potential offered by the ocean energy sector in terms of economic growth, high-skilled job creation and strategic positioning of the Italian industry in the competitive global market.

Indeed, Italy has great potential for offshore wind energy. By considering only a percentage of used area equal to 4% of that available (i.e. about 2,000 km²), the country could reach an installable power of about 13 GW, which is the current offshore wind power installed in the EU. However, the deep-sea condition of the Mediterranean sea, along with a missing mature technology, can partially explain the lack of wind farms in the Med sea. The excessive bureaucracy and a missing legislative and regulatory framework is a further barrier. Therefore the floating offshore farms are a unique opportunity for a growth of the Italian system, both from an environmental point of view, through a sustainable strategy of marine installations, and from an economic and employment point of view, through an investment and appropriate incentives.

Sustaining the deployment of ocean energy would meet the recommendations and directives by the European Union, which established a common framework for Member States to promote the use of energy from renewable sources (EU 2009/28/CE Directive), as well as a framework for the implementation of maritime spatial planning and integrated coastal management by Member States, aimed at promoting the sustainable growth of maritime economies, the sustainable development of marine areas and the sustainable use of marine resources (Directive 2014/89/EU).

The Italian increasing interest in the exploitation of wave and tidal technology to produce clean and renewable energy can be recognized both in government intervention (e.g. high incentives were set for ocean renewables in the Italian [Renewable Energy Action Plan](#)) and in the research and development activities carried out by public and private players. The main actors involved in R&D in this field are universities, spin-offs, SMEs and large enterprises. Thanks to their efforts, Italy has been at the forefront of research in developing and testing prototypal and pre-commercial devices for ocean energy conversion.

The topic of the workshop was “Renewable Energies that impact on coastal environment and development: what are the challenges in to Italy?” The workshop aimed at answering the triggering question: “What Responsible Research and Innovation actions are needed to make renewable energies applicable and replicable in the coastal environment?”

Table 15 shows the roadmap of actions suggested during this workshop.

WHY - overall objectives for making a roadmap and a common vision		TO IMPROVE LEGISLATION, EDUCATION TO DISSEMINATE USAGE OF NEW TECHNOLOGY TO PROTECT MARINE ECOSYSTEM AND PREVENT MARINE POLLUTION							
WHO Stakeholder target group(s) Choose from : Citizens/CSOs/NGOs (C), Business/Industry (B), Researchers & Academia (R), Policymakers & implementers (P) Other (Please specify)	WHAT Action	WHEN How long will it take to complete the action? short (now-1 year), medium (2-5 years), long term (over 5 years)	OVERALL GOAL: Which societal challenge will the action contribute to? Choose from:						
			Health, democratic change and well-being	Food security, agriculture, marine and maritime and inland water research, bioeconomy.	Secure, clean and efficient energy	Smart, green and integrated transport	Climate action, environment, resource efficiency, and raw materials	Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies	Secure societies
PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT									
C, B, R, P	ocean energy: invest on research projects targeting the cultural framework of target communities	MT/LT	x		x		x		
C, B, R, P	ocean energy: project creation in multi-criteria modality, taking into account environmental problems	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
C, R, P	offshore wind: clear and accessible public communication on offshore technologies	MT/LT	x	x	x	x	x	x	
C, B, R, P	offshore wind: developing sustainable plants	LT	x		x		x		
C, B, P	geothermal energy: study and scientific communication, representative of high enthalpy of non-conventional coastal areas and of district heating	MT		x	x		x		
B, R, P	geothermal energy: defining pilot areas for above-mentioned actions	MT		x	x		x		
SCIENCE EDUCATION									
C, B, R, P	ocean energy: invest on research projects targeting the cultural framework of target communities	MT/LT	x		x		x		
C, B, R, P	ocean energy: project creation in multi-criteria modality, taking into account environmental problems	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
C, R, P	offshore wind: clear and accessible public communication on offshore technologies	MT/LT	x	x	x	x	x	x	
C, B, R, P	offshore wind: developing sustainable plants	LT	x		x		x		
P	geothermal energy: action towards the legislator	MT/LT		x	x				
C, B, R, P	geothermal energy: study and scientific communication, representative of high enthalpy of non-conventional coastal areas and of district heating	MT		x	x		x		
B, R, P	geothermal energy: defining pilot areas for above-mentioned actions	MT		x	x		x		
OPEN ACCESS									
B, R, P	ocean energy: joint industry-academia research project	MT/LT			x		x		
C, B, R, P	ocean energy: project creation in multi-criteria modality, taking into account environmental problems	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x

C, R, P	offshore wind: clear and accessible public communication on offshore technologies	MT/LT	x	x	x	x	x	x	
C, B, R, P	offshore wind: developing sustainable plants	LT	x		x		x		
GENDER EQUALITY									
C, B, R, P	ocean energy: invest on research projects targeting the cultural framework of target communities	MT/LT	x		x		x		
C, B, R, P	ocean energy: project creation in multi-criteria modality, taking into account environmental problems	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
ETHICS									
C, B, R, P	ocean energy: invest on research projects targeting the cultural framework of target communities	MT/LT	x		x		x		
C, R, P	offshore wind: clear and accessible public communication on offshore technologies	MT/LT	x	x	x	x	x	x	
C, R, P	geothermal energy: study and scientific communication, representative of high enthalpy of non-conventional coastal areas and of district heating	MT		x	x		x		
C, B, P	geothermal energy: creating value within territories	MT/LT	x	x	x				
GOVERNANCE									
B, R, P	ocean energy: joint industry-academia research project	MT/LT			x				
C, B, R, P	ocean energy: project creation in multi-criteria modality, taking into account environmental problems	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P	offshore wind: developing sustainable plants	LT	x		x		x		
B, R, P	offshore wind: predispose a technical regulation framework able to satisfy the needs of the off-shore wind sector in terms of project creation.	MT/LT		x	x		x		
P	geothermal energy: action towards the legislator	MT/LT		x	x				
C, B, P	geothermal energy: study and scientific communication, representative of high enthalpy of non-conventional coastal areas and of district heating	MT		x	x		x		
C, B, P	geothermal energy: creating value within territories	MT/LT	x	x	x				
B, R, P	geothermal energy: defining pilot areas for above-mentioned actions	MT		x	x		x		

Table 15 Final roadmap produced by the participants of the APRE workshop in Rome, Italy

It appeared from the discussion how important the Italian potential is in this sector, and how existing drawback at the industrial take-up level are attributable to legal framework conditions, and low coordination amongst stakeholders. Potential solutions are available, but there is a need now to leverage on the vitality and creativity of a well-established community of actors from the public and the private sectors, through a set of policies able to support the up-scaling of a variety of connected enterprises, sustaining product diversification and opening access to international visibility.

Therefore, in order to embrace a full energy transition, and all that is connected to it in terms of economic growth, a coordinated and synergic involvement of all actors is required: policymakers are called to foster the growth of clean technologies through adequate policy interventions and law adaptation; the scientific and technological research system is called to cooperate with industries for the sustainable deployment of innovative and eco-sustainable solutions; and industrial and economic stakeholders are encouraged to invest in the sector. As for citizens, it is of utmost importance that all the policy, research and investment explore and take into account the specific cultural framework and social needs of the

communities where interventions are envisaged, involving communities into dialogue and building of a proper awareness of actual environmental opportunities or threats. This would avoid unnecessary worries of the communities regarding interventions.

The RRI dimensions that resulted to be the most important for the actions presented are therefore those connected to the capacity of stakeholders to understand each other and set up realistic plans in order to make the energy transition happen. These RRI dimensions are *Public Engagement*; *Science Education*; and *Governance*.

5.3.3.4 Results of the workshop in Poland (the Baltic Sea) held by IOPAN, Sopot

In Sopot in Poland, the workshop by IOPAN focused on whether the energy from the sea is a viable solution the country, where fossil fuels, mainly coal, are still a number one source of Polish energy. Offshore wind energy issue is not a popular topic in the news. It is mostly discussed in branch portals and in local media. This is also not a popular topic for people to talk about. This issue is rather of a marginal importance on every level of societal engagement. This may also result from the fact that this is an energy source niche in Poland. The mainstream energy production involves coal burning and different developments/innovations in this area, thus any renewable energy sources are treated as rather marginal.

The topic of the workshop was “Energy from the sea: future or a road to nowhere?” The workshop aimed at answering the triggering question: “How can marine renewable energy be regulated to facilitate sustainable development of coastal areas, including the principles of the blue growth?”

Table 16 shows the roadmap of actions suggested during this workshop.

WHY - overall objectives for making a roadmap and a common vision		TO ENSURE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF RENEWABLE ENERGY – FOCUS GROUP (March 5 th and 12 th , 2018)									
WHO Stakeholder target group(s) Choose from : Citizens/CSOs/NGOs (C), Business/Industry (B), Researchers & Academia (R), Policymakers & implementers (P) Other (Please specify)	WHAT Action	WHEN How long will it take to complete the action? short (now-1 year), medium (2-5 years), long term (over 5 years)	OVERALL GOAL: Which societal challenge will the action contribute to? Choose from:							Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies	Secure societies
			Health, democratic change and well-being	Food security, agriculture, marine and maritime and inland water research, bioeconomy.	Secure, clean and efficient energy	Smart, green and integrated transport	Climate action, environment, resource efficiency, and raw materials	Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies	Secure societies		
PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT											
C	Development of societal awareness about water and advantages of using renewable energy sources in general and offshore wind farms in particular	LT			x				x	x	
SCIENCE EDUCATION											
C	Educate	MT		x		x					
B, R, P	Implement program of innovative research in relation to the effectiveness of the constructions of towers and generators	LT			x			x			
B, R, P	Establish law which is favourable for such ecological investments	LT	x	x	x					x	
C	Development of societal awareness about water and advantages of using renewable energy sources in general and offshore wind farms in particular	LT			x				x	x	
B, R	Opening university faculties, strongly connected with wind farms	MT							x		

OPEN ACCESS									
C	Educate	MT		x		x			
B, R, P	Implement program of innovative research in relation to the effectiveness of the constructions of towers and generators	LT			x		x		
B, R	Plan well maintenance actions in the phase of farm operating	LT		x		x	x		
C, R, P	Carry out studies on potential impact of the investment	LT		x			x		
C	Development of societal awareness about water and advantages of using renewable energy sources in general and offshore wind farms in particular	LT			x			x	x
B, R	Opening university faculties, strongly connected with wind farms	MT						x	
GENDER EQUALITY									
B, R	Plan well maintenance actions in the phase of farm operating	LT		x		x	x		
ETHICS									
B, R	Plan well maintenance actions in the phase of farm operating	LT		x		x	x		
C, B, P	Planning what to do with buildings/installations, which have been created while building wind farms	LT				x			
C	Development of societal awareness about water and advantages of using renewable energy sources in general and offshore wind farms in particular	LT			x			x	x
GOVERNANCE									
C	Educate	MT		x		x			
B, R	Plan well maintenance actions in the phase of farm operating	LT		x		x	x		
C, B, P	Planning what to do with buildings/installations, which have been created while building wind farms	LT				x			
C	Development of societal awareness about water and advantages of using renewable energy sources in general and offshore wind farms in particular	LT			x			x	x

Table 16 Final roadmap produced by the participants of the workshop in Sopot, Poland

The RRI dimension that scored the biggest number of actions was *Science Education* whereas the smallest number of actions was related to *Gender Equality*. This may be due to several factors such as the nature of the hot topic and the composition of the group.

The chief message was the importance of *Science Education* for all stakeholder groups: for the general public to make informed responsible choices of types of energy sources to use, for business and industry professionals to produce socially and environmentally acceptable solutions and services, for scientists to scale up research to bring responses to sustainable development of offshore wind farms and finally for policymakers to reinforce policies and adopt coherent legislative frameworks of economic competitiveness and sustainability of offshore wind energy.

5.3.3.5 Results of the workshop in Romania (the Black Sea) held by NIRD GeoEcoMar, Bucharest

Renewable energy represents a political priority and an important component of sustainable development. The business sector considers that in order to achieve a permanent development, we need to produce more energy and an important percent of this energy has to be renewable. Romanian policymakers and implementers have established, through the

strategy for energy, a series of targets. One of them is that by 2020, Romania must have 38% green energy in the share of electricity from renewable sources in domestic consumption.

The topic of the workshop was “Black Sea - an inexhaustible source of energy? How to tip the balance towards renewable energy?” The workshop aimed at answering the triggering question: “What Responsible Research and Innovation actions are needed to develop and make the marine renewable energy sector (wind, waves, biomass, etc.) sustainable?”

Table 17 shows the roadmap of actions suggested during this workshop.

WHY - overall objectives for making a roadmap and a common vision									
WHO Stakeholder target group(s) Choose from : Citizens/CSOs/NGOs (C), Business/Industry (B), Researchers & Academia (R), Policymakers & implementers (P) Other (Please specify)	WHAT Action	WHEN How long will it take to complete the action? short (now-1 year), medium (2-5 years), long term (over 5 years)	OVERALL GOAL: Which societal challenge will the action contribute to? Choose from:						
			Health, democratic change and well-being	Food security, agriculture, marine and maritime and inland water research, bioeconomy	Secure, clean and efficient energy	Smart, green and integrated transport	Climate action, environment, resource efficiency, and raw materials	Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies	Secure societies
PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT									
C, B, R, P	Producing sustainable energy for local consumers	LT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P	Renewable energy - a means of promoting sustainable development	LT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P	Building a coastal protection system that can harness the wave energy	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P	The creation of an coordinating and cooperation organism inside energy sector	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P	The development of new programs in applicable research in the regenerative resources domain	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P	New specialized study opportunities for people in the RES field	ST		x				x	x
C, B, R, P	Pilot projects to capitalize the use of marine biomass in energy generation	ST / MT / LT		x	x		x	x	
B, R, P	Developing a new national program to help finance new research projects in developing the renewable energy sector	ST / MT			x	x		x	x
B, P	Specific action oriented regulations in the renewable energy field	ST			x	x	x	x	
B, R, P	The study of renewable energy on the Black Sea costal area	ST		x		x	x	x	
B, P	Improving the legislative framework to encourage the capitalization process of renewable energy	ST / MT / LT				x	x	x	x
B, R, P	Better harmonization between energy generation and transport/storage	ST / MT / LT			x	x	x	x	

C, B, R, P	New communication networks for the involved stakeholders	ST						x	x
B, P	New stable framework for predictable financing the energy sector	ST / MT / LT			x			x	x
C, B, R	The socio-economic empowerment of investors in the renewable energy sector	LT							x
C, R, P	Rising the public awareness regarding the benefits of renewable energy	ST / MT / LT							x
SCIENCE EDUCATION									
C, B, R, P	Producing sustainable energy for local consumers	LT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P	Renewable energy - a means of promoting sustainable development	LT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P	Building a coastal protection system that can harness the wave energy	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P	The creation of an coordinating and cooperation organism inside energy sector	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P	The development of new programs in applicable research in the regenerative resources domain	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P	New specialized study opportunities for people in the RES field	ST		x				x	x
C, B, R, P	Pilot projects to capitalize the use of marine biomass in energy generation	ST / MT / LT		x	x		x	x	
B, R, P	The study of renewable energy on the Black Sea costal area	ST		x		x	x	x	
B, P	Improving the legislative framework to encourage the capitalization process of renewable energy	ST / MT / LT				x	x	x	x
C, R	The study of the different potential of the local renewable energy resources	ST		x	x		x		
C, B, R, P	New communication networks for the involved stakeholders	ST						x	x
B, P	New stable framework for predictable financing the energy sector	ST / MT / LT			x			x	x
C, B, R	The socio-economic empowerment of investors in the renewable energy sector	LT							x
C, R, P	Rising the public awareness regarding the benefits of renewable energy	ST / MT / LT							x
OPEN ACCESS									
C, B, R, P	Producing sustainable energy for local consumers	LT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P	Renewable energy - a means of promoting sustainable development	LT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P	Building a coastal protection system that can harness the wave energy	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P	The creation of a coordinating and cooperation organism inside energy sector	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P	The development of new programs in applicable research in the regenerative	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	x

	resources domain								
C, B, R, P	New specialized study opportunities for people in the RES field	ST		x				x	x
C, B, R, P	Pilot projects to capitalize the use of marine biomass in energy generation	ST / MT / LT		x	x		x	x	
B, R, P	Developing a new national program to help finance new research projects in developing the renewable energy sector	ST / MT			x	x		x	x
B, P	Specific action oriented regulations in the renewable energy field	ST			x	x	x	x	
B, R, P	The study of renewable energy on the Black Sea coastal area	ST		x		x	x	x	
B, P	Improving the legislative framework to encourage the capitalization process of renewable energy	ST / MT / LT				x	x	x	x
B, R, P	Better harmonization between energy generation and transport/storage	ST / MT / LT			x	x	x	x	
C, R	The study of the different potential of the local renewable energy resources	ST		x	x		x		
C, B, R, P	New communication networks for the involved stakeholders	ST						x	x
B, P	New stable framework for predictable financing the energy sector	ST / MT / LT			x			x	x
C, B, R	The socio-economic empowerment of investors in the renewable energy sector	LT							x
C, R, P	Rising the public awareness regarding the benefits of renewable energy	ST / MT / LT							x
GENDER EQUALITY									
C, B, R, P	Producing sustainable energy for local consumers	LT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P	Renewable energy - a means of promoting sustainable development	LT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P	Building a coastal protection system that can harness the wave energy	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P	The creation of a coordinating and cooperation organism inside energy sector	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P	The development of new programs in applicable research in the regenerative resources domain	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P	New specialized study opportunities for people in the RES field	ST		x				x	x
C, B, R, P	Pilot projects to capitalize the use of marine biomass in energy generation	ST / MT / LT		x	x		x	x	
C, B, R	The socio-economic empowerment of investors in the renewable energy sector	LT							x
C, R, P	Rising the public awareness regarding the benefits of renewable energy	ST / MT / LT							x
ETHICS									
C, B, R, P	Producing sustainable energy for local consumers	LT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x

C, B, R, P	Renewable energy - a means of promoting sustainable development	LT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P	Building a coastal protection system that can harness the wave energy	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P	The creation of a coordinating and cooperation organism inside energy sector	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P	The development of new programs in applicable research in the regenerative resources domain	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P	New specialized study opportunities for people in the RES field	ST		x				x	x
C, B, R, P	Pilot projects to capitalize the use of marine biomass in energy generation	ST / MT / LT		x	x		x	x	
B, R, P	Developing a new national program to help finance new research projects in developing the renewable energy sector	ST / MT			x	x		x	x
B, P	Specific action oriented regulations in the renewable energy field	ST			x	x	x	x	
B, R, P	The study of renewable energy on the Black Sea costal area	ST		x		x	x	x	
C, B, R	The socio-economic empowerment of investors in the renewable energy sector	LT							x
C, R, P	Rising the public awareness regarding the benefits of renewable energy	ST / MT / LT							x
GOVERNANCE									
C, B, R, P	Producing sustainable energy for local consumers	LT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P	Renewable energy - a means of promoting sustainable development	LT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P	Building a coastal protection system that can harness the wave energy	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P	The creation of a coordinating and cooperation organism inside energy sector	MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P	The development of new programs in applicable research in the regenerative resources domain	ST	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
C, B, R, P	Pilot projects to capitalize the use of marine biomass in energy generation	ST / MT / LT		x	x		x	x	
B, R, P	Developing a new national program to help finance new research projects in developing the renewable energy sector	ST / MT			x	x		x	x
B, P	Specific action oriented regulations in the renewable energy field	ST			x	x	x	x	
B, P	Improving the legislative framework to encourage the capitalization process of renewable energy	ST / MT / LT				x	x	x	x
B, R, P	Better harmonization between energy generation and transport/storage	ST / MT / LT			x	x	x	x	

B, P	New stable framework for predictable financing the energy sector	ST / MT / LT			x			x	x
C, R, P	Rising the public awareness regarding the benefits of renewable energy	ST / MT / LT							x

Table 17 Final roadmap produced by the participants of the workshop in Bucharest, Romania

The RRI dimension that scored the biggest number of actions was *Open Access*. This may be due to the fact that in Romania the access to data is still difficult in some situations and there is a lot of space for improvement.

The RRI principles can ensure that the needs and expectations of the society are considered while developing the renewable energy sector to guarantee our marine natural heritage to the next generations.

In order to better protect our planet we need to bridge the gap between policymakers, local stakeholders, scientists and the general public by implementing sustainable development initiatives based on the outcomes of their joint efforts.

The MARINA Project can provide the right platform for people to understand that they have to overcome the animosities from the past, to identify the real problems that our environment is facing due to irresponsible use of the natural resources and to join their efforts by starting to work together.

5.3.3.6 Results of the workshop in Spain (the Atlantic Sea) held by CIC NanoGUNE, San Sebastián

Since the 1980s, the strategic energy plan of the Basque government has been based on the principles of energy efficiency, energy diversification through natural gas, and harnessing of renewable energy (mini-hydraulic, solar, wind and biomass). The strategic energy plan for 2020 of the Basque Government plan is linked to the action against climate change, towards the environmental protection, and the optimisation of the energy consumption of transport, households and industry.

The workshop organised by CIC NanoGUNE addressed offshore wind energy for the future and whether the technology is mature enough. The topic of the workshop was “*Offshore wind energy: Our future? How?*” The workshop aimed at answering the triggering question: “*What Responsible Research and Innovation actions are needed to make marine renewable energy sustainable?*”

The SDD method was used and the participants assembled or classified their ideas of actions jointly in 9 clusters (Figure 28).

Figure 28 Clusters assembled by the participants of the local MML workshop in Donostia-San Sebastián, Spain

The final influence map (Figure 29) developed in the next step indicates a strong need for *Bringing closer to society the results from research and innovation about offshore wind energy through the media* (A8, C5, V5, L3), carrying out *Environmental surveillance of the devices installed in the sea* (A1, C1, V2, L3), *Guaranteeing the environmental standards to protect the fishery, minimising the environmental impact* (A6, C1, V3, L3), achieving the *Visibility of the capabilities of the companies and the sector needs* (A16, C9, V3, L3), defining *Decision-making tools to carry out a Marine Spatial Planning* (A18, C1, V3, L3), and finally, *Developing remote and autonomous monitoring technologies for environmental purposes* (A19, C1, V5, L3). All these actions have to be executed simultaneously for their implementation to be successful and also for the implementation of the next level of ideas/actions (L2, L3) to be successful.

Figure 29 Final influence map produced by the participants of the local MML workshop in Donostia-San Sebastián, Spain

In spite of the advances, today's offshore wind energy still depends upon the government policies to survive.

The regulations of offshore wind energy need to develop further for the business to become really competitive. The fronts of work in research and innovation could include (i) *environmental sustainability*, (ii) *fixation of structures in the sea*, (iii) *optimisation of the costs of operation and maintenance*, (iv) *new wind energy harvesting devices*, (v) *socialisation of science and technology*, (vi) *multidisciplinary research*, (vii) *management of supply*, (viii) *administrative roadmap*, and (ix) *synergies of the business network* (Figure 28).

Corrective measures on both regulations and offshore wind farm design would decrease the costs above 35%. The current regulation applicable to the design of offshore wind farm structures is inherited from the oil & gas sector (A13, V3, C3, L2). However, the operation requirements of offshore wind are completely different from those of oil & gas extraction. Moreover, the consequences, in case of failure or accident, are also very different, from the viewpoint of environment (spills) and personnel (floating wind turbines are not manned whereas oil & gas platforms are). As a result, current structures are oversized, and hence, expensive. Furthermore, there are no standardised designs for floating platforms and fixation technologies (A2, V0, C2) incrementing the price even further.

With wind turbines growing bigger and bigger (8 MW for offshore against a 2-3 MW inland) and being installed in increasingly deep waters, offshore wind farms demand stronger and bigger jacket structures (lattice towers, which are anchored to the seabed) (A2, C2, V0) or exotic floating systems (A13, V3, C3, L2). However the larger infrastructures in the sea, the higher the prices become and also the concomitant impacts and risks for the marine fauna and flora and the activities carried out in the shared maritime space scale-up significantly.

In addition to the costs of offshore wind energy technology and supply issues, the democratisation/decentralisation of the business is also an important issue. The Basque Country, as a result of its technological and industrial capacity, has several companies developing structures for offshore wind farms, e.g. floating platforms. Unfortunately, one of the main barriers for proving the validity of these solutions is the elevated fabrication costs of a first prototype, which is between 10 and 20 million euros. Basque companies do not have enough financial strength to materialise this first prototype into reality and are making strong efforts to keep progressing. The sector could need innovative public-private financial initiatives to allow the intrusion of smaller companies into the business (A14, C2, V3, L1) and make them competitive.

The governments have to really sit and revise the current energy generation/distribution model based, generally, on large infrastructures, which increase tremendously the energy price and could potentially harm the environment and other economic activities (e.g. fishery), decelerating or even impeding the access to the business of small-medium size companies.

Today, governments have to evaluate the possibility of a paradigm shift towards new energy supply systems, which could be based on self-supply renewable energy devices such as solar panels or vortex bladeless (A4, C4, V3, L1), to be installed, for example, on the roof of houses.

Scientific and technological advancements sustain our societies, are the motor of our economic activity, consume resources, and have long-term impacts on our civilization. Hence, humans have to have real power on the decisions concerning the strategy to be followed and on the related research and innovation activities. Moreover, scientific and technological solutions to current societal challenges require, owing to their complexity, not only of technological and scientific research and innovation *per se*, but also of complementary actions such as new law/policies, environmental studies, economic analysis, and inclusion of the criteria and experience of affected citizens. In this process, public participation (jointly with energy literacy) and discussion and collaboration amongst the different stakeholders to co-construct the strategy and solutions is key. Materialising both public participation and multi-stakeholder engagement necessitates the establishment of a transparent, efficient and effective democratic mechanism, which should tackle from the design of the solution, to the implementation stage and the monitoring and revision phases. A solution could be organising consultation processes which are binding for the governments.

The final aim is to build an energy system that is socially responsible because it ensures affordable energy for all, economically democratically because it is a business in which small-medium companies can have a share, and environmentally sustainable because it is responsible with the environment and the use of the resources.

5.3.4 Marine Changes Caused by Climate

5.3.4.1 Description

Climate change is a global and a very local challenge, forcing state, municipalities, researchers and citizen to join forces. According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) 2014 assessment report³⁰, “Mitigation is a public good; climate change is a case of the “tragedy of the commons””. Climate change is a major cause of degradation and alteration of marine ecosystems, which are already registering its impacts. Changes in ocean temperatures, chemical composition (acidification), wind patterns, sea level rise, melting of the poles, alter habitats severely, affect biological diversity having drastic implications for many species including humans.

5.3.4.2 Results of the workshop in Denmark (the Baltic Sea and the North Sea) held by AAU, Copenhagen

In Copenhagen, the workshop organised by AAU discussed collaboration on mitigating climate change in coastal towns by community driven processes. The Danish coastline measures 7,314 km and is composed of hundreds of islands. They are likely to be most affected by the sea level rise, which will reduce the existence of shallow waters in fjords and inlets, the areas known as the most biologically productive and home to large populations of fish, birds and plants. In Denmark, as in other European countries, many coastal towns suffer under an economic pressure, a decreasing population, a shrinking job market and, consequently, the decline in quality of life. Climate protection is a huge investment, both for private landowners as for municipalities, and is a difficult economic, political and technical task. To secure an effective and sustainable solution, joint forces are needed. This offers a unique opportunity for new collaborations and responsible research innovative processes.

The topic of the workshop was “More value. Collaboration on mitigating climate change in coastal areas by community-driven processes.” The workshop aimed at answering the triggering question: “What Responsible Research and Innovation actions are needed to make climate change mitigation measures sustainable in Denmark?”

Table 18 shows the roadmap of actions suggested during this workshop.

WHY - overall objectives for making a roadmap and a common vision									
WHO	WHAT	WHEN	OVERALL GOAL: Which societal challenge will the action contribute to? Choose from:						
Stakeholder target group(s) Choose from : Citizens/CSOs/NGOs (C), Business/Industry (B), Researchers & Academia (R), Policymakers & implementers (P) Other (Please specify)	Action	How long will it take to complete the action? short (now-1 year), medium (2-5 years), long term (over 5 years)	Health, democratic change and well-being	Food security, agriculture, marine and maritime and inland water research, bioeconomy	Secure, clean and efficient energy	Smart, green and integrated transport	Climate action, environment, resource efficiency, and raw materials	Europe in a changing world - Inclusive, innovative and reflective societies	Secure societies
PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT									
C, R, P	Lift citizens' interests/agendas to a function that can give social value	MT					x	x	
C, R, P	Create awareness of challenges and possible solutions	MT					x	x	
C	Citizens must understand and be able to respond to the challenges they perceive	LT					x	x	

³⁰ <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ars/index.shtml>

C, R, P	Work across disciplines	MT<						x	x
R, P	Develop (and spread) concrete examples that citizens and authorities can base on	MT						x	x
C, P	Ensure better guidance for citizens who would like to embark on a coastal climate solution project	MT<						x	x
C	Strengthen citizens' self-involvement in the political/technical system	MT<							x
P	Create ownership of coastal protection	MT<							x
B	Financing climate protection projects in alternative ways								x
P	Create national interest in ownership of major coastal security projects	MT<							x
P	Create continual demand for solutions with added value and cross-cutting sustainability	MT<							x
R, P	Centralization of interdisciplinary decision-making competence	MT<							x
C, B, P	Develop transparent models for allocation of contributions	MT							x
C, P	Ensure that the broad population can understand the necessity of sustainable climate adaptation solutions	LT							x
C, R, B, P	Ensure long-term climate protection by incorporating the special qualities of the site	MT						x	x
SCIENCE EDUCATION									
C, R, P	Lift citizens' interests/agendas to a function that can give social value	MT						x	x
C, R, P	Create awareness of challenges and possible solutions	MT						x	x
C, P	Ensure better guidance for citizens who would like to embark on a coastal security project	MT<						x	x
C	Strengthen citizens' self-involvement in the political/technical system	MT<							x
C, R, P	GIS-modelling/Insurance model. Housing tax corresponding to the risk the homeowners choose to take when settling in potentially exposed areas	MT<							x
C, R, B, P	Ensure long-term climate protection by incorporating the special qualities of the site	MT						x	x
P	Ensure citizen involvement in mutual cooperation on solutions in a broad aspect	LT							x
OPEN ACCESS									
C	Strengthen citizens' self-involvement in the political/technical system	MT<							x
P	Create ownership of coastal protection	MT<							x
C, R, B, P	Create continual demand for solutions with added value and cross-cutting sustainability	MT<							x
C, R, P	GIS-modelling/Insurance model. Housing tax corresponding to the risk the homeowners	MT<							x

	choose to take when settling in potentially exposed areas									
C, B, P	Develop transparent models for allocation of contributions	MT							x	
GENDER EQUALITY										
C	Strengthen citizens' self-involvement in the political/technical system	MT<							x	
ETHICS										
C	Strengthen citizens' self-involvement in the political/technical system	MT<							x	
C, R, P	GIS-modelling/Insurance model. Housing tax corresponding to the risk the homeowners choose to take when settling in potentially exposed area	MT<							x	
GOVERNANCE										
C, R, B, P	Create a common understanding of the project which may also be historically anchored	MT<							x	
C, B, P	Develop transparent models for allocation of contributions	MT							x	
C	Strengthen citizens' self-involvement in the political/technical system	MT<							x	
P	Legislation that allows for new forms of funding, for example, increased state and regional funding for coastal protection. Citizens should value the coasts									
P	Create national interest in ownership of major coastal security projects									
C, R, B, P	Create continual demand for solutions with added value and cross-cutting sustainability	MT<							x	
R, P	Centralization of interdisciplinary decision-making competence	MT<							x	
C, R,	GIS-modelling/Insurance model. Housing tax corresponding to the risk the homeowners choose to take when settling in potentially exposed areas	MT<							x	
R, P	Develop (and spread) concrete examples that citizens and authorities can base on	MT						x	x	
C, P	Ensure better guidance for citizens who would like to embark on a coastal security project	MT<						x	x	
C, P	Ensure the best possible climate adaptation of the municipalities in relation to storm and sea level increases	LT						x	x	
C, R, P	Ensure long-term climate protection by incorporating the special qualities of the site	MT						x	x	

Table 18 Final roadmap produced by the participant workshop in Copenhagen, Denmark

The RRI dimension that scored the biggest number of actions was *Public Engagement*. The second RRI dimension was *Governance*. This may be due to several factors such as the nature of the hot topic (collaboration between private

landowners and municipalities on coastal climate solutions), the composition of the group and to the fact that the two experts presented two different perspectives on the same topic.

It also confirmed that the monumental need for mitigating coastal areas and towns cannot be solved by traditional collaboration methods, technical knowhow and already existing financial models. Climate change is a game changer. And it calls for new ways of collaborating between landowners and officials/municipalities but also new ways to bridge deep technical knowledge with environmental considerations, and private motives like economy (as they will be forced to pay for the climate solution), life-style preferences and the quality of everyday life.

The difficulty is to perceive a complex challenge as a potential, not as a problem that is difficult to resolve. Mitigation coastal areas have the potential to activate citizens as a resourceful group of action that could lead to a more innovative and including society.

The workshop discussions, the actions developed, and the prioritizing of ideas clearly showed new methods to collaborate. New ways of bridging different kind of knowledge very much depend on the need for the state, regions and local municipalities to raise the awareness of climate change and the need for community driven processes.

Also, the state must take on the role in the changing paradigm on innovative and collaborative processes by developing new knowledge, guidelines and best-practices that can inspire local development projects in terms of added value and inclusion. The chief message was the importance of new governance for all stakeholder groups led by local authorities.

5.3.4.3 Results of the workshop in Ireland (the Atlantic Sea) held by UCC, Cork

Europe's coasts are suffering from increasing coastal erosion and in 2004 the pan-European EUROSION project analysed coastal erosion and identified that about 20,000km of coasts faced serious impacts.

In Cork in Ireland, the workshop organised by UCC addressed challenges of coastal protection in a changing climate. Coastal protection is a difficult and often divisive management issue that currently affects the majority of Ireland's coastal counties. Under climate change projections it is anticipated that Ireland's coastline will be subjected to a range of impacts, including sea level rise and increased storminess. Measures to limit the impacts of recent flooding events on coastal areas are required, but dialogue between all parties is necessary to find options on how best to implement a management response.

The topic of the workshop was "*Challenges of Coastal Protection in a Changing Climate*". The workshop aimed at answering the triggering question: "*What Responsible Research and Innovation actions are needed to make climate change mitigation measures sustainable?*"

The workshop proved to be a useful exercise in determining the contemporary and future challenges for coastal protection with respect to the impacts from climate change. It was confirmed that there is a definite need to revisit the historical approaches to coastal protection and establish a long-term, inclusive and contemporary strategy to deal with this ongoing and divisive societal issue.

The ideas generated during this workshop provide some definite approaches and a way forward to meet the challenges identified:

- To assess the scale of the current and future coastal protection issue, a coherent national monitoring and assessment programme should be established, supported by national government and implemented by local authorities in partnership with research centres. This would provide an initial baseline and in the longer term enable managers to identify and quantify the economic, societal and environmental risks of the impacts of climate change and propose a range of options to minimise these risks.
- In order to raise awareness of the issues associated with coastal protection, the impacts, associated risks and costs need to be conveyed to stakeholders at a local and national level. This will require utilisation of the outcomes of the national monitoring and assessment programme as part of a targeted national awareness raising campaign focused on the current and future challenges of providing coastal protection under a range of climate change scenarios.
- To ensure successful implementation of any coastal protection scheme a range of local stakeholders must be engaged and to achieve this a proactive approach to engagement will be required rather than just the routine town-hall planning meetings. Whilst there remains a need for this type of meeting, the use of social media

campaigns, linked to an overarching national campaign, and in combination with traditional approaches will help to reach a wider audience.

- To place coastal protection in the wider context of coastal management ,it should be one of the key sectors included in a national overarching coastal management plan which should consider the national management requirements based on local management needs. This would take a long-term view and would enable a pro-active approach to coastal protection that would provide central support for schemes assessed using a transparent and consistent process.

5.3.4.4 Results of the workshop in Romania (the Black Sea) held by Mare Nostrum, Constanta

The workshop organised by Mare Nostrum in Constanta, discussed the effects of climate change on the Black Sea and the negative influences on its ecosystem. The most important environmental constraints of the Black Sea are coastal erosion, eutrophication, pollution, decline of biodiversity, loss of living resources, and degradation of landscapes. The Black Sea is one of the most isolated seas from the World Ocean, connected to the oceans with the Mediterranean Sea through the Bosphorus Strait, the Sea of Marmara and the Dardanelle. Due to the fact that Europe’s largest rivers flow into it and it is bordered by six countries, the Black Sea is very vulnerable to pressures from land based human activity. Because of these unique characteristics, the Black Sea is a natural test for understanding oceanographic phenomena in other parts of the World Ocean and an ideal laboratory for studying the effects of climate change. The phenomena that are taking place in this very particular sea constitute a natural warning to other regions of the world and the knowledge gained on this sea may serve to protect other parts of the World Ocean.

The topic of the workshop was “Will the unique character of the Black Sea ecosystem survive climate changes?” The workshop aimed at answering the triggering question: “What Responsible Research and Innovation actions are needed to mitigate climate change in the Black Sea region?”

Table 19 shows the roadmap of actions suggested during this workshop.

WHY - overall objectives for making a roadmap and a common vision		To generate actions to mitigate climate change in the Black Sea region Actions at Economic, Political and Social level								
WHO Stakeholder target group(s) Choose from : Citizens/CSOs/NGOs (C), Business/Industry (B), Researchers & Academia (R), Policymakers & implementers (P) Other (Please specify)	WHAT Action	WHEN How long will it take to complete the action? short (now-1 year), medium (2-5 years), long term (over 5 years)	OVERALL GOAL: Which societal challenge will the action contribute to? Choose from:							Secure societies
			Health, democratic change and well-being	Food security, agriculture, marine and maritime and inland water research, bioeconomy	Secure, clean and efficient energy	Smart, green and integrated transport	Climate action, environment, resource efficiency, and raw materials	Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies		
PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT										
C, R, B, P	Promoting and developing responsible and sustainable tourism in a changing environment	ST/MT	x					x	x	
B, R, P	Sustainable approaches for surface transportation, reducing greenhouse emissions	MT		x			x	x	x	x
C, R, B, P	Waste management (recycling, recovery, monitoring)	ST		x				x		
C, R, B, P	Technology transfer platform from public to private sector	ST/MT						x		

C, R, B, P	Sustainable use and management of natural resources	ST/MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	
C, R, B, P	Refurbishment of existing tourist areas	ST/MT					x		
C, R, B, P	Developing an easy reporting system of field reality to decision makers	MT					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Engaging local people in public consultations and decision – making in local regulations	ST					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Developing methodological norms for enforcement of law	ST/MT					x		
C, R, B, P	Financing renewable energy projects and promoting them	MT/LT			x		x	x	x
C, R, B, P	Restructuring the mechanisms designed to promote best practices in environmental protection	MT					x		
C, R, B, P	Restructuring mechanisms designed to prevent pollution	MT					x		x
C, R, B, P	Restructuring mechanisms designed to monitor and report real situation of Black Sea ecosystems	MT					x		x
C, R, B, P	Restructuring mechanisms designed for applying sanctions	ST/MT					x		
C, R, B, P	Restructuring mechanisms designed to reward good practices	ST/MT					x		
C, R, B, P	Restructuring mechanisms designed to ensure transparency in law-making processes	ST/MT					x		
C, R, P	The formal introduction of marine education within the curriculum for schools	MT/LT					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Development of an educational platform between public and private institutions	ST					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Fostering citizen and private organizations participation through innovative programs such as selective collection or online platforms as Citizen Watch, with possible rewards.	ST/MT					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Communicating about climate change with stakeholders	ST					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Changing unsustainable patterns of consumption and production, in order to reduce the amount of waste	ST/MT					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Applying for green programs as RABLA or CASA VERDE	ST					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Creating a framework for recycling biodegradable waste from household waste	ST/MT					x	x	
SCIENCE EDUCATION									
C, R, B, P	Promoting sustainable fishing methods and techniques through protecting resources and other incentives/compensation	ST/MT		x			x	x	
B	Emissions reductions through upgrade of plants and equipment	MT	x	x	x		x	x	x

C, R, B, P	Water treatment measures to improve ecological value, use of ponds, plants and terraces	MT/LT	x	x			x	x	x
B, R, P	Developing business strategy/plan using the concept of sustainable development	ST					x	x	
B, R, P	Law update and improvement on the exploitation of natural marine resources, in context of sustainable development	ST/MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	
C, B, P	Allocate a higher percentage of GDP on research	MT/LT					x		
B, R, P	Introducing the profession of environmental auditor in COR	ST/MT					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Promoting and developing responsible and sustainable tourism in a changing environment	ST/MT	x				x	x	
B, R, P	Sustainable approaches for surface transportation, reducing greenhouse emissions	MT		x		x	x	x	x
C, R, B, P	Waste management (recycling, recovery, monitoring)	ST		x			x		
C, R, B, P	Technology transfer platform from public to private sector	ST/MT					x		
C, R, B, P	Sustainable use and management of natural resources	ST/MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	
C, R, B, P	Refurbishment of existing tourist areas	ST/MT					x		
C, R, B, P	Developing an easy reporting system of field reality to decision makers	MT					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Engaging local people in public consultations and decision – making in local regulations	ST					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Developing methodological norms for enforcement of law	ST/MT					x		
C, R, B, P	Restructuring the mechanisms designed to promote best practices in environmental protection	MT					x		
C, R, B, P	Restructuring mechanisms designed to prevent pollution	MT					x		x
C, R, B, P	Restructuring mechanisms designed to monitor and report real situation of Black Sea ecosystems	MT					x		x
C, R, B, P	Restructuring mechanisms designed for applying sanctions	ST/MT					x		
C, R, B, P	Restructuring mechanisms designed to reward good practices	ST/MT					x		
C, R, B, P	Restructuring mechanisms designed to ensure transparency in law-making processes	ST/MT					x		
C, R, P	The formal introduction of marine education within the curriculum for schools	MT/LT					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Development of an educational platform between public and private institutions	ST					x	x	

C, R, B, P	Fostering citizen and private organizations participation through innovative programs such as selective collection or online platforms as Citizen Watch, with possible rewards.	ST/MT					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Communicating about climate change with stakeholders	ST					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Changing unsustainable patterns of consumption and production, in order to reduce the amount of waste	ST/MT					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Applying for green programs as RABLA or CASA VERDE	ST					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Creating a framework for recycling biodegradable waste from household waste	ST/MT					x	x	
OPEN ACCESS									
B, P	Analysis and evaluation of business opportunities, engaging with the sustainable development through business plan.	ST					x		
P	Additional funding from state budget or European funds, to tackle pollution and climate change.	MT					x	x	
P	Environmental law enforcement and compliance in all areas, especially in the coastal zone.	ST					x		
B, P	Empowering political decision – makers/local authorities (city councils, local councils) in implementing strategies.	ST/MT					x		
C, R, B, P	Development of an integrated legal system, adapted to Romanian coastal zone, within Black Sea Strategy.	MT					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Financing renewable energy projects and promoting them	MT/LT			x		x	x	x
C, R, B, P	Promoting sustainable fishing methods and techniques through protecting resources and other incentives/compensation	ST/MT		x			x	x	
B	Emissions reductions through upgrade of plants and equipment	MT	x	x	x		x	x	x
C, R, B, P	Promoting and developing responsible and sustainable tourism in a changing environment	ST/MT	x				x	x	
B, R, P	Sustainable approaches for surface transportation, reducing greenhouse emissions	MT		x		x	x	x	x
C, R, B, P	Waste management (recycling, recovery, monitoring)	ST		x			x		
C, R, B, P	Technology transfer platform from public to private sector	ST/MT					x		
C, R, B, P	Sustainable use and management of natural resources	ST/MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	
C, R, B, P	Refurbishment of existing tourist areas	ST/MT					x		
C, R, B, P	Developing an easy reporting system of field	MT					x	x	

	reality to decision makers								
C, R, B, P	Engaging local people in public consultations and decision – making in local regulations	ST					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Developing methodological norms for enforcement of law	ST/MT					x		
C, R, B, P	Restructuring the mechanisms designed to promote best practices in environmental protection	MT					x		
C, R, B, P	Restructuring mechanisms designed to prevent pollution	MT					x		x
C, R, B, P	Restructuring mechanisms designed to monitor and report real situation of Black Sea ecosystems	MT					x		x
C, R, B, P	Restructuring mechanisms designed for applying sanctions	ST/MT					x		
C, R, B, P	Restructuring mechanisms designed to reward good practices	ST/MT					x		
C, R, B, P	Restructuring mechanisms designed to ensure transparency in law-making processes	ST/MT					x		
C, R, P	The formal introduction of marine education within the curriculum for schools	MT/LT					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Development of an educational platform between public and private institutions	ST					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Fostering citizen and private organizations participation through innovative programs such as selective collection or online platforms as Citizen Watch, with possible rewards.	ST/MT					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Communicating about climate change with stakeholders	ST					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Changing unsustainable patterns of consumption and production, in order to reduce the amount of waste	ST/MT					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Applying for green programs as RABLA or CASA VERDE	ST					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Creating a framework for recycling biodegradable waste from household waste	ST/MT					x	x	
GENDER EQUALITY									
B, P	Expansion of port facilities in Schengen area	MT/LT					x	x	x
P	Allocate a higher percentage of GDP on environmental protection	MT/LT					x		
B, R, P	Developing business strategy/plan using the concept of sustainable development	ST					x	x	
B, R, P	Law update and improvement on the exploitation of natural marine resources, in context of sustainable development	ST/MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	
P	Environmental law enforcement and compliance in all areas, especially in the coastal zone	ST					x		

B, P	Empowering political decision – makers/local authorities (city councils, local councils) in implementing strategies	ST/MT						x		
C, R, B, P	Development of an integrated legal system, adapted to Romanian coastal zone, within Black Sea Strategy.	MT						X	x	
C, R, B, P	Promoting sustainable fishing methods and techniques through protecting resources and other incentives/compensation	ST/MT		x				x	x	
B	Emissions reductions through upgrade of plants and equipment	MT	x	x	x			x	x	x
B, R, P	Introducing the profession of environmental auditor in COR	ST/MT						x	x	
C, R, B, P	Promoting and developing responsible and sustainable tourism in a changing environment	ST/MT	x					x	x	
B, R, P	Sustainable approaches for surface transportation, reducing greenhouse emissions	MT		x		x		x	x	x
C, R, B, P	Waste management (recycling, recovery, monitoring)	ST		x				x		
C, R, B, P	Technology transfer platform from public to private sector	ST/MT						x		
C, R, B, P	Sustainable use and management of natural resources	ST/MT	x	x	x	x		x	x	
C, R, B, P	Refurbishment of existing tourist areas	ST/MT						x		
C, R, B, P	Developing an easy reporting system of field reality to decision makers	MT						x	x	
C, R, B, P	Engaging local people in public consultations and decision – making in local regulations	ST						x	x	
C, R, B, P	Restructuring the mechanisms designed to promote best practices in environmental protection	MT						x		
C, R, B, P	Restructuring mechanisms designed to prevent pollution	MT						x		x
C, R, B, P	Restructuring mechanisms designed to monitor and report real situation of Black Sea ecosystems	MT						x		x
C, R, B, P	Restructuring mechanisms designed for applying sanctions	ST/MT						x		
C, R, B, P	Restructuring mechanisms designed to reward good practices	ST/MT						x		
C, R, B, P	Restructuring mechanisms designed to ensure transparency in law-making processes	ST/MT						x		
C, R, P	The formal introduction of marine education within the curriculum for schools	MT/LT						x	x	
C, R, B, P	Development of an educational platform between public and private institutions	ST						x	x	
C, R, B, P	Fostering citizen and private organizations participation through innovative programs	ST/MT						x	x	

	such as selective collection or online platforms as Citizen Watch, with possible rewards.								
C, R, B, P	Communicating about climate change with stakeholders	ST					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Changing unsustainable patterns of consumption and production, in order to reduce the amount of waste	ST/MT					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Applying for green programs as RABLA or CASA VERDE	ST					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Creating a framework for recycling biodegradable waste from household waste	ST/MT					x	x	
ETHICS									
C, R, B, P	Promoting and developing responsible and sustainable tourism in a changing environment	ST/MT	x				x	x	
C, R, B, P	Promoting sustainable fishing methods and techniques through protecting resources and other incentives/compensation	ST/MT		x			x	x	
B, R, P	Sustainable approaches for surface transportation, reducing greenhouse emissions	MT		x		x	x	x	x
C, R, B, P	Water treatment measures to improve ecological value, use of ponds, plants and terraces	MT/LT	x	x			x	x	x
C, R, B, P	Waste management (recycling, recovery, monitoring)	ST		x			x		
B, P	Analysis and evaluation of business opportunities, engaging with the sustainable development through business plan.	ST					X		
B, R, P	Developing business strategy/plan using the concept of sustainable development	ST					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Sustainable use and management of natural resources	ST/MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	
B, R, P	Regulating exploitation and production activities in the Black Sea, through ACROPO authority	ST		x			x	x	
B, P	Expansion of port facilities in Schengen area	MT/LT				x	x	x	x
C, R, B, P	Refurbishment of existing tourist areas	ST/MT					x		
P	Environmental law enforcement and compliance in all areas, especially in the coastal zone.	ST					X		
B, P	Transposition and implementation of European Union law	ST			X		X	x	
B, P	Empowering political decision – makers/local authorities (city councils, local councils) in implementing strategies	ST/MT					x		
B, R, P	Law update and improvement on the exploitation of natural marine resources, in context of sustainable development	ST/MT	x	x	x	x	x	x	

C, R, B, P	Developing an easy reporting system of field reality to decision makers	MT					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Engaging local people in public consultations and decision – making in local regulations	ST					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Developing methodological norms for enforcement of law	ST/MT					x		
C, R, B, P	Development of an integrated legal system, adapted to Romanian coastal zone, within Black Sea Strategy.	MT					x	x	
P	Updating and centralizing Romanian legislation in accordance with European Union law	ST/MT					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Restructuring the mechanisms designed to promote best practices in environmental protection	MT					x		
C, R, B, P	Restructuring mechanisms designed to prevent pollution	MT					x		x
C, R, B, P	Restructuring mechanisms designed to monitor and report real situation of Black Sea ecosystems	MT					x		x
C, R, B, P	Restructuring mechanisms designed for applying sanctions	ST/MT					x		
C, R, B, P	Restructuring mechanisms designed to reward good practices	ST/MT					x		
C, R, B, P	Restructuring mechanisms designed to ensure transparency in law-making processes	ST/MT					x		
P	Allocate a higher percentage of GDP on environmental protection	MT/LT					x		
C, B, P	Allocate a higher percentage of GDP on research	MT/LT					x		
C, R, P	The formal introduction of marine education within the curriculum for schools	MT/LT					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Development of an educational platform between public and private institutions	ST					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Fostering citizen and private organizations participation through innovative programs such as selective collection or online platforms as Citizen Watch, with possible rewards.	ST/MT					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Communicating about climate change with stakeholders	ST					x	x	
B, R, P	Introducing the profession of environmental auditor in COR	ST/MT					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Changing unsustainable patterns of consumption and production, in order to reduce the amount of waste	ST/MT					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Applying for green programs as RABLA or CASA VERDE	ST					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Creating a framework for recycling biodegradable waste from household waste	ST/MT					x	x	

GOVERNANCE										
C, R, B, P	Promoting and developing responsible and sustainable tourism in a changing environment	ST/MT	x					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Promoting sustainable fishing methods and techniques through protecting resources and other incentives/compensation	ST/MT		x				x	x	
B, R, P	Sustainable approaches for surface transportation, reducing greenhouse emissions	MT		x		x		x	x	x
B	Emissions reductions through upgrade of plants and equipment	MT	x	x	x			x	x	x
C, R, B, P	Water treatment measures to improve ecological value, use of ponds, plants and terraces	MT/LT	x	x				x	x	x
B, P	Improvement of port reception facilities and services for processing or taking over waste from ships or other economic agents.	MT		x		x		x	x	
C, R, B, P	Waste management (recycling, recovery, monitoring)	ST		x				x		
B, P	Analysis and evaluation of business opportunities, engaging with the sustainable development through business plan.	ST						X		
C, R, B, P	Technology transfer platform from public to private sector	ST/MT						x		
B, R, P	Developing business strategy/plan using the concept of sustainable development	ST						x	x	
C, R, B, P	Sustainable use and management of natural resources	ST/MT	x	x	x	x		x	x	
B, R, P	Regulating exploitation and production activities in the Black Sea, through ACROPO authority	ST		x				x	x	
B, P	Expansion of port facilities in Schengen area	MT/LT					x	x	x	x
P	Additional funding from state budget or European funds, to tackle pollution and climate change.	MT						x	x	
P	Environmental law enforcement and compliance in all areas, especially in the coastal zone.	ST						x		
B, P	Transposition and implementation of European Union law	ST			x			x	x	
B, P	Empowering political decision – makers/local authorities (city councils, local councils) in implementing strategies	ST/MT						x		
B, R, P	Law update and improvement on the exploitation of natural marine resources, in context of sustainable development	ST/MT	x	x	x	x		x	x	
C, R, B, P	Developing an easy reporting system of field reality to decision makers	MT						x	x	
C, R, B, P	Engaging local people in public consultations and decision – making in local	ST						x	x	

	regulations								
C, R, B, P	Developing methodological norms for enforcement of law	ST/MT					x		
C, R, B, P	Development of an integrated legal system, adapted to Romanian coastal zone, within Black Sea Strategy	MT					x	x	
P	Updating and centralizing Romanian legislation in accordance with European Union law	ST/MT					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Financing renewable energy projects and promoting them	MT/LT			x		x	x	x
C, R, B, P	Restructuring the mechanisms designed to promote best practices in environmental protection	MT					x		
C, R, B, P	Restructuring mechanisms designed to prevent pollution	MT					x		x
C, R, B, P	Restructuring mechanisms designed to monitor and report real situation of Black Sea ecosystems	MT					x		x
C, R, B, P	Restructuring mechanisms designed for applying sanctions	ST/MT					x		
C, R, B, P	Restructuring mechanisms designed to reward good practices	ST/MT					x		
C, R, B, P	Restructuring mechanisms designed to ensure transparency in law-making processes	ST/MT					x		
P	Allocate a higher percentage of GDP on environmental protection	MT/LT					x		
C, B, P	Allocate a higher percentage of GDP on research	MT/LT					x		
C, R, P	The formal introduction of marine education within the curriculum for schools	MT/LT					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Development of an educational platform between public and private institutions	ST					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Fostering citizen and private organizations participation through innovative programs such as selective collection or online platforms as Citizen Watch, with possible rewards.	ST/MT					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Communicating about climate change with stakeholders	ST					x	x	
B, R, P	Introducing the profession of environmental auditor in COR	ST/MT					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Changing unsustainable patterns of consumption and production, in order to reduce the amount of waste	ST/MT					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Applying for green programs as RABLA or CASA VERDE	ST					x	x	
C, R, B, P	Creating a framework for recycling biodegradable waste from household waste	ST/MT					x	x	

Table 19 Final roadmap produced by the participants of the workshop in Constanta, Romania

The RRI dimension that scored the biggest number of actions was *Governance* and also the biggest number of action identified are related to the political domain. This may be due to the lack of specific legislation in the Black Sea region in order to mitigate climate change impact. Development of current and specific legislation for the Black Sea area and its implementation can make major differences in time, helping to mitigate climate changes impact on this area.

Through this MML workshop, the participants generated 41 actions, assembled three actions groups (economic, political and social), that are bound to each other and which have contributed to the development of the final roadmap, which shows a connection between all the 41 proposed measures, even though they are from different levels.

The majority of participants understood and clarified issues related to RRI principles and most of them said that they will apply RRI principles in their daily work and daily life.

The workshop provided a good opportunity for participants to interact and share their opinions with others through an interactive method, about which they were very excited because they were able to express their opinions, opinions that helped shape concrete actions to mitigate climate change in the Black Sea region.

5.3.5 Deep-sea Mining

5.3.5.1 Description

The quantity of mineral occupying the ocean floor is potentially large. Deep-sea mining is concerned with the retrieval of minerals to ensure security of supply, and fill a gap in the market where either recycling is not possible or adequate, or the burden on terrestrial mines is too great. The most likely targets for deep-sea mining are polymetallic sulphides, manganese nodules and cobalt-rich ferromanganese crusts. These minerals are essential to make sure we have mobile phones, cars, communications, etc. Potential deep-sea mining sites are situated between 1,000 and 6,000m below the ocean surface, often in highly vulnerable ecosystems and biodiversity hotspots, where many unknown marine species are yet to be identified.

Numerous organisations within the EU are presently getting organised, both as technology providers and as mine operators, should deep-sea mining start as a commercial activity. However, experts claim that the existing knowledge of the deep-sea environment is scarce and therefore we currently cannot properly assess the environmental impacts of deep-sea mining. In addition, there is no legal framework for the activity and the debate on whether or not we need deep-sea mining is just starting.

5.3.5.2 Results of the workshop in Italy (the Adriatic Sea) held by OMM, Molfetta

In Molfetta, OMM organised a workshop to discuss whether minerals in the ocean floor should be exploited and how.

During spring 2014 Global Petroleum Limited Holding, an oil and gas upstream exploration company presently focused on Africa and the Mediterranean, received authorization from the Italian government to proceed to the environmental impact evaluation related to four licences to research hydrocarbons in maritime domain of Bari and Brindisi districts in Apulia. This region in southern Italy on the Adriatic Sea, spreads on 2,986 km² and includes the cities of Giovinazzo, Bari, Fasano, Mola di Bari, Monopoli, Brindisi, Ostuni, Molfetta, Carovigno, Torchiarolo, Polignano a Mare.

The first phase of hydrocarbons research activity is the geological study with the acquisition of seismic data by the method of seismic reflection known as “air-gun” which foresees the use of compressed air energy source. Since Global Petroleum has been authorized to proceed to the geological study in Apulia region, scientists and environmentalists raised several concerns regarding the capacity of the oil company to evaluate carefully the characteristics of the marine ecosystem and biodiversity. At the moment there is a contentious between the Apulia region and Global Petroleum and it is not known how long it will take until it is resolved, which makes it a very relevant topic for local stakeholders.

The topic of the workshop was “*Sustainable sea mining and Responsible Research and Innovation*”. The workshop aimed at answering the triggering question: “*What Responsible and Innovation actions are needed to make seabed mining sustainable?*”

Table 20 shows the roadmap of actions suggested during this workshop.

WHY - overall objectives for making a roadmap and a common vision		Sustainable seabed mining and Responsible Research and Innovation							
WHO Stakeholder target group(s) Choose from : Citizens/CSOs/NGOs (C), Business/Industry (B), Researchers & Academia (R), Policymakers & implementers (P) Other (Please specify)	WHAT Action	WHEN How long will it take to complete the action? short (now-1 year), medium (2-5 years), long term (over 5 years)	OVERALL GOAL: Which societal challenge will the action contribute to? Choose from:						
			Health, democratic change and well-being	Food security, agriculture, marine and maritime and inland water research, bioeconomy	Secure, clean and efficient energy	Smart, green and integrated transport	Climate action, environment, resource efficiency, and raw materials	Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies	Secure societies
PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT									
C, R, P	Build and reinforce scientific citizenship	MT	x	x				x	x
R	Ensure that all steps of extraction activities are evidence based and monitored by super-parties organizations	LT	x	x					
C	Organizing society toward happiness	LT	x	x					
C	Engage citizens and institutions in monitoring and protection of urban health through citizen science programmes	MT		x			x	x	
R	Reinforce knowledge of environmental data available through cartography of seabed and heavy metals and promote public engagement through knowledge sharing platforms	MT					x		x
C, R, B, P	Local participation in coastal and seabed landscape maintenance	MT	x	x			x		
C, R, B, P	Empowering populations to make decision for their future	LT	x	x	x				
R	Youngsters as guarantors of sustainable development	MT	x	x			x	x	
SCIENCE EDUCATION									
C, R, P	Build and reinforce scientific citizenship	MT	x	x				x	x
C, R, P	Engage citizens and research institutions in monitoring, protection and conservation of coastal actions, the interface between land and sea	MT	x	x			x		
R, P	Examine the correlation between the exploitation of seabed mineral resources and the bioavailability of heavy metals in sea food	MT		x					
R	Promote research and innovation to make currently available technologies less invasive for the marine environment	LT	x						
C	Engage citizens and institutions in monitoring and protection of urban health through citizen science programmes	MT		x			x	x	
R	Build and finance a European agency for marine research and long term impact assessment related to the exploitation of	MT		x					

	sea natural resources								
R, P	Reinforce knowledge of environmental data available through cartography of seabed and heavy metals and promote public engagement through knowledge sharing platforms	MT					x		
C, R, B, P	Local participation in coastal and seabed landscape maintenance	MT	x	x			x		
R	Apply and update all safeguard measures to preserve fishery resources and food security	MT		x					
C, R, B, P	Empowering populations to make decision for their future	LT	x	x	x				
C, P	Promote public engagement in the knowledge of limits, problems, doubts related to this new frontier of the mining industry	MT						x	
R	Youngsters as guarantors of sustainable development	MT	x	x			x	x	
R, B	Safeguard cetaceans during seabed mining	LT		x			x		
OPEN ACCESS									
C, R, P	Build and reinforce scientific citizenship	MT	x	x				x	x
R	Ensure that all steps of extraction activities are evidence based and monitored by super-parties organizations	LT	x	x					
C, R, P	Engage citizens and research institutions in monitoring, protection and conservation of coastal actions, the interface between land and sea	MT	x	x			x		
R, P	Examine the correlation between the exploitation of seabed mineral resources and the bioavailability of heavy metals in sea food	MT		x					
R	Promote research and innovation to make currently available technologies less invasive for the marine environment	LT	x						
C	Engage citizens and institutions in monitoring and protection of urban health through citizen science programmes	MT		x			x	x	
R	Build and finance a European agency for marine research and long term impact assessment related to the exploitation of sea natural resources	MT		x					
R, P	Reinforce knowledge of environmental data available through cartography of seabed and heavy metals and promote public engagement through knowledge sharing platforms	MT					x		
C, R, B, P	Local participation in coastal and seabed landscape maintenance	MT	x	x			x		
C, R, B, P	Empowering populations to make decision for their future	LT	x	x	x				
C	Implement environmental education programmes for grown-up	MT		x			x		
C, P	Promote public engagement in the	MT						x	

	knowledge of limits, problems, doubts related to this new frontier of the mining industry								
GENDER EQUALITY									
C, R, P	Build and reinforce scientific citizenship	MT	x	x				x	x
C	Engage citizens and institutions in monitoring and protection of urban health through citizen science programmes	MT		x			x	x	
C	Implement environmental education programmes for grown-up	MT		x			x		
ETHICS									
C, R, P	Build and reinforce scientific citizenship.(10 votes)	MT	x	x				x	x
C	Engage citizens and institutions in monitoring and protection of urban health through citizen science programmes	MT		x			x	x	
R, B	Safeguard cetaceans during seabed mining	LT		x			x		
GOVERNANCE									
C, R, P	Engage citizens and research institutions in monitoring, protection and conservation of coastal actions, the interface between land and sea	MT	x	x			x		
C	Engage citizens and institutions in monitoring and protection of urban health through citizen science programmes	MT		x			x	x	
R	Build and finance a European agency for marine research and long term impact assessment related to the exploitation of sea natural resources	MT		x					
R, P	Reinforce knowledge of environmental data available through cartography of seabed and heavy metals and promote public engagement through knowledge sharing platforms	MT					x		
C, R, B, P	Empowering populations to make decision for their future	LT	x	x	x				
R	Youngsters as guarantors of sustainable development	MT	x	x			x	x	
R, B	Promote in Italy tax breaks, subsidies, consultations financed by the government for SME to go forward any kind of eco-innovation and green/blue-economy				x	x	x		
B	Update legislation tools to improve international governance of the oceans and implement technological innovation to reduce the extension of shadow zones of the integrated marine surveillance.	MT		x					
OTHER (Media)									
R, P	Promote public engagement in the knowledge of limits, problems, doubts related to this new frontier of the mining industry.	MT						x	

Table 20 Final roadmap produced by the participants of the workshop in Molfetta, Italy

The RRI dimension that scored the biggest number of actions at the workshop was *Science Education*. This may be due to the lack of an exhaustive knowledge of the impact of seabed mining on the sustainability of the sea management that could reassure civil society as a whole.

5.3.5.3 Results of the workshop in Portugal (the Atlantic Sea) held by EurOcean, the Azores

In the Azores, the workshop organised by EurOcean looked at how deep-sea mining in the North Atlantic could be an opportunity to do things right in terms of allowing society to decide how it should be performed and controlled, if it ever takes place. In 2017, Portugal applied to the UN Commission on the Limits of the Continental Shelf to expand the country’s jurisdiction beyond its Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ). The continental shelf extension request would make Portugal in the owner of 3.8 million km² of the North Atlantic sea floor. While a decision is being made, participants discussed what is at stake and what are the benefits, the challenges and the responsibilities of any country that wishes to start exploring what lies at the deep-sea floor and below.

The topic of the workshop was “Deep-sea mining in the North Atlantic... an opportunity to do things right”. The workshop aimed at answering the triggering question: “What Responsible Research and Innovation actions are needed to make exploiting the deep-sea in the North Atlantic sustainable?”

Table 21 shows the roadmap of actions suggested during this workshop.

WHY - overall objectives for making a roadmap and a common vision		TO ENSURE THAT THE DECISION-MAKING PROCESS ON DEEP-SEA MINING IS PARTICIPATIVE, TRANSPARENT AND ALLOWS FOR PUBLIC DELIBERATION							
WHO Stakeholder target group(s) Choose from : Citizens/CSOs/NGOs (C), Business/Industry (B), Researchers & Academia (R), Policymakers & implementers (P) Other (Please specify)	WHAT Action	WHEN How long will it take to complete the action? short (now-1 year), medium (2-5 years), long term (over 5 years)	OVERALL GOAL: Which societal challenge will the action contribute to? Choose from:						
			Health, democratic change and well-being	Food security, agriculture, marine and maritime and inland water research, bioeconomy	Secure, clean and efficient energy	Smart, green and integrated transport	Climate action, environment, resource efficiency, and raw materials	Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies	Secure societies
PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT									
R	Promote science dissemination actions	ST	x	x			x	x	
C	Include ocean literacy in all school programmes	MT	x	x			x	x	
SCIENCE EDUCATION									
C	Disseminate information about DSM threats and risks	ST	x	x			x	x	
P	Invest on the training of politicians and public institutions technicians	ST	x					x	
OPEN ACCESS									
R	Invest on research about the deep-sea resources and the DSM impacts	MT		x			x		
GENDER EQUALITY									
C	Create laws to oblige public participation and to make the decision-making process transparent	MT	x					x	

C	Promote exhibitions, debates, documentaries, outreach action and science news on TV	ST	x	x			x	x	
ETHICS									
B	Create a legal framework for DSM	MT	x	x			x	x	
B	Oblige DSM companies to conduct and pay pre-feasibility studies and monitoring programmes	ST	x	x			x	x	
P	Oblige politicians to demonstrate that their decisions are science-based	MT	x	x			x	x	
GOVERNANCE									
P	Incentive the circular economy	LT	x				x	x	
P	Impose a moratorium on DSM until the knowledge level is sufficient to support decisions	ST	x	x			x	x	
C	Promote a deliberative democracy in which the public decides	LT	x					x	
B	Profits of DSM companies should revert to the local societies	ST	x				x	x	
R	Invest on the development of new technologies and materials that do not require deep-sea resources	MT	x	x			x	x	

Table 21 Final roadmap produced by the participants of the workshop in Ribeira Grande, Azores, Portugal

The roadmap includes 16 actions with evident relations to the six RRI dimensions, with Governance being the most targeted of them all. The results suggest that the roadmap implementation requires political enforcement to begin with. However, the results could have been different if more policymakers and implementers attended the workshop. It is likely that they would argue that not every initiative needs the political power to start and that the general public, NGOs, scientists and entrepreneurs can also initiate a few of the actions in the roadmap. Nevertheless, the results of the workshop suggest that society believes that RRI will never be in full effect without a strong political will.

Concerning the hot topic itself, the results suggest that stakeholders feel that:

- The need to conduct deep-sea mining is yet to be confirmed, especially if the circular economy is implemented;
- The decision to carry out deep-sea mining should only take place after the level of knowledge about the deep-sea and its biodiversity is much larger than the existing one;
- Society needs to be much better informed about the deep-sea and deep-sea mining; and
- Any decision-making process related to deep-sea mining needs to allow for public deliberation.

The most voted action provided the title of the roadmap emerging from the workshop: *To ensure that the decision-making process on deep-sea mining is participative, transparent and allows for public deliberation*. Hence, the achieved common vision is about ensuring that the decision-making process on deep-sea mining is participative, transparent and allows for public deliberation. During the workshop, several statements suggested that important misunderstandings exist about what is already decided on deep-sea mining. The existing communication channels between governance, public, industry, NGOs and scientists therefore may be not functioning properly. The actions able to improve efficient communication, generate plural debates and disseminate reliable data and information are therefore recommended to make the common vision a reality. The participants were also highly concerned with the lack of room for the general public to decide what will take place about deep-sea mining.

6 Workshop Assessment by Participants

In order to effectively determine the success of the local MML workshops, a standard Participant Questionnaire was developed by the WP3 leader in collaboration with the Coordinator and WP6 leader. The questionnaire was translated into the language of the country where the workshop was taking place and collected the feedback of participants on the workshops and RRI. The survey was divided into four sections:

- Who are you:** the participants responded to a set of checkbox multiple choice questions about their professional orientation and their personal aims to participate in the MARINA workshop;
- The Workshop:** the goal was to evaluate the satisfaction of the participants with the overall organization and implementation of the workshop;
- Responsible Research and Innovation:** considering that the aim of the workshops was to allow the integration of RRI principles into specific actions, it was deemed essential to assess the participants' knowledge and understanding of RRI before and after the workshop and measure how important they thought RRI was;
- Conclusions:** the participants were requested to provide comments related to the MARINA project and the workshop.

The questionnaire was handed to all participants at the end of the workshop and was returned by as many as 343, which is almost 78% of the total number of stakeholders who joined the workshops. The results of the survey outcomes are demonstrated in *Figure 30*, *Figure 31*, *Figure 32*, *Figure 33*, *Figure 34*, and *Figure 35*.

Figure 30 Satisfaction with the workshop

The assessment of the second round of local MML workshops is shown in *Figure 30*, which demonstrates that almost 93% of the respondents were either “*Very satisfied*” or “*Satisfied*” with the overall implementation of the workshop. 1.2% of the respondents indicated their dissatisfaction but no one had a very dissatisfying experience.

Considering the multidisciplinary group of stakeholders who participated in each MML workshop it seemed important for the MARINA partners to find out their personal motivations to join MARINA initiatives, which could feed the next steps of the project. As presented in *Figure 31*, in which the respondents were free to choose more than one answer from a set of 12 checkboxes, nearly half of the respondents indicated that their motivation to participate in the workshop was “*to work on research questions that can solve societal and economic problems*”. A third of the respondents expressed the opinion that one of the main reasons they accepted the invitation to join the workshops was “*to produce results that follow ethical principles*” (110 respondents) and “*to engage with a wide range of different people from society (who have different jobs, interests, etc.)*”. It is worth noting that 97 of the respondents (29%) participated in the workshops in order “*to learn a participatory method*.” 91 of them (27%) wanted “*to access freely available data (documents, publications, findings)*” and “*to anticipate future opportunities, weaknesses, challenges, risks of problems*”. Finally, only 47 respondents (14%) participated “*to speak their mind and to influence decision-making policies*”.

Figure 31 Participant’s personal aims to participate in the workshop

The answers to the question “What is most useful to you?” are reflected in Figure 32. The respondents were asked to mark from a set of six checkboxes which topics are essential for them. The majority of the respondents (180) indicated that “Research related to the marine challenge discussed” was very useful for them while “Responsible Research and Innovation tools” and “Participatory processes” ranked at the second and third position of preference respectively. “Policy agendas” was the least preferred among the respondents.

Figure 32 “What is useful for you?”

Figure 33 shows the respondents' knowledge of RRI before and after the workshop. There was a significant increase in the number of respondents who understood the RRI principles very well after the workshop, climbing from 59 to 84. The drop in the number of respondents who had a moderate knowledge of the RRI approach from 101 before the event to 90 after the event may possibly be explained by the increase in the percentage of respondents who acquired a very good understanding following the completion of the workshop.

The dramatic decline in the number of respondents who either did not understand very well or had no understanding of the RRI principles from 93 before the workshop to 17 after the workshop is an immediate result of the actions undertaken by the MARINA organizers to introduce the participants to RRI. Adequate time was given to demonstrate the RRI concept and dimensions and to answer questions related to their implementation in real life.

Figure 33 also demonstrates whether the respondents understood how to implement RRI aspects in their daily work / daily life following the completion of the workshop. A considerable percentage of stakeholders (57%), have acquired enough understanding to apply RRI principles in their daily lives after the event.

The success of communications and presentations of the RRI principles to the workshop participants is deduced from comparing the number of respondents who either had not understood them very well or had had no understanding of how to implement the RRI dimensions before and after the workshop. While 102 individuals fell into this category before their participation in the workshop, the number dropped to 30 after it.

Figure 33 Participants' knowledge of RRI before and after the workshop

Finally, the analysis of the questionnaire data showed that almost 85% of the respondents were planning to integrate the RRI principles in their work / daily life as demonstrated in Figure 34.

Figure 34 Participants indicate that they are planning to apply RRI in their work/ daily life

Figure 35 "How important is it to you...?"

The question “How important is it to you...?” aimed at establishing which aspects of research and innovation mattered most to respondents. Figure 35 presents the answers to this question. 68% and 66% of the respondents marked as highly important “that research and innovation respect the environment and natural resources” and “that research and innovation anticipate future opportunities, challenges and risks for the next generations” respectively, giving these two topics the biggest importance. 92.5% of the respondents believed that it was either important or highly important for them “that politicians and policies support society-centred research and innovation programs” while 88% of them touched upon the Ethics dimension indicating that it was either important or highly important “that research and innovation respect ethical principles”.

Surprisingly, Gender Equality has been considered as highly important or important by the respondents in the processes of research and innovation considering that 70% of the respondents believed that “gender equality is supported throughout research and innovation processes”, which is in opposition with the results of the individual workshops where the gender dimension had the least number of actions. In addition, a thorough analysis of the outcomes shows that 28 respondents indicated that this aspect was either less important or not important at all. This represents the greatest number of responses as “Less important” and “Not at all important” for the question “How important is it to you...?” One possible explanation is that the link between the topic discussed during the workshop and Gender Equality was not obvious to the respondents.

While 176 respondents believed that it was important “to learn about RRI”, only 78 of them indicated that it was highly important. This represents the lowest amount of responses as “highly important” to this question.

7 Conclusions

The workshops succeeded in engaging 443 participants from a diverse spectrum of stakeholders, including citizens, NGO representatives, researchers, business representatives and policymakers who shared knowledge and actions to tackle five marine challenges: Marine Biotechnology, Renewable Energy, Sea Transportation, Marine Changes Caused by Climate, and Deep-sea Mining.

A total of 485 actions were proposed by the stakeholders across the 20 MML workshops. The analysis of the combined results revealed that *Governance* was linked to the greatest number of actions generated by the participants (351 out of 485 actions), followed closely by *Open Access* (297 actions) and *Public Engagement* (264 actions), while *Gender Equality* was the least considered RRI dimension. The results of the workshops suggest that society believes that the implementation of the RRI relies on a strong political will.

Besides linking the actions with the RRI dimensions, the workshops aimed at associating the proposed actions with seven societal challenges as a means to assess the level of contribution of the marine field. The analysis has revealed that the greatest number of actions were connected to the societal challenge of *Climate action, environment, resource efficiency and raw materials* (292 actions), while only a limited number of actions correlated with the challenge of *Secure societies*.

The final RRI roadmaps represent the combined vision of the participants to bring sustainability to the marine sector, and provide concrete pathways to ensure Blue Growth in Europe while taking the needs of society into account. The roadmaps also show that close cooperation between citizens, policymakers, researchers and businesses is vital for achieving this. A successful response to marine challenges predominantly calls for:

- Raising awareness among all stakeholders, from the general public and business professionals to researchers and policymakers about the potential, the impact and the consequences of the marine societal challenges;
- Active engagement and cooperation among actors (citizens, industry, academia, policymakers) at a national and European level;
- Transferring knowledge, information and best practices across interested stakeholder groups to fully exploit its potential;
- Creating research infrastructures and funding schemes to allow the enhancement of science education and to bridge the gap between academia and industry;
- Enhancing, developing and implementing existing and future policies and regulations;
- Introducing marine related curricula for different educational level.

The organization and implementation of the workshops was assessed in a positive manner by the participants through a satisfaction questionnaire distributed at the end of each workshop. The vast majority of the respondents highlighted that their understanding and knowledge of the RRI principles and how to implement them was increased after the completion of the workshop.

The findings of the second phase of international MML workshops corroborate the vision of the Blue Society, developed by the Sea for Society project funded by the 7th Framework Programme of the European Union. The Blue Society promotes “innovation through a close collaboration between researchers, entrepreneurs and decision-makers, in order to find solutions to meet society’s present and future needs”.

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